

UTILIZATION OF NATIONAL GUARD CYBER FORCES IN TITLE 32 STATUS FOR NATIONAL CYBER MISSIONS

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David A. Schroeder

<https://daveschroeder.org>

<https://t32cyber.org>

Dissertation Committee:

Professor Cody Welu (Chair), Dakota State University

Dean Mary Bell, Dakota State University

Professor Kristin Eschenfelder, University of Wisconsin–Madison

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Student Name: Dave Schroeder Student ID: 101130272

Dissertation Title: Utilization of National Guard Cyber Forces in Title 32 Status for National Cyber Missions

N/A

Graduate Office Verification: DocuSigned by: *Brianna Mae Feldhaus* Date: 03/10/2026
F44C8D9E621C417...

Dissertation Chair/Co-Chair: Signed by: *Cody Welu* Date: 03/10/2026
3715959B504F439...
Print Name: Cody Welu

Dissertation Chair/Co-Chair: _____ Date: _____
Print Name: _____

Committee Member: Signed by: *Mary Bell* Date: 03/10/2026
D94F2A6A1EAC481...
Print Name: Mary Bell

Committee Member: Signed by: *Kristin Eschenfelder* Date: 03/10/2026
E0B9F0283C9644A...
Print Name: Kristin Eschenfelder

Committee Member: _____ Date: _____
Print Name: _____

Committee Member: _____ Date: _____
Print Name: _____

DECLARATION

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I declare that the dissertation describes original work that has not previously been presented for the award of any other degree of any institution.

At the time of publication, I certify that my Collaborative Institutional Training Initiative (CITI) Program training is current through January 2, 2029.

The views and opinions expressed in this document are my own, and do not necessarily reflect those of any organization with which I am affiliated.

Signed,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'D. Schroeder', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

David A. Schroeder

ABSTRACT

There has been a debate for more than a decade in the United States about the precise role National Guard and Reserve military forces, and the National Guard in particular, can and should play in cyberspace operations. There are legal, policy, doctrinal, organizational, cultural, and bureaucratic issues that must be overcome or understood to employ National Guard forces for national cyber operations. Leaders in Congress, U.S. Cyber Command, and the National Guard have clearly articulated the need to leverage the cyber expertise in the National Guard in defense of the nation. Papers, articles, and hearings have repeatedly examined the existing landscape and proposed various solutions, including legislation and new organizations, but none has resulted in the type of comprehensive understanding required to clearly assign national cyberspace missions and functions while in Title 32 status beyond training. The National Guard is uniquely positioned as a reserve force with a dual federal and state status, and has over 4,000 cyber personnel with deep expertise in cyberspace operations and cybersecurity. In this dissertation we will examine the many proposals for solutions to date, with limited progress. This dissertation examines the existing law, policy, doctrine, and operational practice governing the use of National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status for national cyber missions. Using a multi-method qualitative design that integrates documentary analysis, a practitioner survey, and a focused case study, the study identifies where current authorities enable Title 32 mission support, where implementation barriers persist, and what governance mechanisms are needed for repeatable execution.

Keywords—cyber; cyber operations; cyberspace operations; defensive cyberspace operations; CO; DCO; DoDIN; cybersecurity; military; Army; ARNG; ANG; NG; NGB; National Guard; Title 10; Title 32; RC; reserve component integration; military cyber policy

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Executive Summary

This dissertation examines how the United States can more effectively employ National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status to support national cyber missions — particularly defensive missions — at scale and in a repeatable, legally sound manner. The study addresses a persistent problem of practice:

The United States lacks a consistently understood and consistently executed legal–policy–operational pathway to use Title 32 authorities for national cyber mission support beyond training, resulting in underutilized cyber capacity, uneven governance, and inconsistent resourcing and approval processes (see Section 1.3).

Purpose and Approach

The research investigates two questions: (RQ1) what elements of law and policy support or constrain Title 32 cyber mission support; and (RQ2) what precedent, expert opinion, and policy analysis enable or challenge such use. The study uses a multi-method qualitative design with embedded descriptive quantitative analysis, integrating:

- **Documentary analysis** of statutory authorities, DoD/NGB policy, joint doctrine, and precedent (coded as enabling, conditional, or constraining).
- A structured **expert survey** fielded June–October 2025 (151 respondents; 60 complete responses), combining Likert/0–10 items with nine open-ended prompts.
- A focused operational **case study** of the Wisconsin Federated Cyber Program (WIFCP) as an applied Title 32 mission-support pilot.

Together, these sources are used to assess whether and how Title 32 can support national cyber missions when training remains the paramount purpose and mission support is incidental to training.

Core Findings and Themes

Across all three data sources, the findings support the dissertation's central proposition: National Guard cyber forces can support certain national defensive cyber missions in Title 32 status if a training requirement is met under existing law and policy (see Section 5.2).

1) Existing authorities are more enabling than commonly assumed. The documentary record indicates that existing statutes and policy already support training-aligned operational support under Title 32, with most reviewed sources coded as enabling or conditionally enabling and none strictly prohibitive. A practical pathway centers on 32 U.S.C. §502(a) and (f) (routine training and additional duty) combined with DoD policy and precedent that treat mission outputs as permissible **incident to training** when properly scoped and documented (see Section 4.2).

2) Practitioners view Title 32 as feasible for specific mission types, but not without governance fixes. Survey respondents most strongly identified DoDIN operations and DCO-IDM as feasible under Title 32 with training alignment:

- DCO-IDM—Cyberspace Defense: 86.2%
- DoDIN Operations—Cyberspace Security: 86.2%

Support was more mixed for DCO-RA and OCO actions (Q10). Respondents also strongly agreed that Title 32 activities can be structured to meet training requirements *and* contribute to national mission objectives (55.9% strongly agree; 28.8% agree) (Q11).

At the same time, confidence that Title 32 can support national cyber missions without new legislation was moderate (mean 5.67/10), suggesting the barrier is often implementation clarity rather than statutory absence (Q18).

3) The dominant barriers are implementation ambiguity and institutional friction, not categorical legal prohibitions. Reflexive thematic analysis of open-ended responses produced five major themes:

1. Legal and policy ambiguity
2. Precedent exists but is poorly recognized
3. Operational feasibility and high training value
4. Cultural and institutional resistance
5. Demand for a federated cyber program

The most frequent subthemes were: **lack of implementing guidance** (31.4%), **national–state linkages** (28.1%), and **training–task alignment** (22.9%), followed by **active component bias** and **service parochialism** (see Section 4.4).

4) WIFCP demonstrates a workable Title 32 mission-support model and highlights force-management value. The WIFCP case study documents recurring, training-aligned mission support to a DoD partner in Title 32 status oriented to cybersecurity research and situational awareness. WIFCP also yielded strong mission-partner feedback (e.g., repeated statements that reporting was valuable and used for briefing/analysis) and an observed retention signal: two enlisted cyber Soldiers attributed reenlistment decisions to having meaningful real-world mission work in drilling status, representing an estimated \$800,000 retention impact based on stated replacement costs (see Section 4.5).

Key Recommendations

The dissertation's recommendations are organized into three clusters and explicitly trace to Chapter 4 evidence via a recommendation traceability matrix (see Section 5.4.4).

A) Organizational and Structural Clarify and institutionalize roles and relationships for Title 32 cyber support (see Section 5.4.1):

- Designate clear points of responsibility within U.S. Cyber Command and the National Guard Bureau for Title 32 cyber integration.
- Formalize mission manager roles for federated cyber programs (analogous to federated mission management constructs used elsewhere).
- Encourage state-level cyber integration working groups (TAG, state J-staff, key unit leaders) to align state and federal priorities.

B) Governance and Implementation Treat Title 32 cyber utilization as a cybersecurity risk governance problem and operationalize it with repeatable processes (see Section 5.4.2):

- Develop a formal "Title 32 Cyber Integration Profile" that specifies mission categories appropriate for Title 32 support (e.g., DCO-IDM, DoDIN Ops, cybersecurity situational awareness) and the conditions/expected outcomes.
- Establish standardized request/approval artifacts (templates for training alignment, legal review, and oversight).
- Create standardized metrics and reporting (e.g., number of federated programs, training hours logged on mission, mission impact assessments) to enable oversight and congressional visibility.

C) Strategic Alignment and Policy Development Explicitly align Title 32 cyber integration to national strategy and doctrine (see Section 5.4.3):

- Develop a National Guard Cyber Integration Strategy describing how Title 32 supports national objectives, how it relates to the Cyber Mission Force, and how it contributes to broader multi-domain posture.
- Use FY26 NDAA-directed questions as a roadmap for assessing authorities, leveraging civilian-acquired skills, and identifying billets/infrastructure and barriers.
- Incorporate lessons from pilots like WIFCP into joint/service doctrine/policy so federated Title 32 models become recognized options rather than one-off experiments.

Conclusion

The dissertation concludes that the United States does not primarily face an authority gap for employing National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status for certain defensive national cyber missions; it faces a governance and execution gap. Documentary evidence, practitioner consensus, and the WIFCP operational proof-of-concept converge on the same implication: a deliberate, structured Title 32 cyber integration approach is both feasible and necessary to scale Guard cyber capacity for national missions while preserving the training-first requirement and sustaining the force through meaningful work and retention benefits (see Chapters 4 and 5).

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IN MEMORIAM

In loving memory of my mother

Margaret Ann Schroeder

“Peggy”

May 15, 1948 — January 18, 2026

ACRONYMS

Acronym	Definition
AC	Active Component
AD	Active Duty
ADOS	Active Duty for Operational Support
ADOT	Active Duty for Other Than Training
ADT	Active Duty for Training
AFC	Army Futures Command
AFCYBER	Air Forces Cyber
AFSC	Air Force Specialty Code
AFTP	Additional Flight Training Period
AGR	Active Guard Reserve
AMU	American Military University
ANG	Air National Guard
AOC	Area of Concentration
AOR	Area of Responsibility
ARCYBER	Army Cyber Command
ARNG	Army National Guard
ASA	Air Sovereignty Alert
AT	Annual Training
A2/AD	Anti-Access/Area Denial
C2	Command and Control
CAI	College of Computing and Artificial Intelligence
CCMD	Combatant Command
CDIS	College of Computer, Data & Information Sciences
CFR	Code of Federal Regulations
CISA	Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency
CITI	House Armed Services Committee Subcommittee on Cyber, Information Technologies, and Innovation
CLAMO	Center for Law and Military Operations
CMF	Cyber Mission Force
CMT	Combat Mission Team
CNGB	Chief National Guard Bureau
CNGBI	Chief National Guard Bureau Instruction
CNMF	Cyber National Mission Force
CO	Cyberspace Operations
COCOM	Combatant Command
COF	Cyberspace Operations Forces
CONOPS	Concept of Operations

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Acronym	Definition
CONUS	Continental United States
CPT	Cyber Protection Team
CRT	Wisconsin Cyber Response Team
CSA	Combat Support Agency
CSC	Cyber Security Company
CSD	Cyber Security Detachment
CSF	Cybersecurity Framework
CST	Cyber Support Team
CSS	Central Security Service
CUI	Controlled Unclassified Information
CWC	Cyber Warfare Company
CWP	Cyber Warfare Publication
DCI	Defense Critical Infrastructure
DCO	Defensive Cyberspace Operations
DCOE	Defensive Cyberspace Operations Element
DCO-IDM	Defensive Cyberspace Operations–Internal Defensive Measures
DCO-RA	Defensive Cyberspace Operations–Response Actions
DEVGRU	Naval Special Warfare Development Group
DHS	Department of Homeland Security
DIA	Defense Intelligence Agency
DIB	Defense Industrial Base
DIME	Diplomatic, Information, Military, and Economic
DIRNSA/CHCSS	Director, National Security Agency/Chief, Central Security Service
DoD	Department of Defense
DoDD	Department of Defense Directive
DoDI	Department of Defense Instruction
DoDIN	Department of Defense Information Network
DOMOPS	Domestic Operations
DoW	Department of War (see DoD)
DP	Doctrine Publication
DSC	Dual-Status Commander
DSCA	Defense Support of Civil Authorities
DSCIR	Defense Support to Cyber Incident Response
DSRM	Design Science Research Methodology
DSU	Dakota State University
DTM	Directive-Type Memorandum
EMS	Electromagnetic Spectrum
EO	Executive Order
ERM	Enterprise Risk Management
EW	Electronic Warfare
FBI	Federal Bureau of Investigation
FCP	Federated Cyber Program
FEMA	Federal Emergency Management Agency
FIP	Federated Intelligence Program

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Acronym	Definition
FOUO	For Official Use Only
FTNGD	Full-Time National Guard Duty
FTNGD-AT	Full-Time National Guard Duty–Annual Training
FTNGD-OS	Full-Time National Guard Duty–Operational Support
FTNGD-OTD	Full-Time National Guard Duty–Other Training Duty
FTNGD-T	Full-Time National Guard Duty–Training
FY	Fiscal Year
G2	Intelligence Staff (G-2)
GG	General Government (civil service grade scale)
GOFO	General Officer / Flag Officer
GS	General Schedule (civil service grade scale)
HDA	Homeland Defense Activity
HASC	House Armed Services Committee
HD&GS	Homeland Defense and Global Security
IADS	Integrated Air Defense System
IADT	Initial Active Duty Training
IC	Intelligence Community
ICS	Industrial Control Systems
IDA	Institute for Defense Analyses
IDM	Internal Defensive Measures (in DCO-IDM)
IDT	Inactive Duty Training
ILE	Intermediate Level Education
INDOPACOM	United States Indo-Pacific Command
IO	Intelligence Oversight
IRB	Institutional Review Board
IROC	Intelligence Readiness and Operations Capability
IRT	Innovative Readiness Training
IT	Information Technology
JADC2	Joint All-Domain Command and Control
JAG	Judge Advocate General
JAGC	Judge Advocate General’s Corps
JIM	Joint, interorganizational, and multinational
JIOPC	Joint Information Operations Planners Course
JP	Joint Publication
JPME	Joint Professional Military Education
JRCC	Joint Reserve Component Command
JWICS	Joint Worldwide Intelligence Communications System
LRPF	Long Range Precision Fires
LTG	Lieutenant General
MDO	Multi-Domain Operations
METL	Mission Essential Task List
MI	Military Intelligence
MIPR	Military Interdepartmental Purchase Request
MOA	Memorandum of Agreement

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Acronym	Definition
MOS	Military Occupational Specialty
MOU	Memorandum of Understanding
MPA	Military Personnel Appropriations
MT&E	Man, Train, and Equip
MUOS	Mobile User Objective System
NASEM	National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine
NCCIC	National Cybersecurity and Communications Integration Center
NDAA	National Defense Authorization Act
NGA	National Geospatial-Intelligence Agency
NG	National Guard
NGB	National Guard Bureau
NGAUS	National Guard Association of the United States
NGR	National Guard Regulation
NIOC	Navy Information Operations Command
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
NMT	National Mission Team
NORAD	North American Aerospace Defense Command
NPS	Naval Postgraduate School
NRO	National Reconnaissance Office
NSA	National Security Agency
NSA/CSS	National Security Agency/Central Security Service
NSOC	National Security Operations Center
NST	National Support Team
NTOC	National Threat Operations Center
OCA	Original Classification Authority
OCO	Offensive Cyberspace Operations
OE	Operational Environment
OIE	Operations in the Information Environment
OPCON	Operational Control
OS	Operational Support
OSD	Office of the Secretary of Defense
OSINT	Open Source Intelligence
OT	Operational Technology
OTD	Other Training Duty
PED	Processing, Exploitation, and Dissemination
PI	Principal Investigator
PII	Personally Identifiable Information
PNT	Positioning, Navigation, and Timing
P&R	Personnel and Readiness (as used in USD(P&R))
PPP	Public-Private Partnership
PT	Proficiency Training
RA	Response Actions (in DCO-RA)
RC	Reserve Component
RCIE	Reserve Component Intelligence Enterprise

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Acronym	Definition
RQ	Research Question
RSOI	Reception, Staging, Onward Movement, and Integration
SAD	State Active Duty
SASC	Senate Armed Services Committee
SECDEF	Secretary of Defense
SECWAR	Secretary of War (see SECDEF)
SIGINT	Signals Intelligence
SOF	Special Operations Forces
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure(s)
SSC	Space Systems Certificate
STAT	Statutory Tour
ST	Specialized Training
T&R	Training and Readiness
TACON	Tactical Control
TAG	The Adjutant General
TDY	Temporary Duty
TFE	Task Force Echo
TIWO	Tactical Information Warfare Officer
TOD	Tour of Duty
TPPA	Training Period for Preparation of Assemblies
TS	Top Secret
TS/SCI	Top Secret/Sensitive Compartmented Information
U	Unclassified
UMGC	University of Maryland Global Campus
USAF	United States Air Force
USAP	United States Antarctic Program
USAR	United States Army Reserve
USC	United States Code
USCYBERCOM	United States Cyber Command
USD	Under Secretary of Defense
USD(P&R)	Under Secretary of Defense for Personnel and Readiness
USNORTHCOM	United States Northern Command
UTA	Unit Training Assembly
UW	University of Wisconsin–Madison
WIARNG	Wisconsin Army National Guard
WIFCP	Wisconsin Federated Cyber Program
WING	Wisconsin National Guard
WISC	Wisconsin Information Security Center
WO	Warrant Officer
WOAC	Warrant Officer Advanced Course
WOCS	Warrant Officer Candidate School
WSRC	Wisconsin Security Research Consortium

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Background

The problem addressed by this study is that the United States lacks a consistently understood and consistently executed legal-policy-operational pathway to employ National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status to support national defensive cyber missions at scale. Although multiple statutory authorities, policies, and operational precedents can support Title 32 mission execution under training-aligned conditions, implementation remains fragmented across stakeholders, resulting in underutilization of available cyber capacity, uneven governance, and inconsistent resourcing and approval processes.

The U.S. military possesses a deep and extensive body of cyber expertise in uniform in the National Guard and Reserve force in particular. Leveraging this expertise effectively, both in a way that is productive for the military, and that is fulfilling and meaningful for the servicemember — which results in benefits for recruiting, retention, and continued development of this expertise — has been an ongoing challenge.

This productive employment is even more challenging while in reserve status, resulting in attrition of this critical force (Harper, 2025; Lonergan & Montgomery, 2024). There is a national imperative, as well as clear statements from military cyber leadership, to effectively utilize all available resources to include the Guard and Reserve force for the nation's cyber challenges.

Nomenclature Note: The U.S. Department of Defense (DoD) and Secretary of Defense (SECDEF) are referred to by their statutory names as defined in Title 10 U.S. Code §111 (“U.S. Code Title 10”, n.d.) throughout this document. Department of War (DoW) and Secretary of War (SECWAR) may be used as “secondary names” per Executive Order (EO) 14347 (White House, 2025).

1.1.1 Cyber Leadership Comments

U.S. Army General Paul Nakasone, Director, National Security Agency (NSA)/Chief, Central Security Service (CSS), and Commander, U.S. Cyber Command (USCYBERCOM) from 2018 to 2024, now the Director of the Institute of National Security at Vanderbilt University, stated that the Guard and Reserve force is “a crucial part of achieving our mission of protecting the Nation in cyberspace. Cybersecurity is national security. Malicious actors utilizing tools less than a few thousand dollars in value are capable of impacting national security. That’s where the Total Force comes in, in terms of what we need to do collective as a team to protect national interest in cyberspace,” (Paschal, 2021) and, “Protecting the nation against malicious cyber activity is a whole-of-nation effort involving partners from industry, academia, interagency, and the Guard and Reserve.” (U.S. Cyber Command Public Affairs, 2022)

U.S. Air Force General Timothy Haugh, head of NSA/CSS and USCYBERCOM from 2024 to 2025, stated that “USCYBERCOM is exploring innovative ways to enhance our operations using the expertise resident in the National Guard and Reserves. We operate side-by-side daily with activated members of the Reserve Component integrated into our teams [...]” (Haugh, 2024)

U.S. Army Lieutenant General William “Joe” Hartman, acting head of NSA/CSS and USCYBERCOM from 2025 to 2026, made the identical statement one year later in pre-

pared testimony to Congress, stating that “USCYBERCOM is exploring innovative ways to enhance our operations using the expertise resident in the National Guard and Reserves. We operate side-by-side daily with activated members of the Reserve Component integrated into our teams [...]” (Hartman, 2025)

Most recently, U.S. Army General Joshua Rudd, current head of NSA/CSS and USCYBERCOM, stated that “Members of the National Guard enhance USCYBERCOM’s missions and provide essential cyber capabilities to their home states. Many Guard members bring valuable private-sector experience, allowing them to quickly share threat information with state and local authorities. They can operate under state authority (Title 32) to protect critical infrastructure or be federally mobilized under Title 10 to directly support USCYBERCOM’s national mission.” (Rudd, 2026)

1.1.2 National Guard Leadership Comments

On the capabilities of the National Guard, Air Force General Steve Nordhaus, the Chief of the National Guard Bureau, stated, “Innovation is not just an option for the National Guard — it must be our way of life. [...] We must empower every Guardsman to think creatively, to experiment, and to fail forward. It’s about fostering a culture where a cyber specialist in a small town can spark the next breakthrough that will ripple across the entire DoD. We have something our adversaries cannot replicate: The ingenuity of the American spirit, embodied in the warrior ethos of our Citizen-Soldiers and Citizen-Airmen. [...] When we innovate, we decisively win.” (Nordhaus, 2025a) And in his Fiscal Year 2026 Posture Statement before Congress in May in 2025, Gen. Nordhaus said, “The National Guard provides critical cybersecurity and information technology support, including mission assurance, network assessment and protection and risk mitigation. The National Guard cyber force is principally organized, trained and equipped to support DoD cyber mission requirements, however, can be directed to provide threat mitigation support to critical infrastructure and other non-DoD entities. Many National Guard

servicemembers hold cyber positions in their civilian jobs, allowing them to combine an intimate knowledge of leading-edge cyber technologies from the private sector with a deep appreciation of cyber tradecraft that comes from high-level security clearances and years of military training. The Guard’s cyber force is proud to fight on the frontlines of the cyber domain.” (Nordhaus, 2025b)

Army General Daniel Hokanson, the Chief of the National Guard Bureau (NGB) from 2020 to 2024, stated, “Cyber warfare is not just our future — it is our contemporary reality. The National Guard is positioned to be leaders in the digital domain and continues to enhance our nation’s cyber capabilities in combat and in the homeland. With 4,000 National Guard cyber operators across 40 states, many working for leading tech companies, the National Guard has the knowledge, skills, and abilities to play a critical role in the DoD’s cyber enterprise.” (U.S. Cyber Command Public Affairs, 2022)

1.1.3 Policy Foundations

Law and policy allow for the employment of National Guard members for various cyber functions, in a Title 10 (“U.S. Code Title 10”, n.d.) or Title 32 (“U.S. Code Title 32”, n.d.) status. Title 10 of the U.S. Code outlines the role of the armed forces in general, while Title 32 outlines the role of the National Guard. Both NSA and USCYBERCOM have offices dedicated to the constructive employment of Guard and Reserve personnel. While there are ample examples of Guard employment in cyber roles on active duty, such as Task Force Echo for Army Guard personnel (Pomerleau, 2021), or the individual mobilization of personnel to active duty to fill specific work roles, this study seeks to explore the viability of employment of Guard personnel for doctrinal cyberspace operations (CO) while in a Title 32 status, remotely from suitable facilities away from the major NSA and USCYBERCOM Cryptologic and Cyber Centers. This would enable Guard personnel to be engaged in meaningful work while also fulfilling training requirements for their assigned federal mission.

This study examines proposals to use the National Guard in support of cyberspace operations and the law, and/or policy which informs employment of National Guard cyber forces in support of national cyber missions doctrinally characterized as cyberspace operations as defined in Joint Publication 3-12 Cyberspace Operations (Joint Chiefs of Staff, 2018). This is a complex policy and legal landscape, but it can be simplified by specific employment that meets the requirements for a particular national cyber mission while fulfilling the requirements necessary under Title 32.

The functions of the national security components of the U.S. government are defined in U.S. code.

Title 10 – Armed Forces governs conventional military forces and operations and provides the legal foundation for the U.S. Department of Defense (DoD) and its branches (“U.S. Code Title 10”, n.d.).

Title 50 – War and National Defense focuses on intelligence operations, national security, and covert activities and provides the legal foundation for functions of the U.S. Intelligence Community (IC) (“U.S. Code Title 50”, n.d.).

Title 32 – National Guard governs the role of the National Guard. 32 USC §101 (4) and (6) (“U.S. Code Title 32”, n.d.) for the Army and Air National Guard, respectively, state for each National Guard component:

“[Army|Air] National Guard” means that part of the organized militia of the several States and Territories, Puerto Rico, and the District of Columbia, active and inactive, that—

- (A) is a[n] [land|air] force;
- (B) is trained, and has its officers appointed, under the sixteenth clause of section 8, article I, of the Constitution;
- (C) is organized, armed, and equipped wholly or partly at Federal expense; and
- (D) is federally recognized.

Figure 1.1: Adapted Authorities Breakdown
(Oakley, 2019)

In modern cyber warfare, there is growing integration between Title 10 military cyber missions (offensive and defensive operations) and Title 50 intelligence-based cyber operations (espionage, information warfare, and covert actions) (Figure 1.1), and Reserve Component forces, to include National Guard forces, augment and support Title 10 and Title 50 capabilities.

The National Guard is therefore connected to Title 10 and federal armed forces by such federal recognition (Figure 1.1), and by the "U.S. Constitution" (n.d.) which states:

*[The Congress shall have Power . . .] To provide for organizing, arming, and disciplining, the Militia, and for governing such Part of them as may be employed in the Service of the United States, reserving to the States respectively, the Appointment of the Officers, and the Authority of **training the Militia according to the discipline prescribed by Congress**; . . .*

1.2 DoD Cyberspace Operations Forces

The **Cyberspace Operations Forces (COF)** represent the cyberspace operations (CO) capabilities of the U.S. armed forces (Joint Chiefs of Staff, 2018). These forces include personnel and units assigned to conduct cyberspace operations across defensive, offensive, and support functions. The COF is categorized into three primary elements:

- **Cyber Mission Force (CMF)** – The operational core of U.S. Cyber Command (USCYBERCOM), responsible for executing national-level cyber operations.
- **Cyber Support Elements (CSE)** – Personnel embedded within military units to provide cyber expertise, intelligence, and operational support.
- **Service Cyber Forces** – Cyber units under the individual military services (Army, Navy, Air Force, Marine Corps, Coast Guard, and Space Force) that contribute to the overall cyberspace operations mission (Joint Chiefs of Staff, 2018).

Joint Publication 3-12 (JP 3-12) (Joint Chiefs of Staff, 2018) provides guidance to the COF by defining cyberspace operations into three core mission areas:

- **Offensive Cyberspace Operations (OCO)** – Actions taken to project power in and through cyberspace to achieve military objectives.
- **Defensive Cyberspace Operations (DCO)** – Efforts to protect, detect, respond to, and recover from cyber threats targeting DoD networks and information systems.
- **Department of Defense Information Network (DoDIN) Operations** – Ensuring the availability, integrity, and security of DoD information systems and networks (Joint Chiefs of Staff, 2018).

The COF integrates with national intelligence, law enforcement, and private-sector entities to enhance cybersecurity resilience and response capabilities.

1.2.1 Cyber Mission Force

The **Cyber Mission Force (CMF)** is the primary operational component of U.S. Cyber Command (USCYBERCOM). Established in 2012, the CMF is comprised of teams that are assigned to execute cyber operations in support of national defense, military operations, and critical infrastructure protection. As of 2025, the CMF structure consists of 135 teams organized into four distinct mission categories:

- **Cyber National Mission Teams (NMTs)** – Conduct offensive cyber operations to defend U.S. national interests from threats posed by nation-state adversaries by targeting adversary infrastructure.
- **Cyber Combat Mission Teams (CMTs)** – Support military combatant commands by conducting offensive cyber operations in coordination with kinetic operations.
- **Cyber Protection Teams (CPTs)** – Focus on defensive cyber operations, securing Department of Defense (DoD) networks and responding to cyber incidents.
- **Cyber Support Teams (CSTs)** – Provide specialized support, including intelligence analysis and planning, to enhance the effectiveness of cyber operations.

Each team is aligned with one of the military services, ensuring joint operational capabilities. The CMF operates under Title 10 authority, meaning its personnel are federal active-duty military members who execute national-level cyber missions.

1.2.2 National Guard Cyber Forces

The Army National Guard (ARNG) and Air National Guard (ANG) have several different types of cyber teams (Figure 1.2) (National Guard Bureau, 2022). The National Guard Cyber Forces provide a unique component of the nation's cyber defense capabilities.

Unlike active duty and reserve CMF personnel who operate under Title 10, National Guard cyber forces can be activated under Title 10, Title 32, or State Active Duty (SAD) status, allowing them to support both federal and state-level cyber operations.

National Guard cyber units can work with state and local governments, critical infrastructure sectors, and federal agencies such as the Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency (CISA) and the Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI) on defensive cyber operations and cybersecurity functions. Their primary functions include:

- Conducting defensive cyber operations to secure state and local government networks.
- Assisting in election security efforts.
- Responding to cyber incidents affecting critical infrastructure.
- Collaborating with private-sector partners to enhance overall cyber resilience (Forscey & Ruiz, 2019).

Despite their significant capabilities, the role of National Guard cyber forces remains limited due to legal and policy constraints. Some policymakers advocate for expanding Title 32 authorities to enable greater National Guard participation in national cyber efforts (Neville, 2023).

The Army National Guard currently has:

- 1 Cyber Brigade
- 5 Cyber Battalions
- 5 Cyber Security Companies (CSC)
- 2 Cyber Security Detachments (CSD)
- 5 Cyber Warfare Companies (CWC)
- 2 Cyber Warfare Company Detachments
- 11 Cyber Protection Teams (CPT)
- 3 Cyber Protection Detachments

The Air National Guard currently has:

- 3 Cyber Operations Groups
- 12 Cyber Operations Squadrons (Cyber Protection Teams (CPTs))
- 3 Cyber Operations Squadron (National Mission Teams (NMTs))
- 20 Mission Defense Teams
- 1 Cyber Operations Squadron (Aggressor/Red Team)

Figure 1.2 shows the cyber force organization types across the Army and Air National Guard.

Figure 1.2: Types of National Guard Cyber Units and their roles (including while activated to federal status)

(National Guard Bureau, 2022)

1.3 Problem Statement

The United States does not effectively utilize the Guard and Reserve Total Force for national cyber missions, even though senior cyber officials throughout government, in and out of uniform, as well as Congress, all universally say this utilization is essential to national security and recruiting and retention of cyber forces.

Despite the increasing importance of cyber defense in national security, the role of National Guard cyber forces under Title 32 remains ambiguous due to inconsistencies in legal interpretations, policy directives, and operational implementation. Current statutes and policies provide no clear mandate for utilizing National Guard personnel in Title 32 status for federal cyber missions, leading to challenges in workforce mobilization, command authority, and mission readiness.

This lack of clarity hinders effective cyber defense coordination between state and federal agencies, ultimately affecting the nation's cybersecurity posture. This study investigates these legal and policy ambiguities, assesses historical precedents, and explores expert perspectives to determine the feasibility and implications of National Guard cyber operations in Title 32 status.

1.4 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to examine the extent to which National Guard cyber forces may be utilized in Title 32 status to support national cyber missions under existing law, policy, and doctrinal guidance. Although senior leaders in Congress, U.S. Cyber Command, and the National Guard Bureau have consistently articulated the importance of leveraging Reserve Component cyber expertise for national defense, the legal and policy mechanisms that enable or constrain the use of National Guard personnel in Title 32 status for national cyber missions remain poorly understood and/or utilized.

This study employs a qualitative, multi-method design to analyze these mechanisms and to determine whether viable pathways for Title 32 cyber mission support already exist within current statutory and regulatory authorities. Specifically, the study conducts a documentary analysis of Title 32 authorities; Department of Defense (DoD) and National Guard Bureau (NGB) policy; joint and service cyberspace doctrine; and relevant congressional provisions. It further incorporates practitioner perspectives through a structured expert survey and demonstrates real-world applicability through a focused case study of an operational pilot program.

By integrating legal analysis, policy interpretation, expert assessment, and operational evidence, this study seeks to clarify how National Guard cyber forces may fulfill training requirements while simultaneously providing support to national cyber missions under Title 32 of the United States Code.

1.5 Significance of the Study

This study addresses a critical and unresolved problem in U.S. national security policy: how to effectively employ the cyber expertise resident in the National Guard for national cyber missions while personnel remain in Title 32 status. The National Guard possesses over 4,000 cyber operators — many of whom work in advanced cybersecurity roles in their civilian careers — and represents a uniquely skilled and distributed force that could substantially enhance national cyber defense. However, ambiguity regarding the legal, policy, and doctrinal boundaries of Title 32 employment has prevented consistent or systematic integration of this capability into federal cyber operations.

Clarifying these boundaries is significant for several reasons. First, it addresses an urgent national security need: adversary cyber activity increasingly targets U.S. government networks, critical infrastructure, and allied interests, and the demand for highly skilled defensive capability exceeds the capacity of the Active Component alone. Second, the

study supports force readiness and retention by identifying mechanisms through which National Guard cyber personnel may engage in meaningful, mission-aligned work that maintains or enhances proficiency. Third, it informs ongoing policy debates in Congress and the Department of Defense regarding Reserve Component integration, Cyber Mission Force development, and the potential establishment of a U.S. Cyber Force.

Finally, this study contributes to the academic and practitioner literature by providing one of the first comprehensive analyses that integrates legal frameworks, policy review, expert insight, and operational precedent. Its findings may guide future legislation, DoD policy development, National Guard training models, and state–federal cyber coordination efforts, thereby strengthening the ability of the United States to employ its Total Force effectively in cyberspace.

1.6 Nature of the Study

The nature of this study is qualitative, employing a multi-method qualitative research design with embedded descriptive quantitative analysis to examine how National Guard cyber forces may support national cyber missions while in Title 32 status. Because this topic involves legal interpretation, policy analysis, doctrinal review, and practitioner insight, a qualitative approach is most appropriate for evaluating the feasibility and boundaries of Title 32 cyber mission support (Bowen, 2009; Creswell & Creswell, 2023; Yin, 2018). The study does not seek to measure causal relationships or produce statistically generalizable findings; rather, it aims to describe, interpret, and evaluate existing authorities and their practical application in context.

The study consists of three integrated components. First, a documentary analysis was conducted across statutory authorities (Titles 10, 32, etc.), Department of Defense and National Guard Bureau policies, joint and service cyberspace doctrine, congressional provisions, and other authoritative sources. These documents were coded for enabling,

constraining, or ambiguous language regarding Title 32 cyber operations.

Second, the study incorporates expert perspectives through a structured survey of current and former practitioners in military cyber operations, federal cyber policy, legal frameworks, and National Guard or Reserve Component employment. The survey includes Likert-scale, multiple-choice, and open-ended items. Numeric survey responses were analyzed using descriptive techniques only to summarize patterns of expert perspectives and to support qualitative interpretation, while open-ended responses were thematically analyzed. No inferential statistical generalization was sought.

Third, a focused case study of the Wisconsin Federated Cyber Program (WIFCP) provides an applied example of National Guard cyber personnel conducting training-aligned mission support for a national customer in Title 32 status. The case documents observed operational workflows, mission outputs, duty statuses, and personnel-related outcomes relevant to the study's research questions.

Together, these complementary methods enable a comprehensive qualitative examination of how existing law and policy function in practice, and how National Guard cyber forces may be utilized under Title 32 to support national cyber missions while meeting required training objectives, as articulated in official cyber training and readiness (T&R) publications and implemented in the Cyber Mission Force (CMF) training model (Table 1.1).

A central tension of this study is that operational support must occur incident to training, and this determination depends on context, documentation, supervisory judgment, and the intent of the activity. This study does not seek to resolve this determination in every scenario, but rather to identify conditions under which training activities may provide support to national mission requirements while in Title 32 status.

Table 1.1: Cyber Mission Force (CMF) Training Model Phases (GAO, 2019)

	Phase one <i>Basic individual training</i>	Phase two <i>Individual foundation training</i>	Phase three <i>Collective training</i>	Phase four <i>Sustainment training</i>
Training standards established by	Services or by a joint organization (e.g. signals intelligence training standards are set by the National Security Agency).	U.S. Cyber Command	U.S. Cyber Command	U.S. Cyber Command
Training administered by	Services	U.S. Cyber Command vendors, such as the Defense Cyber Investigations Training Academy. Some services also have the U.S. Cyber Command's approval to deliver training.	Services at the unit level.	Services at the unit level and U.S. Cyber Command vendors.
Description	Provides initial specialty occupation training.	Prepares personnel for the specific position they will fill in the CMF team to which they are assigned using a particular progression of courses.	Prepares personnel to pass U.S. Cyber Command's certification standards through on-the-job training and exercises.	Refreshes team skills and certifications using activities from phases two and three. Also includes mission rehearsal exercises.

1.7 Research Justification

This research is critical for policymakers, military leadership, and cyber practitioners because it addresses an urgent gap in U.S. cybersecurity policy. While prior studies have explored National Guard roles in disaster response and kinetic warfare, there is limited research on their integration into federal cyber operations in Title 32 status. Given the increasing sophistication of cyber threats, clarifying the legal and policy framework governing Title 32 cyber forces is essential to ensuring operational effectiveness, workforce retention, and legal compliance. The findings of this study will inform:

- The National Guard Bureau (NGB), U.S. Cyber Command (USCYBERCOM), and service cyber components (e.g. Army Cyber Command (ARCYBER)) on optimizing cyber force utilization.
- DoD policymakers on potential legislative or policy adjustments to enhance Title 32 cyber integration.
- State and federal agencies on improving coordination and command structures in cybersecurity missions.

1.8 Research Objectives

To address the identified policy gaps and operational challenges, this study intends to:

- Identify the specific elements of current law and policy that enable or constrain the use of National Guard personnel in Title 32 status for federal cyber missions.
- Examine historical precedents and expert analyses to determine how Title 32 authorities have been interpreted and applied in cybersecurity contexts.

- Assess the operational feasibility and strategic implications of leveraging Title 32 cyber forces for national security missions.
- Provide evidence-based recommendations for policymakers to enhance the clarity and effectiveness of Title 32 cyber force integration.

1.9 Central Proposition

National Guard Cyber Forces in Title 32 status can be used to support certain national defensive cyber missions, if a training requirement is met, under existing law and policy.

This proposition does not assert that current legal authorities automatically enable Title 32 cyber mission execution under all circumstances. Rather, it identifies conditions under which such execution may be feasible when supported by appropriate governance, oversight, and demonstrated training alignment.

1.10 Research Questions

This study seeks to establish the viability and efficacy of the utilization of Army National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status for national cyber missions by answering the following research questions:

1. What elements of current law and policy support or constrain the utilization of National Guard personnel in Title 32 status for national cyber missions?

At the present time it is unclear which elements of law or policy may support or constrain the utilization of National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status for federal cyber missions. Title 32 is the status in which National Guard forces operate when training for their federal missions under the authority of the state governor, as specified in 32 U.S.C. Chapter 5—Training. Federal cyber missions are those that may be conducted by active-duty military forces in a Title 10 status.

2. What precedent, expert opinion, and policy analysis enable or challenge the use of National Guard personnel in Title 32 status for national cyber missions?

Current or former military, civilian, industry, and academic participants familiar with both the National Guard and United States military cyber operations in a policy or legal context, at the national and state levels, will offer valuable insight into the applicability and viability of solutions for mission support in training status. Participants are in a cyber or cyber-related field, or in a policy or legal field relevant to cyber operations, or are familiar with the policy or legal landscape.

1.10.1 Connection Between Research Questions and the Problem Statement

The research questions for this study are directly aligned with the research problem and objectives. They are designed to systematically address the lack of policy clarity, assess real-world applicability, and derive informed recommendations. By answering these questions, the study will contribute to the ongoing policy discourse on cyber force structure, command authority, and the evolving role of the National Guard in national cybersecurity.

1.10.2 Anticipated Policy Contributions

This study intends to provide policy recommendations that enhance the legal, strategic, and operational framework for utilizing National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status for national cyber missions. Based on the findings from documentary analysis, expert surveys, and an embedded case study, the study may drive policy refinements, such as:

1. Clarification of Title 32 Cyber Authorities to eliminate legal ambiguities surrounding support to national cyber missions.
2. Development of a National Guard Cyber Integration Strategy to formally align Guard cyber personnel with national cyber defense.
3. Establishment of a Federated Cyber Program (FCP) construct to provide a scalable model for doctrinal cyber operations similar to the Federated Intelligence Program (FIP) for intelligence activities.
4. Interoperability Enhancements between Title 10 and Title 32 cyber forces to improve coordination and mission readiness.
5. Legislative Adjustments in future National Defense Authorization Acts (NDAAs) to institutionalize National Guard cyber capabilities within the broader U.S. cyber defense strategy.

These recommendations will contribute to ongoing cybersecurity policy discussions at the National Guard Bureau (NGB), U.S. Cyber Command (USCYBERCOM), and DoD policymakers, providing data-driven insights into the role of National Guard cyber forces in national defense.

1.11 Theoretical Foundations

This study is guided by an integrated conceptual and theoretical framework that combines organizational theory, cybersecurity governance, and operational doctrine to analyze the feasibility and execution pathways for employing National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status for national cyber missions. The research problem is not purely legal, not purely technical, and not purely organizational; it is a *governance-and-execution* problem spanning authorities, institutional design, and mission implementation. Accordingly, no single lens is sufficient. This framework uses three complementary lenses: Mintzberg’s organizational configurations, the NIST Cybersecurity Framework (CSF) 2.0 governance and risk-management model, and Multi-Domain Operations (MDO) doctrine.

- **Organizational Configurations** (Mintzberg, 1983, 1984) — This theory explains the hierarchical decision-making and bureaucratic challenges in integrating National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status into national cyber missions. The National Guard operates within a dual-status framework (state and federal), leading to bureaucratic inefficiencies when transitioning between Title 32 and Title 10 roles. By applying this theory, this study examines how institutional structures influence the policy limitations and operational constraints affecting National Guard cyber forces.
- **NIST Cybersecurity Framework (CSF) 2.0** (NIST, 2024) — Cybersecurity governance emphasizes the importance of clear policies, compliance mechanisms, and strategic coordination among stakeholders. Given that Title 32 lacks a unified governance model for integration into national cyber operations while in this status, this framework provides insight into the policy fragmentation that limits National Guard cyber readiness and effectiveness. The study applies cybersecurity governance principles to assess whether existing policies align with best practices for cyber defense.

- **Multi-Domain Operations (MDO) Concept** (AFC, 2020) — The MDO concept highlights the need for integrated capabilities across land, air, sea, space, and cyberspace. The National Guard plays a critical role in cyber defense missions, but a lack of policy clarity in the context of Title 32 authorities hinders full participation in federal cyber operations. This study examines how aligning National Guard cyber forces with MDO principles could enhance their strategic role in national cybersecurity.

1.11.1 Interactions Between Theoretical Approaches

While these three theories address different aspects of military cyber policy, they are interconnected. Organizational Configurations explains why command-and-control challenges emerge in cyber force integration under Title 32, while Cybersecurity Governance highlights the policy misalignments that contribute to operational inefficiencies. Multi-Domain Operations, in turn, provides a strategic justification for resolving these policy gaps to enhance cyber capabilities.

For example, bureaucratic inefficiencies may slow down decision-making, limiting the agility required for effective cyber operations. Cybersecurity governance frameworks advocate for clear roles and responsibilities, which, if implemented, could mitigate some of these bureaucratic issues. Similarly, integrating Guard cyber forces into MDO structures would require governance reforms to ensure seamless Title 32 participation in federal cyber missions.

1.11.2 Application of Theoretical Frameworks to Research Questions

This study considers these theoretical perspectives to guide data collection and analysis. Specifically:

- **Organizational Configurations** helps analyze how existing laws and policies shape or hinder the effective use of National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status.
- **Cybersecurity Governance** under the NIST Cybersecurity Framework provides a lens to assess policy inconsistencies and determine whether governance reforms are needed to enable Title 32 cyber missions.
- **Multi-Domain Operations (MDO)** as a concept is used to evaluate how National Guard cyber capabilities can be better aligned with national security strategy.

These theoretical perspectives guide the interpretation of documentary analysis findings and expert survey data, ensuring a structured and methodologically sound approach to understanding National Guard cyber integration under Title 32.

These frameworks provide a background for evaluating the policy, legal, and operational challenges related to National Guard cyber force utilization for national cyber missions while in Title 32 status.

The three lenses are used together to ensure that findings and recommendations are grounded in legal-policy evidence, organizational feasibility, and doctrine-informed operational context. Table 1.2 summarizes how each lens supports the research questions.

1.12 Assumptions

This study rests on several foundational assumptions necessary for the research design to be valid and for the conclusions to be meaningful.

First, the study assumes that publicly available and unclassified sources adequately represent the legal and policy landscape governing Title 32 cyber operations. While some relevant guidance may exist in classified or controlled environments, the core statutory authorities, published DoD and NGB policy, joint doctrine, and congressional materials

Table 1.2: Traceability of Theoretical Lenses to Research Questions and Analytic Use

Lens	RQ Alignment	How the Lens is Used
Organizational Configurations	RQ1 and RQ2	Interprets institutional design, decision rights, and coordination mechanisms; structures coding for bureaucratic/cultural barriers; supports explanation of execution gaps.
Cybersecurity Governance	RQ1 (primary), RQ2 (secondary)	Frames governance and oversight requirements for repeatability; organizes findings about roles, responsibilities, and accountability; informs governance-centered recommendations.
MDO Doctrine	RQ2 (primary), RQ1 (secondary)	Provides doctrine-informed framing for operational feasibility and mission alignment; supports interpretation of what mission categories plausibly fit Title 32 training-first constraints.

examined here capture the essential framework. This assumption is reasonable given that the authorities in question are codified in public law and policy.

Second, the study assumes that survey respondents answered honestly and accurately based on their professional knowledge. This assumption is supported by the IRB-approved design ensuring anonymity and voluntary participation, and by the experienced respondent profile. However, self-selection bias may affect the sample, as participants may hold stronger views and/or greater familiarity with the topic than nonrespondents.

Third, the study assumes that the legal and policy environment remained relatively stable during the data collection period (2025). Where significant developments occurred — such as enactment of the FY2026 NDAA — these were incorporated to maintain currency.

Fourth, the study assumes that the Wisconsin Federated Cyber Program (WIFCP) case study represents a valid operational example of how Title 32 cyber mission support can be structured, while acknowledging that local factors such as state leadership, unit

capabilities, and mission partner relationships will vary across contexts.

Finally, the study assumes that the researcher’s practitioner background provides contextual insight without introducing systematic bias. Standard qualitative practices — methodological triangulation, structured coding, and transparent documentation — were employed to ensure findings are grounded in evidence rather than advocacy.

These assumptions represent necessary conditions for the study’s execution. Where assumptions may not hold — in states with different Guard structures, under future policy changes, or with access to classified or controlled guidance — applicability of findings should be evaluated accordingly.

1.13 Definitions

Title 10 Status Federal active-duty status under Title 10 of the United States Code in which forces operate under federal command authority for national defense missions. (“U.S. Code Title 10”, n.d.)

Title 32 Status Federally funded but state-controlled National Guard duty status under Title 32 of the United States Code. In this dissertation, Title 32 is discussed as the primary status for Guard training for federal missions and as a potential pathway for mission-aligned support when structured to satisfy training requirements. (“U.S. Code Title 32”, n.d.)

Title 50 Authorities Authorities under Title 50 of the United States Code governing intelligence and national security activities. In this dissertation, Title 50 is referenced to distinguish intelligence-governed activity and oversight regimes from Title 10 military operations and Title 32 Guard activities. (“U.S. Code Title 50”, n.d.)

32 USC §502(a) A Title 32 authority for required drills and annual training. In this dissertation, §502(a) is relevant because training conducted under this authority

may produce operationally useful outputs when training remains the paramount purpose. (“U.S. Code Title 32”, n.d.)

32 USC §502(f) A Title 32 authority commonly used for additional duty (including full-time orders). In this dissertation, §502(f) is discussed as a mechanism by which Guard personnel may be placed on Title 32 orders beyond routine drill/annual training when appropriately authorized and scoped. (“U.S. Code Title 32”, n.d.)

Operational Support (OS) Work that contributes to operational mission requirements. In this dissertation, OS is evaluated in relation to Title 32 as potentially permissible when it is incidental to (and subordinate to) *bona fide* training. (USD I&S, 2020)

Training A duty purpose in which training requirements drive task selection, resourcing, and documentation. In this dissertation, the central analytic distinction is that Title 32 activities must be structured so that training remains the primary purpose even when mission outputs result. (USD I&S, 2020)

Cyberspace Operations (CO) Actions taken in and through cyberspace to achieve objectives. The dissertation uses CO as the doctrinal umbrella under which defensive and offensive activities (and related supporting functions) are categorized. (Joint Chiefs of Staff, 2018)

Cyber Mission Force (CMF) The Department of Defense operational cyber force structure organized into mission teams employed under U.S. Cyber Command tasking. (Joint Chiefs of Staff, 2018)

Cyber Protection Team (CPT) A mission team/unit type aligned to defensive cyber functions. The dissertation references CPTs as the operationally relevant Guard cyber unit type for the proposed Title 32 mission-support pathways. (Joint Chiefs of Staff, 2018)

Defensive Cyberspace Operations (DCO) Cyberspace operations intended to defend friendly networks, systems, and missions from malicious cyber activity. The dissertation treats DCO as inclusive of both internal defensive measures and response actions. (Joint Chiefs of Staff, 2018)

DCO–Internal Defensive Measures (DCO-IDM) Defensive actions conducted within the defended environment to protect, monitor, detect, analyze, and mitigate malicious cyber activity, without extending response actions into external or adversary-controlled infrastructure. (Joint Chiefs of Staff, 2018)

DCO–Response Actions (DCO-RA) Defensive actions taken in response to malicious cyber activity that extend beyond internal defensive measures and may involve external actions, typically raising additional authorization and policy considerations. (Joint Chiefs of Staff, 2018)

Offensive Cyberspace Operations (OCO) Cyberspace operations intended to project power in and through cyberspace to achieve objectives against adversary systems or capabilities; included in the dissertation primarily to delimit scope relative to Title 32 feasibility discussions. (Joint Chiefs of Staff, 2018)

Department of Defense Information Network (DoDIN) The globally interconnected set of DoD information systems used to collect, process, store, transmit, and manage information for DoD missions. The dissertation references DoDIN operations as part of doctrinal mission-taxonomy context. (Joint Chiefs of Staff, 2018)

Homeland Defense Activity (HDA) A federally designated National Guard activity under Title 32 intended to support homeland defense objectives, conducted under gubernatorial control with federal funding when designated/approved by the Secretary of Defense. (“U.S. Code Title 32”, n.d.)

Defense Support of Civil Authorities (DSCA) Support provided by DoD compo-

nents (including the National Guard under specified statuses and approvals) to civil authorities for domestic emergencies, special events, and other approved circumstances. (Beaver, 2024)

Defense Support to Cyber Incident Response (DSCIR) A DSCA-related pathway for DoD support to cyber incident response when requested and approved under applicable authorities and policy, typically involving federal-state coordination and defined approval processes. (DOD CIO, 2023)

Federated Intelligence Program (FIP) An Army National Guard training construct described in the dissertation as precedent for Title 32 training-first activity that can produce incidental operational value while remaining within applicable oversight constraints. (Kirschner & McGarry, 2015)

Federated Cyber Program (FCP) A proposed structured mechanism for National Guard cyber personnel to provide mission-aligned, training-creditable support to national cyber mission customers while in Title 32 status, using repeatable tasking and explicit scoping to cybersecurity functions.

Wisconsin Federated Cyber Program (WIFCP) A Wisconsin National Guard operational pilot described in the dissertation that implements federated cyber support while personnel are in Title 32 status and aligned to training requirements. (Schroeder, 2023)

Intelligence Oversight (IO) The legal and policy compliance regime governing intelligence activities. The dissertation references IO to distinguish cybersecurity mission-support activity from intelligence-governed activity and to address oversight constraints where applicable. (DCMO, 2017)

Controlled Unclassified Information (CUI) Unclassified information that requires

safeguarding and dissemination controls pursuant to law, regulation, or government-wide policy. (White House, 2010)

1.14 About the Author

The author has served for over 30 years as a senior strategist, information technology manager, and cyber subject matter expert at the University of Wisconsin–Madison, a major public research university and large state government agency. As Director of National Security Initiatives, he supports both the Vice Chancellor for Research (VCR) and Vice Chancellor for University Relations (VCUR) to advance University initiatives on national security research and partnerships. He also serves as a UW Expert and member of Badger Talks for media requests and public speaking on cyber and national security issues. He holds an Honorary Fellow appointment as a National Security Research Strategist in the College of Letters & Science (L&S). He currently serves on the Board of Directors for the Wisconsin Security Research Consortium (WSRC) and Wisconsin Information Security Center (WISC).

The author also serves in the Wisconsin Army National Guard as a Cyber Warfare Officer (17A), Signal Officer (25A), Military Intelligence Officer (35A), and Space Cadre. He is currently serving as the Commander of Detachment 1-176th Cyber Protection Team (CPT). Previously, he served as a Cryptologic Warfare Officer (1815) and Information Warfare Officer in the U.S. Navy Reserve. He has mobilized in support of Operations Noble Eagle and Enduring Freedom in conventional and special operations units, and is qualified in joint and tactical Operations in the Information Environment (OIE).

The author holds a bachelor's degree in Intelligence Studies (Information Operations) and a master's degree in Intelligence Studies (Information Warfare) from American Military University (AMU), a master's degree in Cybersecurity Policy from the University of Maryland Global Campus (UMGC), and a Graduate Space Systems Certificate (SSC)

from the Naval Postgraduate School (NPS). He is also a qualified Tactical Information Warfare Officer (TIWO) and Cryptologic Warfare Planner. He completed Intermediate Level Education (ILE) and Joint Professional Military Education (JPME) Phase I with distinction at the Naval War College (NWC), and completed the Joint Information Operations Planners Course (JIOPC) at the Joint Forces Staff College. His academic and research interests are focused on cyber policy, systems, and operations, especially how to integrate and employ the extensive cyber expertise in the Reserve Component (RC) of U.S. military forces. He is an avid follower of national security issues.

The author enjoys traveling and hiking with his wife of 21 years, Valerie, and their two sons, Nathaniel (Nat) and Vincent (Vin).

1.15 Summary

Chapter 1 introduced the problem, purpose, context, and foundational direction of this study. The chapter established that although senior leaders across Congress, the National Guard Bureau, the Department of Defense, and U.S. Cyber Command have consistently emphasized the need to leverage National Guard cyber expertise, the mechanisms for utilizing Guard personnel in Title 32 status for national cyber missions remain poorly defined and inconsistently applied. The chapter outlined the problem statement, research purpose, and significance of clarifying the legal, policy, and doctrinal pathways that may enable this form of mission support. The study's qualitative, multi-method design was introduced, integrating documentary analysis, expert survey data, and an operational case study. The research questions, objectives, and central proposition were presented, connecting these elements to the broader policy and organizational challenges facing the National Guard cyber enterprise. Collectively, the chapter provided the conceptual and methodological grounding for the literature review and research analysis that follow.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

2.1 Background

The body of literature on the utilization of National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status for national cyber missions is limited. Unlike other domains of cybersecurity, cyber defense, and military operations where academic research is abundant in peer-reviewed journals, this particular subject primarily resides in military theses, white papers, and notional policy documents. As a result, much of the existing discourse is shaped by military doctrine and strategic assessments rather than empirical research in academic journals.

The National Guard's role in cyberspace operations presents a unique challenge that has been examined primarily through service-specific studies at military educational institutions, government reports, and congressional directives rather than traditional scholarly outlets. Many of these works originate from the U.S. Army War College, the Naval Postgraduate School, and the Air War College, where military officers propose models and frameworks for the employment of Guard and Reserve cyber forces. While these studies provide valuable insights, they are often theoretical in nature and lack extensive empirical validation. Similarly, policy papers from defense think tanks and government agencies, such as the Department of Defense (DoD) or the National Guard Bureau (NGB), contribute to the available literature, but they are typically written with a focus on immediate

operational and policy concerns rather than long-term academic inquiry.

The scarcity of peer-reviewed research in this field highlights a broader issue: the integration of National Guard cyber forces into federal cyber operations under Title 32 status exists in a policy gray area rather than as a fully established practice. As a result, most analyses are focused on legislative and doctrinal feasibility and policy proposals, rather than detailed research or case studies. Additionally, some of the available documentation and relevant materials are classified or controlled, further limiting widespread scholarly engagement on the topic.

This chapter synthesizes the available literature, drawing primarily from military theses, white papers, Congressional action, and defense policy documents. By examining these sources, this review aims to establish the current state of knowledge, identify key debates, and highlight the gaps in research that this dissertation seeks to address.

2.2 Survey of Existing Proposals

Several papers over approximately the last 15 years have explored the employment of National Guard forces in the cyber domain, especially as cyber issues have become more prominent in the national discourse on issues ranging from ransomware to critical infrastructure and election security. These papers exist largely in the realm of the service War Colleges, policy proposals, and military journals; as such, these papers are used as a major basis for the survey.

2.2.1 Early Proposals

2.2.1.1 A Reserve Component Initiative to Defend DoD and National Cyberspace

In 2011, Hollis (2011) argued that the U.S. is “is under increasing threat from both nation state and non-nation state cyberspace domain aggressors,” and further, that the

ability to effectively conduct cyberspace operations “is a predicate to both successful military operations and successful private sector operations such as in the economic/financial, health, telecommunications, logistics, and energy operations sectors.”

However, Hollis continues by stating that the military’s approach to the cyberspace domain is “fragmented, unorganized, and not under effective command and control (C2); requires integrated individual and collective training; and lacks effective inter-agency national policy to achieve full effectiveness.” Moreover, “the extensive capabilities of the military’s Reserve [and Guard] Components are not effectively utilized to conduct and support cyberspace domain operations.”

Hollis goes on to describe a model wherein Reserve Component (RC) forces (which includes National Guard) could be employed for a Defensive Cyberspace Operations (DCO) function; namely, to secure the country’s critical infrastructure from cyber threats. Hollis proposes a Joint RC Command (JRCC), under the operational control (OPCON) of USCYBERCOM, which would be aligned with functional areas and organized by Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) geographic regions and focused on critical infrastructure defense (Figure 2.1).

Figure 2.1: Reserve Critical Infrastructure Defense Model (Hollis, 2011)

This is one of the earliest examples of a broad recommendation for a comprehensive model of employment of the Guard and Reserve cyber force in support of national cyber missions. In this model, the National Guard component of the JRCC operates in a Title 32 status unless federalized. But Hollis makes the clear case that extensive cyber and information technology (IT) expertise exists in the Guard and Reserve force and the “fundamental reason for the existence of the JRCC.”

Hollis closes by noting there are daunting legal, bureaucratic, and resource obstacles that would impede this or a similar plan, and that USCYBERCOM needs to develop the organizations, capabilities, and infrastructure to support this concept prior to a cyber event. If implemented, Hollis asserts that this model leveraging Guard and Reserve forces

for national cyber missions “represents the Citizen-Soldier concepts of national defense, regional security, and an operational reserve at their finest.”

2.2.1.2 A National Solution Rethinking the Employment of Air National Guard Title 32 Status Citizen-Airmen to Defend the Nation’s Cyberspace Infrastructure

Two years later in 2013, McKinney (2013) makes the case that this matter is not yet resolved, and that “the Air National Guard’s [the Guard component of the U.S. Air Force] role in defending the nation against cyber-attacks is unclear and that policy makers must enact legislation that authorize and fund the employment of ANG members in a Title 32 state, versus federal, status to conduct cyberspace operations.”

McKinney draws several parallels with Air National Guard (ANG) support to domestic events to include Modular Airborne Fire Fighting System (MAFFS) crews to suppress fires, Air Sovereignty Alert (ASA) operations instituted after 9/11 wherein a pilot flying an alert mission automatically converts from Title 32 to Title 10 status upon takeoff, or airlift support to the National Science Foundation’s (NSF) United States Antarctic Program (USAP).

McKinney reviews national and military cyberspace law and policy, the authorities granted under Title 10 and Title 32, and recommends legislation under Title 32 “that authorizes and funds the employment of Air National Guard members in a Title 32 state, versus federal, status to conduct cyberspace operations.” A review of the duty types and the Title under which they can be conducted is used to make the point that many Title 32 duty types are available (Table 2.1), to include for routine training — e.g., drill weekends and annual training (AT) — but that ANG authorities to support cyberspace operations under Title 32 are unclear.

Table 2.1: Air National Guard Duty Relationships.

Service Type	Duty Type	Training Category	Title
Inactive Duty	IDT	AFTP	32
		TPPA	32
		UTA	32
		PT	32
AD or FTNGD	ADOT	ADOS	10/32
		AGR	10/32
		MPA	10
		STAT TOUR	10
	ADT	IADT	10/32
		FST	10/32
		AT	10/32
		ST	10/32
Acronyms			
ADOS: Active Duty for Operational Support			
ADOT: Active Duty for Other Than Training			
AD: Active Duty ADT: Active Duty for Training			
AFTP: Additional Flight Training Period			
AGR: Active Guard Reserve			
AT: Annual Training			
FTNGD: Full-time National Guard			
FST: Formal School Training			
IADT: Initial Active Duty for Training			
IDT: Inactive Duty Training			
MPA: Military Personnel Appropriations			
PT: Proficiency Training			
STAT TOUR: Statutory Tour			
TPPA: Training Period for Preparation of Assemblies			
UTA: Unit Training Assembly			

Air National Guard Duty Relationships. Adapted from Air National Guard Instruction 36-2001, *Management and Training Operational Support within the Air National Guard*, 30 April 2019. (McKinney, 2013)

ANG cyber forces are presented to USCYBERCOM as a part of the 16th Air Force (AFCYBER) reserve cyber forces. However, the utilization of these forces is only clear when personnel are mobilized to active duty on Title 10. McKinney notes that even 2½ years after the standup of USCYBERCOM (the time the paper was authored), “debate continues about how to integrate ANG cyber forces, in a Title 32 status, into AFCYBER and USCYBERCOM’s missions.” (The same largely remains true at the time of this

writing.)

McKinney proposes a new construct for National Guard cyber forces, the National Guard Cybersecurity Program (NGCSP), with specific cybersecurity authorities under Title 32. The cyber forces organized under NGCSP would have interfaces with the state government, Department of Homeland Security (DHS), Department of Defense (DoD) (including USCYBERCOM and NSA), the Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI), and the White House Cybersecurity Coordinator, all in Title 32 status (Figure 2.2).

At the time of this writing, a comprehensive plan like the one proposed for NGCSP or similar has not been realized.

2.2.1.3 The Challenges of Defense Support of Civil Authorities and Homeland Defense in the Cyber Domain

In 2013, Hopes (2013) examined National Guard cyber activities in the context of the broader Defense Support of Civil Authorities (DSCA) and homeland defense. The paper again observes that part of USCYBERCOM's charge is "integration of National Guard (NG) and Reserve component forces" (McKinney, 2013) for cyber mission support.

Hopes outlines one DoD sector specific plan for protection of the Defense Industrial Base (DIB), wherein one response option is that "a State Governor may request other Federal assistance or employ NG (Title 32 Authorities) under his command and control," e.g., to an attack against a DIB asset in that state. This addresses the use of National Guard cyber forces directly under the authority of a State Governor.

Hopes proposes that "NG and Reserve components should be made more available to exponentially increase capacity to USCYBERCOM," because "NG and Reserve personnel as well versed in technical fields and can be utilized to increase capacity" and "NG and Reserve Components are better suited to recruit highly skilled Soldiers that are already working in the civilian industry."

This paper again notes McKinney's (2013) proposal for a "NG Cybersecurity Program

that integrates forces, operating in a Title 32 status, into DHS’s NCCIC, NSA’s NTOC, the FBI, and integrates additional forces into USCYBERCOM,” providing for “an absolute force strategy that is more conducive to protecting against cyber threats to [Critical Infrastructure and Key Resources] that are evolutionary and global.”

Figure 2.2: Conceptual National Guard Cybersecurity Program (McKinney, 2013)

2.2.1.4 The Federated Intelligence Program at the State Level

In 2013, “Department of Defense (DoD) Instruction 3300.05 was published instructing all DoD entities including the Defense Intelligence Agency, COCOMs [note: this is a legacy acronym for Combatant Commands (CCMDs)], the Services, the Army National Guard Bureau, and all five Reserve Services to fully integrate the reserve components into the Defense Intelligence Enterprise” (Kirschner & McGarry, 2015). With this clear directive, the Army National Guard moved quickly at the direction of Lieutenant General Mary Legere, then the Director of Intelligence (G2) for the Army, to create a model to integrate

Guard and Reserve *intelligence* personnel in Title 32 status into national *intelligence* missions, with the philosophy of “Intelligence Readiness: No Cold Starts, No MI Soldier At Rest” (Legere, 2015). The ARNG calls this model the Federated Intelligence Program (FIP) (Kirschner & McGarry, 2015).

Through FIP, Guard intelligence personnel provide intelligence expertise, support, and analysis to a Combatant Command (CCMD) or Combat Support Agency (CSA), such as the National Security Agency (NSA), Defense Intelligence Agency (DIA), National Geospatial-Intelligence Agency (NGA), or the National Reconnaissance Office (NRO) while in Title 32 status (drill, AT, and other Title 32 duty statuses. Soldiers are assigned to the FIP mission on a rotating basis. A Mission Manager at each FIP site coordinates availability, intelligence requirements, operations, and so on. While assigned to FIP, this is the assigned soldier’s primary focus beyond baseline administrative requirements.

While FIP offers a valuable precedent for training-aligned operational support under Title 32, it should not be construed as a direct analog for cyberspace operations. Intelligence activities operate under distinct statutory authorities, oversight mechanisms, and institutional norms that differ from those governing cyber operations. This study therefore treats FIP as a conceptual reference point rather than a prescriptive model, demonstrating how structured governance and training alignment enable operational support for missions in the information domain while in Title 32 status.

2.2.1.5 DoD Instruction 3300.05: Reserve Component Intelligence Enterprise (RCIE) Management

DoDI 3300.05 (USD I&S, 2020) does not change any law or provide additional legal basis, but gave the Army’s Reserve Component Intelligence Enterprise (RCIE) a policy foundation from which to establish “operational support” of national intelligence missions while in Title 32 status:

3. UNDER SECRETARY OF DEFENSE FOR PERSONNEL AND READI-

NESS (USD(P&R)). The USD(P&R):

a. Develops Total Force policies that encourage RC recruiting and retention, achieve optimal alignment and integration of Active Component (AC) and RC personnel, facilitate efficient and effective training, and foster shared use of resources to provide the greatest operational benefit to missions pursuant to Reference (c) and in accordance with Vice Chairman of the Joint Chiefs of Staff and Assistant Secretary of Defense for Reserve Affairs Report (Reference (o)).

(1) Provide guidance and oversight for the development of programs that enable the operational capabilities of the RC as part of the Total Force.

(2) Develop policies to support the effective planning, organization, and use of the RC to provide operational support during inactive duty for training (IDT), annual training (AT), and active duty (AD) periods of service, including National Guard service pursuant to section 502 of Reference (f).

2.2.1.6 National Guard Forces in the Cyber Domain

In 2015 the trend of examination of methods for the integration of National Guard cyber forces into national missions continued.

McCullough (2015) states that “DoD should integrate the National Guard into the national cyber forces because of the cyber threats and the need for assistance at the state level.” The 2015 National Defense Authorization Act (NDAA) stated, “The reserve component has a role in the defense of the United States against cyber threats and consideration should be given to how the reserve component might be integrated into a comprehensive national approach for cyber defense.”

Examining the Title 32 authorities landscape further, it is noted that, “[w]hile DoD could place Guard forces in a Title 10 status for offensive operations, it can immediately utilize them in their Title 32 status for defensive cyber operations,” and that as “a part of the total force, the Guard provides a better way to pursue the strategic objective of defending critical infrastructure.” Also noted is the Stafford Act authorizing the use of National Guard forces in Title 32 status during major disasters or emergencies declared by the President.

As such, McCullouch focuses on the roles where National Guard cyber forces can best assist. Examples are the creation of “cybersecurity teams that include a mix of professionals from the private sector, state agencies, and the National Guard.” While the Guard is “not in a position to supplement a state’s normal day-to-day cybersecurity operations,” it “can assist in incident response and in a coordinate, train, advise, and assist (C/TAA) role for other state agencies.”

But on the topic of National Guard cyber support to federal missions, the options are again less clear. In 2013-2014 a bill known as the Cyber Warrior Act was introduced by Sen. Kirsten Gillibrand (D-NY). While the bill did not pass, it called for the creation of “National Guard Cyber and Computer Network Incident Response Teams (CCNIRT),” and explicitly “recognized that the Guard could operate in a Title 10 or Title 32 status based off the particular situation.”

In the 2014 NDAA, Congress asked DoD to create plans for “integrating the Guard and other Reserve Component units to meet total force requirements for cyber security,” and “to identify all Guard cyber resources, to assess the manpower needs for cyber operations forces, to evaluate the potential roles of the Guard in a concept of operations and employment, to identify the mission requirements that could be conducted by the Guard.”

McCullouch notes that Section 933 of the 2014 NDAA asked if “the National Guard, when activated in a State status (either State Active Duty or in a duty status under Title

32, United States Code) [could] operate under unique and useful authorities to support domestic cyber missions and requirements of the Department or the USCYBERCOM.” The DoD response to these questions is unanswered with respect to the ultimate creation of Army National Guard cyber forces that as of this writing are not a part of the Cyber Mission Force (CMF) nor the DoD’s Cyberspace Operations Forces (COF).

McCullouch closes by concluding that “National Guard cyber capabilities should be fully integrated with DoD’s overall cyber response” and that National Guard units that are currently performing cyber missions “should be aligned with active duty units and more fully integrated with their training and operations.” Furthermore, professionals with cyber expertise may desire to serve in uniform, but not in a regular active duty status. National Guard cyber forces act as a vehicle to access that talent.

Because National Guard cyber forces are the closest to the “front lines” of future cyber attacks, they are best positioned to detect and defend against those attacks, making the “National Guard’s integration into the larger DoD cyber forces is critical to developing an integrated web to catch these actors prior to an attack.”

2.2.1.7 Using the Oldest Military Force for the Newest National Defense

In the Journal of Strategic Security, Claus et al. (2015) engaged with colleagues on an analysis of how to utilize the National Guard for cyber operations, but took a novel approach, opening with the fact that “[a]pproximately 85 percent of America’s critical infrastructure is owned and operated by private industry,” and largely mediated by Industrial Control Systems (ICS).

In 2014, Colorado Governor John Hickenlooper, then the vice chair of the National Governors Association, warned that, “the next battlefield is likely not a field or town, but a computer network that supports our critical infrastructure.” Admiral Michael Rogers, former DIRNSA/CHCSS and Commander, USCYBERCOM, stated in March 4, 2015, testimony before the House Armed Services Committee, “The U.S. government, the states

and the private sector can't defend their information systems on their own against the most powerful cyber forces.”

This is the backdrop for this paper’s analysis, which again mentions the Cyber Warrior Act as well as the National Guard cyber provisions in the 2015 NDAA. Claus et al. again note that the National Guard can operate both in Title 10 and Title 32 status, providing added flexibility in responding to cyber threats against the homeland. The authors also note that the National Guard is exempt from the Posse Comitatus Act when in Title 32 status, easing support to law enforcement. They then enumerate some examples of application of National Guard cyber forces in Maryland, Michigan, and California.

The authors recommend that for maximum effectiveness of cyber defenses given the prevalence of privately owned and operated critical infrastructure, effective public-private partnerships (PPPs) must be developed for collective cyber defense. The authors’ interviews with National Guard and DHS cyber defense teams and private critical infrastructure operators exposed four recurring key features for effective PPPs: relationships, competency, shared equities and governance (Figure 2.3).

Figure 2.3: Critical Infrastructure Cyber Defense Model (Claus et al., 2015)

One example of National Guard participation in cyber defense is “acting as a fusion cell to interpret the many government cyber threat feeds and filter[ing] out the most serious threats to critical infrastructure providers.” Thus, National Guard cyber teams

“will have to develop effective private-public partnerships with those private industries in order to be successful in this new mission set vital to our nation’s security.”

2.2.1.8 Total Army Cyber Mission Force: Reserve Component Integration

Papenfus (2016) makes the argument that constrained budgets and the uncertainty of future missions calls for a “Total Force” concept (Guard and Reserve, together known as “Reserve Component” (RC) integration). Furthermore, current USCYBERCOM and Army Cyber Command (ARCYBER) requirements are greater than the active component forces available to fill them, with the Army RC “uniquely postured to fill current, midterm and longer-term cyber gap requirements.”

Papenfus opens with a vignette about the response to the 2008 cyberattack against US military networks, known as Operation Buckshot, where RC personnel were “eventually mobilized for longer periods to provide the surge capacity needed to mitigate and counter the attack.” In order for the Army to meet its mission obligations, there is no alternative but to leverage Guard and Reserve forces.

Papenfus continues with an analysis of the various authorities and organizations constructs under which Army Reserve (USAR) and Army National Guard (ARNG) cyber forces may operate, and describes the now-current 133 teams that make up the CMF: 13 National Mission Teams (NMTs), 8 National Support Teams (NSTs), 27 Combat Mission Teams (CMTs), 17 Combat Support Teams (CSTs), 18 National Cyber Protection Teams (CPTs), 24 Service CPTs, and 26 Combatant Command or DoD Information Network (DoDIN) CPTs (Figures 2.4, 2.5 and 2.6). The paper continues with a summary of CMF authorities, and the US Army cyber organization and mission areas.

Figure 2.4: Department of Defense Cyber Mission Force Relationships (JP 3-12) (Joint Chiefs of Staff, 2018)

Figure 2.5: Command and Control of the Cyber Mission Force (JP 3-12) (Joint Chiefs of Staff, 2018)

Figure 2.6: The Cyber Mission Force (CMF) (Cyber Mission Force Fact Sheet) (Army Cyber Command, 2020)

USAR and ARNG cyber capabilities are then covered. Again, the observation is made that “ARNG units can assist local and state governmental agencies nationwide to defend critical infrastructure networks,” and concludes that “integration within state and local agencies, not restricted by the Posse Comitatus Act, and having ties to Department of Homeland Security (DHS) places the ARNG (Title 32) CPTs in the best position to support USNORTHCOM’s mission for Defense Support of Civil Authorities (DSCA).”

For ARNG in Title 32 status, Papenfus reiterates that personnel on Title 32 are paid with federal funding, but are still under control of the Governor, and overseen by state law. Because of this, “A key advantage during a Presidential disaster or emergency declaration is their activated with federal funding while still not being subject to Posse Comitatus Act limitations.”

Papenfus concludes that the Total Force concept is necessary as cyberspace plays an increasingly important role in projection of military power, and that the Army Guard and Reserve are “uniquely postured to fill current, midterm and longer-term cyber re-

quirements, but it requires planning and investment now in training, development, and integrations of the RC CMF.”

2.2.1.9 Moving Left of Boom: Leveraging Title 32 National Guardsmen to Share Cyber Threat Intelligence With State Authorities

The proposals to use the Guard in a Title 32 status for cyber functions continued to evolve, with Archer (2016) asking, “How can the National Guard (NG) legally aid in the prevention of cyber attacks by providing cyber threat intelligence to state governments?” Archer states in the paper introduction that, “the lack of legal clarity and intelligence oversight concerns may deter intelligence sharing by the National Guard,” but that “with the proper approval; the NG can be leveraged to share intelligence and help alleviate the high demand for skilled analysts.”

The key point made about Guard personnel in Title 32 status is that they are federally funded but under the control of the governor, and that while in any Title 32 status, personnel are training for their federal mission. Archer then conducts a review of Executive Orders, Regulations, and Directives which pertain or relate to National Guard personnel and cyber functions, as well as several federal- and state-focused cyber strategy documents. Archer also cites intelligence-related policy regulations, and the perceived lack of clarity about which cyber activities or functions may constitute an “intelligence activity” and thus be subject to intelligence oversight.

Archer concludes that while intelligence activities are clearly subject to intelligence oversight, cyber information sharing may not be an intelligence activity — but that personnel may not understand the relevant regulations. The distinction is made that information sharing, e.g., of cyber threat data, does not constitute “intelligence” if it is not subject to analysis and refinement into an intelligence product. This is a key distinction for National Guard personnel in Title 32 status. Archer recommends a blanket request from the National Guard Bureau to the Secretary of Defense to allow all 54 states and

territories to use cyber intelligence analysts in a Title 32 training status and provide clear guidance that cyber intelligence work be focused exclusively on foreign actors.

2.2.1.10 The Hybrid Benefits of the National Guard

Forscey and Ruiz (2019) analyze the National Guard's unique role in U.S. cybersecurity, emphasizing its hybrid status under Title 32 and its ability to support both state and national cyber defense missions. The authors argue that the National Guard is an underutilized asset in national cybersecurity, despite its flexibility to operate under state, federal, and hybrid authorities.

The study highlights how the National Guard can be activated under three primary statuses:

- State Active Duty (SAD): The governor activates Guard personnel for local emergencies, with state funding and control.
- Title 32: The governor, with Defense Department approval, can deploy Guard members for federally funded state operations, maintaining state control.
- Title 10: The president federalizes Guard forces, shifting control to the federal government for national defense missions.

The National Guard's cyber units often operate under Title 32 status, which allows them to provide cyber defense at the state level while being funded by the federal government. This status is particularly valuable because it enables Guard units to:

- Respond to cyber incidents affecting state and local governments, such as ransomware attacks.
- Engage in cybersecurity assessments and network protection for critical infrastructure.

- Support election security, as seen in Washington, Wisconsin, Illinois, and Ohio, where Guard personnel provided cybersecurity monitoring.

The study argues that Title 32 offers a critical advantage because it allows the National Guard to operate domestically without the restrictions of the Posse Comitatus Act, which limits federal military operations on U.S. soil. This legal flexibility makes the Guard an ideal force for cyber incident response, as it can assist state and local agencies without the legal and bureaucratic hurdles associated with active-duty military involvement.

Despite its advantages, the National Guard faces challenges in fully realizing its cybersecurity potential:

- Limited federal capacity: The Department of Homeland Security (DHS) and the FBI lack the resources to provide comprehensive cyber assistance to state and local governments, leading to gaps that the Guard could fill.
- Legal and bureaucratic hurdles: The Defense Department's current policies restrict how Title 32 funding can be used for cybersecurity operations, limiting the Guard's ability to assist with preventive security measures.
- Coordination issues: The Guard's role in national cyber defense remains poorly defined, with varying capabilities across states and inconsistent integration with federal cybersecurity strategies.

The study suggests several policy changes to better integrate the National Guard into national cybersecurity efforts:

1. Expand the use of Title 32 for cybersecurity operations, allowing Guard units to conduct preemptive cyber defense activities.
2. Increase funding for Guard cyber units to enhance training, equipment, and readiness for cyber incident response.

3. Develop clearer federal guidance to formalize the National Guard's role in national cyber strategy and incident response.
4. Enhance coordination with civilian agencies, ensuring that Guard units establish relationships with state and local governments before cyber incidents occur.
5. Improve training and joint exercises, such as Cyber Guard and Cyber Shield, to strengthen collaboration between the Guard, U.S. Cyber Command (USCYBERCOM), and civilian cybersecurity agencies.

Forscey and Ruiz argue that the National Guard is uniquely positioned to bridge the gap between federal cybersecurity efforts and state-level needs. Its ability to operate under Title 32 makes it a vital tool for cyber defense, yet outdated policies and bureaucratic hurdles limit its full potential. The study calls for greater investment in Guard cyber capabilities, improved federal coordination, and expanded legal authorities to allow the Guard to proactively defend U.S. infrastructure against cyber threats. These findings align with broader discussions on leveraging the National Guard for cyber incident response and national cybersecurity integration (Lacroix, 2023; Neville, 2023).

2.2.2 Recent Proposals

2.2.2.1 Election Infrastructure Security: Grants and Reimbursement to the States for Usage of their National Guards in State Active Duty Status to Provide Cybersecurity for Federal Elections

By 2020, attention to election security had increased, as well as the role of the National Guard in providing cybersecurity support to elections. Muller and Thomas (2020) note that federal elections are state-administered activities with a federal nexus, and that the federal government should therefore provide grants and reimbursement to states when utilizing Guard personnel for election cybersecurity support on State Active Duty (SAD).

SAD differs from Title 32 in that it is funded with state dollars, but in the context of federal election support is still aiding a federal function.

Muller and Thomas suggest that such reimbursement only cover Defensive Cyberspace Operations-Internal Defensive Measures (DCO-IDM) (Figure 2.7). Because this is a domestic critical infrastructure defense task, the Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency (CISA) would be the lead coordinating agency.

Figure 2.7: Cyberspace Operations Missions and Actions (JP 3-12) (Joint Chiefs of Staff, 2018)

2.2.2.2 The Militarization of Cyberspace: Cyber-Related Provisions in the National Defense Authorization Act

In 2021, more cyber provisions would be added to the NDAA. Garcia (2021) examines these in a summary monograph on specific cyber provisions in the 2021 NDAA, to include those relevant to National Guard employment for cyber activities. One is a “pilot program to determine how National Guard units could provide remote assistance to other units to help states train, prepare for, and respond to cyber incidents,” and the other will “detail when a governor could deploy their National Guard units to respond to cyber incidents with federal reimbursement (known as Title 32 operations) and prescribe how the National Guard would collaborate with other civilian agencies to respond to a cyberattack.”

However, Garcia concludes that “outside of a few provisions that empowered DHS to help state and locals and provided election-security assistance,” the last several years’ NDAAs have not significantly moved forward cyber assistance to state and local governments.

2.2.2.3 Federated Cyber Program Concept

In 2021, the author proposed a model for Army National Guard cyber forces to provide operational support to national cyber missions called the Federated Cyber Program (FCP) (Schroeder, 2023). Like the Federated Intelligence Program (FIP) support to combatant commands, the expertise present in ARNG Cyber Protection Teams (CPTs) can be applied to cyber mission support while in Title 32 status. This program meets a mission need while fulfilling training requirements, and can be conducted in the context of cybersecurity research and Defensive Cyberspace Operations consistent with the mission, function, and assigned tasks of a CPT. This real-world mission support model is also a key recruiting and retention tool for critical cyber expertise in the Guard and Reserve Total Force.

In the FCP construct, National Guard personnel can provide cybersecurity subject

matter expertise and support to DoD while in a Title 32 status. The personnel assigned to FCP are in cyber designators (e.g., 17 series) and assigned to a cyber unit (e.g., a CPT). These personnel are not in an intelligence unit or designator and do not perform intelligence collection or analysis, and thus are not performing an intelligence or intelligence-related activity as defined by applicable policy. This activity is characterized as cybersecurity research or cybersecurity situational awareness.

FCP personnel work with mission managers in DoD to identify gaps in requirements that could be filled with the specialized expertise of Guard cyber personnel on drill weekends or on other Title 32 order types. FCP personnel ensure that such work also meets a training requirement. For example, ARNG cyber personnel in a CPT will ensure that FCP missions are consistent with the training requirements specified in USCYBERCOM Cyber Warfare Publication (CWP) 3-33.4, *Cyber Protection Team (CPT) Organization, Functions, and Employment*; USCYBERCOM Cyber Technical Manual 7-0.2: *Cyber Mission Force (CMF) Training and Readiness (T&R) Manual*, and/or *ARCYBER FY23-28 Defensive Cyberspace Operations (DCO) Training Objectives and Goals*, or similar applicable readiness and training requirements publications. When additional support or continuity is required, FCP personnel can be placed on active duty in either a Title 32 (e.g., 502(f)) or Title 10 status, as appropriate.

FCP success under the above criteria depends on two factors: 1. Assignment of only cyber personnel in cyber units to FCP missions, and 2. Ensuring FCP mission activities also meet a training requirement. A mission partner will expect productive work to be done, and constant vetting of work will be required to ensure the work is always meeting a training requirement and could not be misconstrued as constituting an intelligence activity. FCP managers coordinate with intelligence oversight (IO) personnel to ensure these distinctions are understood.

2.2.2.4 Using National Guard Cyber Forces to support Homeland Cyber Defense activities in non-DoD-Owned Cyberspace

A 2022 study conducted by the Institute for Defense Analyses (IDA) (Ayers et al., 2022) examined the growing demand for National Guard cyber forces to support homeland cyber defense activities beyond the Department of Defense Information Network (DoDIN). Commissioned by the National Guard Bureau (NGB), the study explored the statutory and operational feasibility of employing National Guard cyber personnel in Title 32 status for missions within non-DoD-owned cyberspace, including state and private sector networks.

The study's premise aligns with ongoing trends of increasing cyberattacks against critical infrastructure, including hospitals, local governments, and utilities. It noted that while large institutions may have resources to respond to such threats, smaller entities often turn to state resources — including the National Guard — for help. The research emphasized that while Guard forces have robust cyber capabilities, they are limited in capacity and not positioned to be the sole solution to national cyber defense needs. In particular, the study stressed that over-reliance on the National Guard for off-DoDIN support could impair their ability to meet federal (Title 10) obligations.

Title 32 authority, especially the Homeland Defense Activity (HDA) provisions under 32 USC §§901–908, was analyzed in depth. While theoretically offering flexibility to use National Guard cyber forces for critical infrastructure protection, the IDA found that the lack of a “prototypical scenario” and restrictive criteria — such as attribution to a state actor engaged in open conflict with the U.S. — make HDA approvals unlikely. The authors could not find an example of an approved HDA request, and at least three HDA requests submitted by states were denied by the Secretary of Defense.

A key contribution of the IDA report is its framework for National Guard cyber support to off-DoDIN activities 2.8, which emphasized pre-incident operations (e.g., assessments, planning, and exercises) as more viable and sustainable than *in-extremis* responses. The

Figure 2.8: Comparison of Relative Use of National Guard Authorities when Conducting Off-DoDIN Cyber Actions
(Ayers et al., 2022)

study recommended collaboration with offices such as the Office of the Assistant Secretary of Defense for Homeland Defense and Global Security (HD&GS) to refine scenarios that might justify HDA requests under Title 32. It also advocated aligning Guard activities with DoD’s mission assurance priorities to bolster justification for federal funding.

The study concluded that although legal and policy mechanisms currently exist for employing National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status for certain national missions, operational limitations and policy ambiguity continue to restrict implementation. Nonetheless, the report supported the notion that a structured approach emphasizing training alignment, strategic collaboration, and selective mission support could expand the Guard’s role in a manner consistent with current law and policy.

2.2.2.5 Posturing U.S. Cyber Forces to Defend the Homeland

Neville (2023) examines the evolving cyber threat landscape and the critical need for the U.S. Department of Defense (DoD) to effectively position its cyber forces to defend the homeland. The study highlights increasing threats from state actors such as Russia and

China, particularly following geopolitical tensions like the Russo-Ukrainian war and U.S.-China frictions over Taiwan. The author emphasizes that adversaries are likely to target U.S. critical infrastructure, including the power grid, transportation networks, and energy systems, as a means to undermine national security and power projection capabilities.

A key focus of Neville's work is the necessity for a coordinated response between U.S. Northern Command (USNORTHCOM), U.S. Cyber Command (USCYBERCOM), the Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency (CISA), the Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI), and other federal and non-federal stakeholders. Neville argues that cyber defense is inherently a "team sport," but current federal cyber laws, regulations, and interagency relationships create significant challenges to a unified cyber defense strategy. (Figure 2.9)

To address these challenges, Neville proposes the creation of a Complex Catastrophe Cyber Stakeholders, Communications, Authorities, and Narratives (C3 SCAN) framework, designed to foster collaboration, validate operational plans, and integrate public and private sector stakeholders into a cohesive cyber defense effort. The study also discusses legal complexities, including the roles of Titles 10, 32, and 50 of the U.S. Code in governing cyber operations, as well as the limitations posed by the Posse Comitatus Act.

Figure 2.9: Strategic and Operational Command Environment. Note National Guard in U.S. Military quadrant in upper right.

(Neville, 2023)

The research underscores the importance of proactive and integrated cyber defense mechanisms, drawing historical parallels with World War II's Operation Drumbeat, where fragmented and uncoordinated coastal defenses allowed German U-boats to inflict significant damage. Neville suggests that, just as the U.S. ultimately adapted to counter such asymmetric threats, the modern cyber domain requires a similarly agile and cooperative approach.

This work contributes to the broader discourse on National Guard and Reserve Component cyber forces by reinforcing the argument that cyber defense requires a whole-of-government and whole-of-nation approach. While Neville primarily focuses on active-duty cyber forces and federal coordination, his findings align with discussions on National Guard cyber force integration, particularly in Title 32 status, as explored in other literature (Claus et al., 2015; McCullouch, 2015). His emphasis on interagency collaboration and legal frameworks provides a valuable foundation for further analysis of how the Na-

tional Guard can contribute to national cyber defense efforts.

2.2.2.6 Raising the Cyber Guard: Analyzing the Cost and Use of the National Guard in Local Municipal and State Cyber Defense

Lacroix (2023) critically examines the role of the National Guard in defending municipal and state-level cyber infrastructure, assessing both cost-effectiveness and the broader sociological barriers to its utilization. The dissertation identifies a significant gap in how municipal and state governments incorporate the National Guard into their cyber incident response frameworks, despite the federal prioritization of cybersecurity as a homeland security concern.

A key focus of the study is a two-pronged research question: (1) whether it is more cost-effective for state and local governments to use the National Guard for cyber incident response rather than private sector contractors, and (2) whether sociological perceptions of the National Guard's role in disaster response create barriers to its employment in cyber defense. LaCroix employs a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative cost analyses of major cyber incidents with qualitative survey research from emergency management, military, law enforcement, and cybersecurity professionals.

The cost analysis portion of the study compares real-world ransomware attacks, including the 2019 Baltimore, Texas, and Louisiana cyber incidents. LaCroix finds that states like Texas and Louisiana, which had pre-established cyber emergency response plans incorporating the National Guard, were able to mitigate cyber threats more efficiently and at a lower cost than municipalities that relied exclusively on private contractors. The Baltimore case, in particular, underscores the financial burden of failing to leverage National Guard cyber resources, as the city incurred \$18.2 million in remediation costs while bypassing National Guard assistance.

The qualitative research further uncovers a widespread lack of understanding among state and local officials regarding the National Guard's cyber capabilities. Surveys indi-

cate that emergency managers and policymakers are more likely to associate the National Guard with traditional disaster response (e.g., hurricanes and floods) than cyber emergencies. Furthermore, concerns about the legality of National Guard cyber operations under Title 32 status, as well as distrust between private sector firms and military entities regarding proprietary information, contribute to hesitancy in engaging the Guard for cyber defense.

LaCroix calls for policy changes that institutionalize the use of National Guard cyber units at the state and municipal levels, drawing parallels to established frameworks for natural disaster response under the Stafford Act. The study aligns with broader discussions on National Guard cyber force integration (Neville, 2023) and contributes empirical evidence demonstrating that the National Guard is both a cost-effective and underutilized asset in domestic cyber defense.

2.2.2.7 Training National Guard Cyber Forces: Clarifying Title 32 Authorities

In 2023, Colonel Sam Kinch (U.S. Air Force, Retired) published a white paper addressing the legal and operational ambiguities surrounding National Guard cyber force training under Title 32 authority (Kinch, 2023). The paper, titled *A Call to Action: Effectively Utilizing the National Guard Under Title 32*, seeks to clarify which cyberspace actions Reserve Component (RC) cyber personnel may conduct while in Title 32 status in order to maintain operational readiness for their federally-assigned missions.

Kinch frames the core problem as uncertainty regarding which cyberspace actions are legally permissible for National Guard cyber forces operating under state command authority while training to federal Cyber Mission Force (CMF) standards. This uncertainty has practical consequences for work role currency requirements, particularly affecting Title 32 National Guard personnel operating in traditional or Active Guard and Reserve (AGR) capacities during dwell periods between mobilizations. As USCYBERCOM tran-

sitioned from building to maintaining a trained CMF following full operational capability in 2018, the need for clarity on Title 32 training authorities became increasingly pressing.

The white paper provides a comprehensive examination of the legal frameworks governing National Guard cyber operations, drawing from multiple authoritative sources including Joint Publication 1, Joint Publication 3-12 (Cyberspace Operations) (Joint Chiefs of Staff, 2018, 2022), DoDI 1215.06 (USD P&R, 2022), and National Security Presidential Memoranda 13 and 21. Kinch emphasizes a critical doctrinal distinction: cyberspace missions are categorized based on the *intent or objective* of the issuing authority, while cyberspace actions are defined exclusively by the *types of effects* they create. This distinction has significant implications for determining what activities National Guard personnel may conduct under Title 32 authority.

Drawing from Joint Publication 3-12, Kinch identifies four cyberspace actions: Cyberspace Security, Cyberspace Defense, Cyberspace Exploitation, and Cyberspace Attack. The paper argues that three of these actions — Cyberspace Security (mission assurance), Cyberspace Defense (incident response), and Cyberspace Exploitation (enabling activities) — can be legally authorized for Title 32 training to federal missions. These actions align with NSPM-13/21 definitions of Cyber Collection and Cyber Effects Enabling Activities. Crucially, Kinch contends that Cyberspace Attack, which creates noticeable denial effects and constitutes a form of fires potentially crossing the use of force threshold, requires either Title 10 orders or specific authorization by POTUS or SECDEF under 32 USC § 502(f)(2)(A).

A central argument in the white paper is that “operations (regardless of the originating organization) are not exclusive of training; they are enablers of training” (Kinch, 2023). This framing supports the position that Title 32 cyber operators can support Title 10 operations “outside the kill chain” under a Title 10 mission commander’s authority, provided the mission aligns with the Title 32 operator’s training readiness requirements. Kinch cites legal precedent from a 2007 Headquarters Air Force Operations and Interna-

tional Law Division review, which determined that analytical work roles further removed from immediate targeting — such as intelligence analysis not intended for immediate use — do not require Title 10 status.

The paper dedicates significant attention to framing Cyberspace Exploitation, often the most contentious action in legal discussions. Kinch notes that exploitation actions “include military intelligence activities, maneuver, information collection, and other enabling actions required to prepare for *future* military operations” (Joint Pub 3-12, II-6, emphasis in original). This temporal distinction — preparation for future rather than immediate operations — is critical to Kinch’s argument that exploitation activities fall within permissible Title 32 training. The paper further references a 2019 NSA Office of General Counsel legal opinion that validated and expanded support for Title 32 training in Cyberspace Exploitation.

Kinch introduces a novel recommendation for “hip pocket orders” in the cyber domain. Drawing from the Air National Guard’s established use of this mechanism for NORAD air defense missions, where Title 32 personnel can instantaneously transition to Title 10 status upon predetermined triggering events, the paper proposes similar arrangements for cyber operations. This would require updates to existing Memoranda of Agreement between USCYBERCOM and state National Guard organizations, identification of pre-approved triggering events, and standardized language in Title 32 orders. Such arrangements would enable cyber operators to rapidly transition authorities in direct support of USCYBERCOM operations when cyberspace attack actions become necessary.

The white paper also addresses a significant but often overlooked consideration regarding Status of Forces Agreement (SOFA) requirements. While RC personnel traveling physically outside the Continental United States (OCONUS) require Title 10 orders for SOFA coverage, Kinch argues this requirement should not apply to CONUS-based cyber operators conducting cyberspace actions with OCONUS effects. As cyberspace operations occur in a virtual domain separate from traditional geographic space, SOFA considera-

tions — which protect personnel physically present in foreign nations — are inapplicable to personnel who remain physically within the United States.

The paper concludes with a summary table of recommended cyberspace actions authorized for training National Guard cyber forces under different duty statuses (Figure 2.2).

Table 2.2: Recommended National Guard Cyber Authorities Alignment (Kinch, 2023)

Cyberspace Action	Doctrinal Alignment	Title 10	Title 32	SAD
Cyberspace Security <i>(Network Defense)</i>	DoDIN Operations	✓	✓ Training*	As directed by governor
Cyberspace Defense <i>(Network Defense)</i>	DCO-IDM	✓	✓ Training*	As directed by governor
Cyberspace Exploitation <i>(Cyber Collection/Enabling)</i>	DCO-RA	✓	✓ Training*	—
Cyberspace Attack <i>(Cyber Effect)</i>	DCO-RA OCO	✓	Authorization Required**	—
*Training to federal mission standards under T&R Oversight authority				
**Requires POTUS/SECDEF authorization per 32 USC §502(f)(2)(A)				

Kinch’s analysis provides significant theoretical and practical foundations for the employment of National Guard cyber forces in support of national missions. The white paper’s framework aligns with and extends the proposals of Muller & Thomas 2020 regarding DCO-IDM activities, while offering more granular guidance on the specific cyberspace actions permissible under Title 32. The Federated Intelligence Program (FIP), which Kinch cites as precedent for Title 32 personnel supporting federal requirements, directly informs the Federated Cyber Program (FCP) concept proposed by this author (Schroeder, 2023). The legal analysis presented establishes that existing authorities already permit substantial integration of Guard cyber forces into national missions when properly structured around training requirements.

The significance of Kinch’s work lies in its systematic compilation of applicable legal authorities, doctrinal references, and practical recommendations into a coherent framework for National Guard cyber force employment. By distinguishing between mission intent and action effects, and by clearly delineating the “kill chain” boundary that separates permissible training activities from those requiring federal orders, the paper provides

actionable guidance for commanders, staff judge advocates, and policymakers. These distinctions are essential for resolving the legal and policy ambiguities that have historically constrained Guard and Reserve cyber integration into national missions—a theme that emerges repeatedly in the literature and in practitioner discourse (Forscey & Ruiz, 2019; Garcia, 2021).

While Kinch provides a thorough legal analysis, the paper acknowledges that implementation requires coordination across multiple stakeholders including USCYBERCOM, the National Guard Bureau, state Adjutants General, and Service Component Commands. The recommendations for hip pocket orders, MOA updates, and standardized order language represent administrative and policy changes that, while feasible, require sustained institutional effort to implement. The framework presented nonetheless represents a substantial contribution to clarifying the conditions under which National Guard cyber forces can train to, and operationally support, federal cyber missions under existing legal authorities.

2.2.2.8 Empowering the National Guard for OT Cyber Defense

In an opinion piece in *RealClearDefense*, Robert Lee (2025), CEO of cybersecurity firm Dragos, argues that the United States is leaving critical cyber capacity on the table by not systematically leveraging the National Guard for the defense of domestic critical infrastructure. Framing the problem against increasingly sophisticated cyber threats to operational technology (OT) and industrial control systems (ICS) in sectors such as lifeline critical infrastructure sectors as power, water, and transportation, he contends that National Guard cyber units are uniquely positioned to help defend these systems because of their dual state–federal status, local presence, and deep private-sector expertise. Lee notes that existing public–private mechanisms such as ISACs already provide a framework for sharing threat information with state and local entities, and he suggests that National Guard cyber forces should be more tightly integrated with these efforts to provide surge

capacity, threat-hunting, and incident-response support at the state level. While the article does not offer a detailed legal analysis, it recommends the creation of a “National Cybersecurity Center of Excellence (NCCoE)” to enable a more deliberate, national-level use of the Guard for cyber defense, provided Guard cyber units receive appropriate resourcing, clear tasking, and sustained partnerships with state CISO offices and federal cyber centers.

Lee is himself an Army National Guard Cyber Warfare Officer, who received a direct commission to Lieutenant Colonel (O-5) to assist the National Guard with operationalizing OT cybersecurity (Keller, 2025). As such, this article represents a high-profile example of the policy discourse that calls for “empowering” the National Guard in cyberspace without fully resolving how Title 32 authorities, doctrine, and command relationships should be employed. Like earlier proposals that envision a “Cyber National Guard” or Guard-centric critical-infrastructure defense models, his argument highlights the Guard’s comparative advantages (technical talent, community ties, and flexible status) but largely treats the legal and doctrinal questions as background issues rather than as primary research problems. In doing so, the article reinforces the central gap identified in this study: senior leaders and influential commentators repeatedly assert that the Guard must play a larger role in national cyber defense, yet there remains limited concrete guidance on how to integrate Guard cyber forces into national missions under Title 32 in a way that is both legally grounded and operationally repeatable.

2.2.2.9 National Guard Association of the United States (NGAUS) cyber advocacy

The National Guard Association of the United States (NGAUS), the primary advocacy and lobbying organization of the National Guard, argues in its *FY26 Cyber Fact Sheet* (Plamann, 2025) to “Allow the National Guard to serve as a conduit for cyber operations between federal, state, and local governments, as well as the private sector”

and further notes that “The traditional part-time nature of the majority of the National Guard force also allows the Department of Defense to retain well-trained cyber warriors when they depart the Active Component after their service obligation is complete for other opportunities. The National Guard captures the experience of those servicemembers while allowing them to seek other career opportunities, which significantly reduces the military’s challenge of training and retaining highly skilled warriors.” The key issue as articulated by NGUAS is that, “The National Guard is and should continue to be a critical partner in developing, planning, and executing the Department of Defense strategy in the cyber domain.”

Of note, Title 10 “hip pocket” autoconversion for cyber training (as proposed by Kinch (2023) (see Section 2.2.2.7)) was proposed as a resolution at the 2025 annual conference of the National Guard Association of the United States (NGAUS) by Colonel Sarah Frater, Deputy Chief of Staff for Cyber and Electromagnetic Warfare, and Colonel Jeannie Jeanetta, Chief of Staff—Joint Staff, both of the Wisconsin National Guard, with additional state cosponsors, in August 2025.

2.2.2.10 Comments from Army Principal Cyber Advisor

On the McCrary Institute’s *Cyber Focus* podcast, Army Principal Cyber Advisor Brandon Pugh noted the rationale for using Guard and Reserve cyber expertise (Pugh, 2025):

“When you think about what resources the Army has, one of the key ones is our National Guard and Reservists. [...] These are individuals that live in their local communities, often hold cyber jobs. Matter of fact, some of our — it’s extraordinary, this isn’t an exaggeration — we have some individuals that show up to their reserve weekend in three, four hundred thousand dollar vehicles because they are the experts in what they do as civilians. They have signed up and taken the oath because they want to serve this country. That

is the talent we have in the Reserve and Guard that we need to continue to expand. You know, who is better to address some of these OT [Operational Technology] and critical infrastructure concerns than those who already are working in the power companies, the electric providers, have the expertise, and have the training? They're already doing it.”

2.2.2.11 Whole-of-Society Cyber Strategy and Digital Dominance

Recent strategic literature has increasingly characterized cyberspace as a persistent arena of competition rather than a discrete operational domain governed by episodic conflict. A prominent example of this shift is *Dominating the Digital Space: A Whole-of-Society Strategy for Securing the United States from Cyber Aggression*, produced by the Vanderbilt University Institute of National Security's Wicked Problems Lab in 2025 (Moore & Goldstein, 2025). The report situates U.S. cybersecurity challenges within a broader framework of long-term strategic competition, arguing that adversaries—most notably the People's Republic of China — are deliberately exploiting cyberspace below the threshold of armed conflict to erode American economic strength, military readiness, and societal resilience.

Although *Dominating the Digital Space* does not focus explicitly on National Guard authorities, its whole-of-society framing directly reinforces the central premise of this dissertation: that effective national cyber defense cannot rely solely on active-duty forces and federal agencies. The report's emphasis on distributed infrastructure, state-level impact, and workforce scale implicitly elevates the importance of National Guard cyber forces, whose dual federal-state status uniquely positions them to operate at the nexus of national security and critical infrastructure protection and resilience.

In particular, the report's call for persistent engagement, integrated resilience, and real-time visibility aligns with emerging models that leverage Title 32 authorities. It calls for the creation of a National Cyber Operations Team (NCOT) that “unifies gov-

ernment and private-sector cyber talent into a single, integrated team-of-teams under the operational control of U.S. Cyber Command,” that “scal[es] the effectiveness of Title 32 National Guard cyber forces operating in support of state and national resilience.” (Moore & Goldstein, 2025)

By framing cyber defense as a continuous, society-wide endeavor rather than a narrowly military function, *Dominating the Digital Space* provides strategic justification for exploring how existing National Guard authorities may be operationalized to support national cyber missions without requiring wholesale legislative reform.

2.2.2.12 Support and Leverage National Guard for Stronger Cyber Defense

In 2025, Lieutenant Colonel Giancarlo Moats (Michigan Air National Guard) published a professional commentary in *The Cyber Defense Review* arguing that military auxiliary organizations — particularly the National Guard — represent an underutilized resource for improving U.S. cyber defense capabilities (Moats, 2025). The article contends that regardless of whether an independent cyber force is established, auxiliary organizations offer force-multiplying opportunities that military planners often overlook.

Moats highlights the National Guard’s unique value proposition for cyber operations. Guard personnel “bring expertise in state-based systems and authorities to the national defense mission, as well as federal training in cyber to state defense efforts.” This bidirectional flow of expertise — civilian industry best practices flowing into military service, and federal cyber training enhancing state-level capabilities — represents a distinctive advantage of the Reserve Component model. The article notes that many civilian cyber professionals serve part-time in the National Guard, enabling the military to access current industry practices through individual service members.

The commentary identifies the *Cyber Yankee* exercise as an exemplar of National Guard-led cyber training. Held in the Northeastern United States, Cyber Yankee brings together Guard cyber forces with professionals from industry, academia, government, and

international partners to practice cyber defense and incident response. Moats argues such exercises put auxiliary organizations “front-and-center with tangible impacts upon military readiness and threat awareness” and deserve increased resourcing.

The article concludes with a warning: if an independent cyber force were established “without due regard for strengthening the relationships among existing auxiliaries,” there is “considerable risk of inadvertently muddling and undermining the country’s capabilities.” Thus, “whatever the future of USCYBERCOM, with or without a new cyber force, it will be critical for cyber auxiliaries to be given due regard for all that they can do in this domain.” This caution reinforces the importance of deliberate integration strategies for National Guard cyber forces — a central concern of this dissertation.

2.3 Concept of Cyber National Guard

As early as 2017, the concept of a “Cyber National Guard” has been discussed by members of Congress (Korolov, 2017). Goure (2017) noted that the National Guard has a “sophisticated capability for cyber defense” and “is a way of attracting and retaining desired [cyber] talent,” concluding that a “Cyber National Guard could help deter attacks on U.S. infrastructure.” Here experts and legislators acknowledge the expertise and the need for cyber expertise in the National Guard, and acknowledge the applicability of this expertise to 1. cybersecurity needs at the state level, and 2. requirements while mobilized in federal service under Title 10, but does not address the issue of utilization of such a force for national missions while in Title 32 status.

2.3.1 Connection with an Independent Cyber Force

Since the establishment of U.S. Cyber Command, there have been discussions, policy proposals, and legislation calling for a study into the establishment of a separate U.S. Cyber Force, culminating in a major effort in 2024 (Lonergan & Montgomery, 2024;

Lonergan et al., 2024; Luttrell, 2024) which resulted in language requiring an independent study by the National Academies of Science, Engineering, and Medicine (NASEM) in the FY25 NDAA (Matishak, 2025; Miller, 2025; Pomerleau, 2024b). The military services *generate* forces, while the combatant commands, like USCYBERCOM, *employ* forces. Each service is responsible for the "man, train, and equip" (MT&E) function for forces in their warfare domain — land, maritime, air, and space.

Because the National Guard is a key mechanism of the broader Reserve Components (Guard and Reserve) to retain talent in uniform when servicemembers leave active duty (Plamann, 2025), and because of the unique authorities alignment of the National Guard (Title 10, Title 32, SAD) (Forscey & Ruiz, 2019), any Cyber Force would need to have a robust Reserve Component (RC) to continue to leverage this expertise. Couillard (Couillard, 2024) writes about the imperative for a Cyber Force:

A new U.S. Cyber Force, addressing national cyber threats across all sectors, must incorporate a National Guard component. In a cyber emergency, whether state or local government or private sectors, state or territory Governors could mobilize their National Guard Cyber forces upon request. These Guard units, equipped with the same training and tools as the full-time cyber force, offer the added benefit of being locally based in the states they serve.

The Guard Cyber force could offer immediate emergency response and support to local law enforcement. It could provide state-specific vulnerability assessments, reporting findings to the Governor. Additionally, these forces would aid their parent service's Title 10 missions, having the same training and equipment as the active-duty force, similar to the current Army and Air Guard. The Cyber National Guard could recruit volunteers from their local commercial industries. Some of these professionals are already part of state and territory-aligned CPTs. Integrating these CPTs into a separate cyber military force as the Cyber National Guard component would standardize

training, equipment, and doctrine for both Title 32 and Title 10 missions.

Here, Couillard discusses the critical aspects of training standardization and active duty force augmentation and employment, but focuses on the use of the Cyber National Guard by state governors for local and state functions when not federally activated. However, it does not address the utilization of these National Guard forces for national cyber missions, aside from conventional employment on Title 10 active duty. This leaves the gap of utilization for national cyber missions beyond training while in a Title 32 status.

Lonergan and Montgomery (2025a) in a monograph on the need for a U.S. Cyber Force make the specific case that “[e]stablishing a Cyber Force would facilitate better use of legal authorities and Guard/Reserve components”:

Americans expect their military to protect them from foreign adversaries, but cyberspace is largely owned by companies and private individuals. Accordingly, building out a Cyber Force presents the opportunity to create structures with different authorities — especially for critical infrastructure protection and homeland defense — that can best leverage the experience and expertise found in the civilian population. Driving attention to the military’s relationship with the private sector will enable more effective integration and collaboration with robust Guard, Reserve, and auxiliary components. To attract the best talent, the service would likely need to offer new incentives and flexible career paths tailored to technical experts. Establishing a Cyber Force would best accelerate innovation in recruiting, acquisition, and R&D freed from the weight of traditional service bureaucracies.

In 2025, Lonergan and Montgomery (2025b) again referenced the concept of a “Cyber Guard” in a new monograph as a part of the launch of a commission to define the parameters of a U.S. Cyber Force. (Chavez, 2025) Several specific issues are highlighted:

- flexible training regimens
- rotational and on-demand service
- virtual, remote, or local muster/drills
- ongoing, easily accessible training
- prepositioned security clearances, accesses, and accounts
- streamlined bureaucratic process with minimal administrative steps for activation
- response frameworks that integrate seamlessly with local and state authorities, or other federal agencies
- fluid transitions to and from the private sector or other government agencies, or between active-duty and guard/reserve status

Specifically on the National Guard component, Lonergan and Montgomery (2025b)

state:

The Unique Importance of a Cyber Guard

The traditional National Guard structure offers a unique blend of authorities making the Guard essential for domestic response. Typically, the Guard operates under Title 32 authorities under the command of the state's governor, enabling Guard units to conduct missions in support of emergency and disaster response at the state level. However, the Guard can also be federalized and operate under Title 10 authorities under the command of the president during times of war or national emergency. In the current model, there are various state National Guard units across the existing services that can be mobilized to respond to cyber incidents, especially cyber incidents targeting critical infrastructure. However, there is no unified approach, and various guard units organize, train, and equip differently. Creating a Cyber Force would cohere these disparate guard units under one service umbrella and would align organizing, training, and equipping across all of the service's components. Most importantly, given the unique nature of its authorities, a Cyber Guard would be an essential element of critical infrastructure defense at both the state and the national levels. (Lonergan & Montgomery, 2025b)

2.4 Legislative Action

2.4.1 Statements in National Defense Authorization Act

2.4.1.1 FY17 NDAA

The most notable early legislative effort is Section 1651 of the National Defense Authorization Act for Fiscal Year 2017 (Public Law 114-328) (U.S. Congress, 2016);

SEC. 1651. STRATEGY TO INCORPORATE ARMY RESERVE COMPONENT CYBER PROTECTION TEAMS INTO DEPARTMENT OF DEFENSE CYBER MISSION FORCE.

(a) STRATEGY REQUIRED.—Not later than 180 days after the date of the enactment of this Act, the Secretary of the Army shall provide to the Committees on Armed Services of the Senate and the House of Representatives a briefing on a strategy for incorporating reserve component cyber protection teams into the cyber mission force of the Department of Defense.

(b) ELEMENTS OF STRATEGY.—The strategy required by subsection

(a) shall include, at minimum, the following:

(1) A timeline for incorporating reserve component cyber protection teams into the cyber mission force of the Department of Defense, including a timeline for the appropriate training of such teams.

(2) Identification of the specific reserve component cyber protection teams to be incorporated into the cyber mission force of the Department of Defense.

(3) An assessment of how the incorporation of reserve component cyber protection teams into the cyber mission force of the Department of Defense might be used to enhance readiness through improved individual and collective training capabilities.

(4) A status report on the progress of the Army in issuing additional guidance that clarifies how reserve component cyber protection teams of the Army National Guard can support State and civil operations in National Guard status under title 32, United States Code.

(5) Other matters as considered appropriate by the Secretary of the Army.

(c) RESERVE COMPONENT CYBER PROTECTION TEAMS DEFINED.—In this section, the term “reserve component cyber protection teams” means cyber protection teams of—

(1) the Army National Guard; and

(2) the other reserve components of the Army.

2.4.1.2 FY24 NDAA

In the House Armed Services Committee Subcommittee on Cyber, Information Technologies, and Innovation (CITI) mark for the FY24 National Defense Authorization Act, the below statement is included: (CITI, 2023; Pomerleau, 2023)

Utilization of National Guard and Reserve Forces in Cyberspace Operations

Over the last 10 years, Congress has expressed its position that the Department of Defense can bolster its operational capacity in cyberspace through improved utilization of the National Guard. This has resulted in 10 legislative provisions over a decade's worth of National Defense Authorization Acts and is most pertinently expressed through sections 1729 and 1730 of the William M. (Mac) Thornberry National Defense Authorization Act for Fiscal Year 2021 (Public Law 116-283). Despite these calls for change, the Department of Defense and the military services appear not to have made any meaningful change in how the expertise resident within the National Guard and the Reserve Component can be better leveraged.

Therefore, the committee directs the Assistant Secretary of Defense for Cyber Policy, in coordination with the Commander, U.S. Cyber Command, to submit a report to the Senate Committee on Armed Services and the House Committee on Armed Services not later than May 31, 2024, on the specific actions and institutional obstacles that have prevented change from being instantiated after the requirements directed in the following legislative provisions:

- (1) section 1651 of the National Defense Authorization Act for Fiscal Year 2017 (Public Law 114-328);
- (2) section 1653 of the John S. McCain National Defense Authorization Act for Fiscal Year 2019 (Public Law 115-232); and
- (3) section 1729 and 1730 of the William M. (Mac) Thornberry National Defense Authorization Act for Fiscal Year 2021 (Public Law 116-283).

2.4.1.3 FY26 NDAA

2.4.1.3.1 Senate Version In the Senate version of the National Defense Authorization Act for Fiscal Year 2026, section 1605 is titled, "Report on Reserve Component Integration Into Cyber Mission Force and Cyberspace Operations." (SASC, 2025) If it would have been integrated into the final FY26 NDAA, it directed, by August 1, 2026, a report and briefing to Congress which include the following:

- (1) An assessment of the different authorities available within each status of the reserve components, with particular focus on the National Guard and authorities under title 32, United States Code, and how the Department of Defense can use personnel of the reserve components in such statuses within the cyber mission force and in support of cyberspace operations.
- (2) An analysis of current and planned efforts to work with the military departments, the National Guard, and the adjutants general of each State to develop

unique cyber capabilities that address identified operational requirements and that maximize use of local industry expertise and academic partnerships.

(3) A description of methods to work with the military departments, the National Guard Bureau, and the adjutants general of each State to track and identify key skills and competencies that are not part of primary military occupational specialties of members of the military departments, but are developed through their civilian career experience.

(4) An identification of the billets, resources, and support infrastructure needed to maximize the unique expertise, capabilities, and authorities of the reserve components in support of the cyber mission of the Department.

(5) An evaluation of what types of authorities would be most beneficial to maximize the activation and support of the reserve components to cyberspace operations, including any legislative action that may be required.

(6) An evaluation of the existing barriers to or impediments for integration of the reserve components into the cyber mission force in support of cyberspace operations and an assessment of mitigation initiatives with respect to paragraphs (1) through (5).

This demonstrates a recognition among members of Congress of the importance and ongoing need to address the continuing challenges with the integration and utilization of Reserve Component cyber forces, “with particular focus on the National Guard and authorities under title 32, and how the Department of Defense can use personnel [...] in such statuses within the cyber mission force and in support of cyberspace operations.” (SASC, 2025)

2.4.1.3.2 Final Version The final enacted version of the FY26 National Defense Authorization Act (Public Law 119-60) (U.S. Congress, 2025) adopted a narrower provision than that originally proposed by the Senate Armed Services Committee. As enacted, Section 1544 directs the Secretary of Defense to conduct a study examining the integration of Reserve Component personnel into the Cyber Mission Force and cyberspace operations, without specific consideration given to National Guard authorities under Title 32, United States Code. The statute retains a requirement for a written report to the congressional defense committees but does not mandate the development of an implementation plan, prescribe changes to force structure, nor require interim or final congressional briefings.

Compared to earlier legislative language addressing Reserve Component cyber integration, Section 1544 reflects a continuation of Congress's reliance on reporting and assessment mechanisms rather than prescriptive direction. The provision emphasizes evaluation of authorities, identification of barriers, and analysis of potential benefits, while deferring decisions regarding execution, organizational change, or legislative reform. As such, Section 1544 occupies a position consistent with prior NDAA provisions that have sought to further examine, rather than resolve, questions surrounding the operational employment of National Guard cyber forces, or have resulted in inaction from the services or Department of Defense.

2.4.2 Summary

As of this writing, none of these legislative directives, to include the clear directive to include Army National Guard (ARNG) Cyber Protection Teams (CPTs) as forces presented via the Cyber Mission Force (CMF), have resulted in substantive action.

2.5 Gaps in the Literature

Despite ongoing research on cybersecurity policy and military cyber operations, several gaps remain in the literature:

- **Limited empirical studies on Title 32 cyber force integration:** Few studies comprehensively examine how National Guard cyber forces have been engaged in federal cyber missions under Title 32.
- **Insufficient legal analysis of Title 32 cyber missions:** The interplay between federal and state authorities in cyber operations remains poorly defined in legal scholarship.
- **Lack of operational case studies:** While National Guard cyber units have been

activated for various missions, there is minimal published research on their effectiveness, challenges, and outcomes in federal cyber missions.

2.6 Summary

Chapter 2 examined the existing body of scholarship and policy literature related to the employment of National Guard cyber forces under Title 32 status. Because research in this domain remains relatively sparse—and is often found in military theses, white papers, and congressional directives rather than traditional peer-reviewed outlets—the chapter drew heavily from doctrinal publications, service school analyses, proposed legislative solutions, and strategic assessments.

The literature demonstrates a long-standing recognition of the Guard's cyber potential, yet also reveals recurring uncertainty about how Title 32 authorities may be used for national cyber missions. Several proposals over the past fifteen years advocate models ranging from a Cyber National Guard to federated support structures, but few offer empirically tested solutions. The Federated Intelligence Program (FIP) emerged as an important precedent illustrating how Title 32 personnel may support federal missions when activities are aligned with training requirements.

The review identified multiple gaps, including the lack of empirical case studies, limited legal analysis of Title 32 cyber applicability, and minimal documentation of prior Title 32 operational support to national missions. These gaps directly motivate the present study's research design, which seeks to integrate documentary evidence with expert assessments and operational data to clarify existing pathways for employing National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status.

Despite senior leaders repeatedly stating that National Guard cyber forces are essential to national cyber defense, they are not systematically integrated into national cyber missions under Title 32. Legal, policy, and bureaucratic ambiguities and Army and Air

Force service cultures prevent full utilization, even though existing policy and precedent suggests viable pathways for involvement. This study addresses the gaps by combining documentary analysis and expert surveys to provide a clearer understanding of National Guard cyber operations in support of national missions while in Title 32 status.

Chapter 3

Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study employs a multi-method qualitative research design with embedded descriptive quantitative analysis, combining documentary analysis, a structured expert survey, and an embedded case study to explore the utilization of National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status for national cyber missions. This approach ensures a comprehensive examination of existing legal frameworks, policy precedents, and operational applications while incorporating expert insights from military and cyber professionals. (Figure 3.1)

A multi-method qualitative approach is appropriate because it allows for the triangulation of different qualitative data sources (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017; Mik-Meyer, 2020; Roller & Lavrakas, 2015). Documentary analysis establishes the legal, policy, and operational framework, while surveys provide firsthand experiences and perspectives on implementation challenges and feasibility. This approach enhances the study's analytic rigor and credibility by integrating multiple forms of qualitative data (Bowen, 2009).

As discussed in the introduction, this is a critical area of study because of the importance of cyber operations for national strategic priorities, and for the recruitment and retention of cyber expertise across the National Guard. Because of the research gap, it is important to determine what viable existing pathways may exist for utilizing the force without requiring changes to the law.

This approach allows for an assessment of existing law and policy, while eliciting expert perspectives on military cyber and policy matters to document perceived feasibility, constraints, and existing precedent that may inform future utilization. The research questions, the applicability of this approach to these questions, challenges with this study, the sources of information reviewed, and the population surveyed are the primary components of this chapter.

Consistent with the study's qualitative design, any numeric survey outputs are treated as descriptive summaries used to organize expert perspectives and support qualitative interpretation, rather than as independent inferential evidence.

Figure 3.1: Adapted Research Methodology Framework for Title 32 cyber policy study. This diagram illustrates the structured research approach used in this study, adapted from the Design Science Research Methodology (DSRM) (Peffer et al., 2007). The process integrates documentary analysis and surveys in an iterative framework to analyze existing policies, evaluate feasibility, and refine policy recommendations for National Guard cyber operations under Title 32.

3.1.1 Theoretical Application in Research Design

The theoretical foundations discussed in Chapter 1 provide the analytical framework for this study's methodology. The application of these theories ensures that the study's approach is structured to systematically evaluate the legal, policy, and operational chal-

lenges associated with the use of National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status.

1. **Organizational Configurations** (Mintzberg, 1983, 1984) guides the analysis of organizational constraints and hierarchical decision-making in National Guard cyber operations. It helps assess how bureaucratic structures influence the efficiency and authority of cyber forces under Title 32.
2. **Cybersecurity Governance** under the NIST Cybersecurity Framework (NIST, 2024) provides a lens for evaluating policy misalignments and inconsistencies between state and federal cyber defense strategies. Governance principles help determine whether existing policies effectively support Title 32 cyber missions.
3. **Multi-Domain Operations (MDO)** (AFC, 2020) justifies the need for National Guard cyber forces to be fully integrated into broader national security efforts. This framework is used to analyze how cyber forces operating under Title 32 can support federal cyber missions while maintaining state-level responsibilities.

These theories inform both documentary analysis and survey data interpretation, ensuring a structured and methodologically sound approach to examining the complexities of Title 32 cyber force integration. In the data analysis phase, thematic coding incorporated these theoretical lenses to assess bureaucratic constraints, governance gaps, and strategic alignment in National Guard cyber operations.

In addition to documentary analysis and a structured expert survey, the study incorporates a focused operational case to illustrate how Title 32 cyber mission support has been implemented in practice. This embedded case is used to contextualize and exemplify findings derived from the primary data sources, rather than as an independent basis for theory generation or hypothesis testing.

3.1.2 Justification for Study Methodology

A **multi-method qualitative design with embedded descriptive quantitative analysis** is suitable for this research because it enables an in-depth investigation of a policy-driven and operationally complex issue (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017; Mik-Meyer, 2020; Roller & Lavrakas, 2015). Given the lack of extensive empirical research on National Guard cyber force utilization under Title 32, this approach provides a rich contextual analysis to inform future policy and military doctrine, and additional modes of operational application of National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status.

Documentary analysis allows for an objective review of statutes, policy documents, and operational reports (Bowen, 2009), while surveys of key stakeholders add a practical and experiential dimension to the findings (Fowler, 2013). By using both methods with the embedded use case, this study can:

- **Identify** existing legal and policy frameworks governing Title 32 cyber operations.
- **Assess** operational feasibility through expert insights.
- **Provide** a structured comparison between documented policy intent and real-world application.

3.1.3 Research Questions

This study seeks to establish the viability and efficacy of the utilization of Army National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status for national cyber missions by answering the following research questions:

1. What elements of current law and policy support or constrain the utilization of National Guard personnel in Title 32 status for national cyber missions?
2. What precedent, expert opinion, and policy analysis enable or challenge the use of National Guard personnel in Title 32 status for national cyber missions?

3.1.4 The Researcher

The researcher has worked in academic and government enterprise information technology and national security environments for over 30 years. The researcher holds a Bachelor of Arts in Intelligence Studies (Information Operations), a Master of Arts in Intelligence Studies (Information Warfare), a Master of Science in Cybersecurity Policy, and is a Certified Information Systems Security Professional (CISSP).

The researcher has experience relevant to both the military Reserve and Guard components, as well as military cyberspace operations. The researcher served for 8 years as a Cryptologic Warfare Officer in the United States Navy Reserve in the Navy Cryptologic Community, the Navy's proponent for cyber, and for 6 years as a Cyber Warfare Officer in the Wisconsin Army National Guard on the 176th Cyber Protection Team (CPT).

The researcher is an active practitioner in this domain, and has the appropriate skills and experience to carry out this study, serving in environments interacting with service and joint military, civilian, and contractor personnel in support of cyber operations in an active and reserve component (both Reserve and National Guard) context, in both Title 10 and Title 32, and both active reserve and active capacities.

3.2 Data Collection

Data collection consists of documentary analysis, a survey instrument, and an embedded use case ensuring triangulation and enhancing validity and reliability (Fowler, 2013; Patton, 2014).

3.2.1 Documentary Analysis

Documentary analysis is used to examine laws, policies, and official directives that impact the employment of National Guard cyber forces. Since no law *per se* explicitly

states that National Guard cyber forces can or cannot be used in Title 32 status for national cyber missions, this study assesses how Title 32 has been applied in similar contexts. This method allows for a systematic review of existing legal and operational frameworks (Bowen, 2009).

In this study, documentary analysis was used to collect data on the following topics:

- The current state of law and policy regarding the utilization of National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 Status for national cyber missions.
- Precedent, expert opinions and analysis, and experiences regarding the utilization of National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 Status for national cyber missions.

To collect data for the documentary analysis, the researcher searched for relevant unclassified, publicly released documents in a variety of sources, including:

- United States Code
- Government publications
- Academic journals
- News articles
- Military school theses and papers
- Published reports

The researcher placed a special focus on US Code and DoD policy to interpret the authorities landscape for this topic:

- Constitution of the United States
- United States Code (USC)
 - Title 10 USC — Armed Forces
 - Title 32 USC — National Guard

- Title 50 USC — War and National Defense
- DoD Policy, Directives, Instructions, and Memoranda
 - Department wide policy (DoD Instructions, Directives, and Memoranda)
 - Combatant Command (CCMD) or Combat Support Agency (CSA) policy
- Service policies and publications
- Service cyber element policies and publications
- National Guard Bureau (NGB) policies and publications
- Congressional Hearings and Think Tank Reports:
 - RAND, IDA, FDD, and CSIS reports on National Guard cyber integration.
 - Legislative discussions on cyber force utilization.
- Operational Reports and Doctrinal Documents:
 - After-action reviews (AARs) from National Guard cyber missions.
 - Operations Reports from the Wisconsin Federated Cyber Program (WIFCP).

The researcher analyzed the documents to identify information that clarifies the legal and policy framework, including provisions that explicitly authorize, restrict, or omit guidance on such operations, governing the utilization of National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status for national cyber missions. With the exceptions of the Constitution and U.S. Code, document searches were scoped to publication since the year 2000.

3.2.1.1 Operational Reports

Operational reports provide empirical data on actual mission activities, effectiveness, and outcomes. These reports include:

- **Mission Logs:** Documentation of tasks performed by Guard personnel.
- **Training Records:** Proof of how personnel met training requirements.
- **Performance Metrics:** Data on response times, operational impact, and mission support outcomes.

These reports provide quantifiable evidence of real-world application and effectiveness in fulfilling national mission needs.

3.2.2 Survey Research

A structured survey was distributed to a broader pool of cyber professionals, including military personnel, policymakers, and cybersecurity experts. The survey includes:

- **Likert-scale questions** to assess perceptions of Title 32 cyber force utilization.
- **Multiple-choice and ranking questions** to evaluate legal and operational challenges.
- **Open-ended questions** to capture qualitative perspectives.

Survey results provide insights to help identify broader trends.

3.2.2.1 Survey Development

To ensure that survey questions effectively capture key insights on the use of National Guard cyber forces under Title 32, this study follows a structured development and validation process. The survey questions are designed to:

- Align with the research questions to elicit relevant data.
- Include some open-ended questions to encourage responses from participants.
- Avoid leading or biased wording to ensure neutrality.
- Be accessible and understandable to participants with different backgrounds (e.g., policymakers, military personnel, cybersecurity professionals).
- Include limited quantitative elements (e.g., Likert-scale items) used to support descriptive summarization of expert perspectives and qualitative interpretation.

3.2.2.1.1 Pre-Testing and Validation Process To enhance the clarity and effectiveness of the survey questions, the study conducted two rounds of pre-testing before official data collection:

1. First Pre-Test (Expert Review)

- A small group of subject-matter experts (e.g., military policy analysts, cybersecurity researchers) reviewed the draft survey questions.
- Feedback focused on question clarity, relevance, and potential biases.
- Questions were refined based on expert input to improve their precision and applicability.

2. Second Pre-Test (Pilot Surveys)

- A small number of non-study participants (e.g., former Guard cyber personnel or academic cybersecurity experts) took the survey.
- These test surveys were analyzed to identify unclear or redundant questions, ensuring the final set was both effective and efficient.
- Final adjustments focused largely on question clarity were made based on pilot feedback before the formal survey began.

By conducting these two rounds of pre-testing, this study ensures that survey questions are well-developed, methodologically sound, and capable of eliciting meaningful data while minimizing misunderstandings or biases.

3.2.3 Embedded Case Data

The study also includes a focused operational case drawn from the Wisconsin Federated Cyber Program (WIFCP). Case data consist of program artifacts, activity summaries, status-type documentation, and output counts generated during a defined period in which

Wisconsin Army National Guard personnel supported a national cyber mission while in Title 32 training status. These materials are used descriptively to demonstrate how training-aligned mission support may occur under existing law and policy.

3.3 Validity and Reliability

Ensuring validity and reliability is critical to maintaining academic rigor in this study (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017). The following measures are implemented:

3.3.1 Construct Validity

- **Triangulation of data sources:** Combining documentary analysis and survey responses enhances credibility (Patton, 2014).
- **Chain of evidence:** Clear documentation of data sources and coding procedures (Bowen, 2009).
- **Sample size:** For qualitative policy studies using expert surveys, sample adequacy is assessed based on respondent expertise and thematic saturation rather than statistical power. (Creswell & Poth, 2018; Guest et al., 2006).
- **Peer debriefing:** Policy experts and military professionals review findings for accuracy (Janesick, 2015).

3.3.2 Internal Validity

- **Pattern matching:** Comparing findings from documents and surveys to assess alignment (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017).
- **Thematic analysis:** Coding qualitative data to identify recurring themes (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

3.3.3 External Validity

- **Comparative analysis:** Evaluating parallels between National Guard cyber, intelligence, or other operations while in Title 32.
- **Policy implications:** Providing a framework for broader National Guard cyber force integration in other states when appropriate.

3.3.4 Reliability

- **Standardized data collection protocols:** Ensuring consistency across surveys (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017).
- **Qualitative rigor strategies:** Multiple techniques ensure trustworthiness of thematic analysis:
 - *Methodological triangulation:* Convergent findings across documentary analysis, survey data, and operational case evidence strengthen credibility (Denzin, 2017; Patton, 2014).
 - *Systematic coding procedures:* Development of a structured codebook with explicit code definitions and decision rules documented in Appendix B (Braun & Clarke, 2006).
 - *Audit trail:* Documentation of major coding decisions and iterative theme refinement maintains transparency (Lincoln & Guba, 1990).
 - *Reflexivity:* Explicit acknowledgment of researcher positionality as both analyst and active-duty practitioner, treating insider knowledge as an interpretive asset rather than bias to be controlled (Braun & Clarke, 2019).
 - *Expert validation:* Review of emergent themes by subject matter experts in cyber defense policy and National Guard operations to ensure alignment with operational and policy realities (Janesick, 2015).

3.4 Ethical Considerations

This study adheres to ethical research principles and follows Institutional Review Board (IRB) guidelines to ensure:

- **Informed consent:** Participants receive clear explanations of study objectives, confidentiality, and voluntary participation requirements.
- **Data confidentiality:** Sensitive military and cybersecurity information is protected in accordance with DoD and other applicable regulations.
- **Minimization of risk:** Participants are assured anonymity when discussing operational or policy-sensitive topics.

3.4.1 Protection of Participant Confidentiality

Ensuring the confidentiality of participants is a fundamental ethical priority in this study. Given the potential sensitivity of discussions related to National Guard cyber operations and federal cyber missions, the following measures were implemented to protect participant identities and responses:

- **Anonymization of Data:** Reported data is anonymized. Unless a participant chooses to contact the Principal Investigator or the institution, no personal information about participants will be known or collected; in the event participants choose to contact the Principal Investigator and/or institution, no personal information is reported. No survey participants were known to have contacted the Principal Investigator and/or institution during this study.
- **No Personal Information:** No personally identifiable information (PII) was collected, published, or shared. Only the principal investigator and approved committee members have access to raw data, which is anonymized. No personally identi-

fiable information (PII) was solicited during this survey. Where PII was suspected (e.g., names mentioned in survey responses), those instances were redacted.

- **Secure Data Storage:** Survey data is stored on secure systems and retained only as necessary for research purposes.
- **Controlled Access to Data:** Raw survey data is not shared outside the research team. Only anonymized, summarized data is used in this publication and the survey data explorer.
- **Non-Attribution Policy:** Findings are reported without attributing statements to specific individuals even if able to be known or deduced via other means, ensuring that participants felt free to share insights without concern for professional or institutional repercussions.

By implementing these measures, the study upholds ethical standards in qualitative research and ensures that participants can contribute candid insights while maintaining their privacy and confidentiality.

The survey instrument was determined by the Dakota State University IRB to be Exempt under 45 CFR §46.104(d)(2). This exemption covers survey-based research where no identifiable information is collected and where participation poses minimal risk. DSU IRB approval was granted on June 3, 2025, and assigned record DSUIRB-20250603-07EX.

3.5 Limitations

While this study employs a rigorous research design, the following limitations should be considered:

- **Limited generalizability:** Findings may not fully represent all National Guard cyber units. Because the case study reflects a single state-level implementation, it

is presented as illustrative rather than representative, and findings derived from the case are not treated as generalizable beyond the study context.

- **Restricted access to classified or controlled data:** Some policy details and operational reports are not publicly available.
- **Participant bias:** Participants may have organizational loyalties or biases affecting their responses.
- **Evolving policy landscape:** Future legislative, policy, or force structure changes could impact findings.

3.5.1 Controlled or Classified Information

While the US Code and many government documents relevant to this study are publicly available, that represents only a small component of the complete authorities and policy framework which supports military cyberspace operations in practice. While much of the policy is unclassified, certain documents may have not been released publicly, or exist only at the Controlled Unclassified Information (CUI)/For Official Use Only (FOUO) level.

Additionally, some operational details relevant to precedent may be controlled or classified national security information. This complicates full discussion or awareness of all the existing precedent that may exist in this area.

The study is intended to be read entirely at the UNCLASSIFIED level. Findings and recommendations are presented at the UNCLASSIFIED level in order to reach the widest audience. Survey participants were advised that questions and responses shall be confined to the UNCLASSIFIED level.

3.6 Research System Design

Figure 3.2: Research System Design

3.7 Implementation

3.7.1 Phase 1: Documentary Analysis

The initial phase of the research consisted of a comprehensive documentary analysis to identify and clarify existing legal and policy frameworks. Documents including the United States Constitution, relevant sections of the U.S. Code (Title 10, Title 32, Title 50), Department of Defense policies, and publications from DoD agencies will be systematically reviewed. The findings were categorized to identify enabling and constraining factors affecting the utilization of National Guard cyber forces operating under Title 32 status.

3.7.2 Phase 2: Surveys

In this phase, data were collected via a survey instrument conducted with 151 participants. The target audience included subject matter experts from military, civilian cybersecurity, academia, and policy analysis sectors. The survey was structured around predefined and open-ended questions designed to capture expert opinions, operational precedents, policy interpretation challenges, and practical implications. A thematic analysis was performed to identify recurring themes, consensus, and areas of divergence.

3.7.3 Phase 3: Validation and Integration

The final phase integrated and validated the results from phases one and two. Cross-validation techniques ensured the alignment of survey insights with the documentary analysis findings. Synthesizing these inputs resulted in comprehensive, actionable policy recommendations. Future workshops with stakeholders, including policymakers, National Guard leadership, and cybersecurity practitioners, will validate the practicality and applicability of recommendations.

3.8 Methods for Validation

3.8.1 Documentary Cross-validation

To ensure robustness, documentary findings were cross-referenced with insights gained from surveys to validate consistency in the interpretation and application of Title 32 authorities.

3.8.2 Expert Validation

Validation also included feedback from subject matter experts and key stakeholders to confirm the practical applicability and relevance of the gathered documentary and survey data.

3.8.3 Policy and Operational Feasibility Workshops

In the future, workshops with stakeholders can simulate realistic implementation scenarios, testing proposed recommendations against practical and bureaucratic constraints to refine and finalize solutions.

3.8.4 Expected Results and Contributions

The anticipated contributions of this research include:

- **Enhanced Legal and Policy Clarity:** This research delivers a clear understanding of the legal and policy environment governing the use of National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status.
- **Operational Guidelines and Best Practices:** Practical guidelines for integrating National Guard cyber forces into national cybersecurity initiatives are provided, facilitating operational effectiveness.

- **Policy Recommendations:** Evidence-based policy recommendations address identified legal, bureaucratic, and operational gaps, enhancing efficiency and clarity in cyber operations.
- **Academic and Operational Contributions:** Empirical insights from this research significantly contribute to both academic literature and practical military cyber defense strategies.

3.9 Metrics and Evaluation of Effectiveness

3.9.1 Future Metrics

Key metrics to be used in evaluating the effectiveness of the proposed recommendations in the future could include:

- **Policy Clarity Index:** This qualitative metric will measure the improved clarity and interpretability of policies related to cyber operations in Title 32 status.
- **Operational Readiness Level:** Evaluations will assess the readiness and operational capabilities of National Guard cyber forces in conducting defensive cyberspace operations.
- **Expert Consensus Measure:** This metric will capture the degree of expert consensus regarding the feasibility and desirability of the integration approaches proposed.

3.9.2 Future Effectiveness Evaluation

The effectiveness of the approach could be evaluated through several methods:

- **Pre-Post Policy Analysis:** Operational outcomes, retention rates, and readiness levels could be compared before and after policy implementation to measure effectiveness.
- **Stakeholder Feedback Surveys:** Surveys could capture perceptions from National Guard cyber leaders and personnel regarding the improvements in operational clarity, efficiency, and effectiveness.
- **Scenario-based Exercises:** Exercises could empirically test the operational effectiveness of the proposed frameworks, analyzing individual and team performance outcomes in simulated cyber scenarios.

3.10 Summary

Chapter 3 detailed the multi-method qualitative research design used to examine the feasibility of employing National Guard cyber forces under Title 32 status for national cyber missions. The chapter explained the rationale for integrating three components — documentary analysis, expert survey data, and a focused operational case study — to triangulate findings across legal, policy, doctrinal, and practitioner domains.

Documentary analysis served to identify enabling, constraining, and ambiguous language across federal statutes, DoD and NGB policy, joint doctrine, and congressional provisions. The survey methodology captured expert insights from practitioners across military, civilian, and academic cyber roles, employing both structured scales and open-ended responses. The case study component examined an operational pilot program to provide empirical evidence of Title 32 cyber mission support aligned with training requirements.

The chapter also addressed validity, reliability, sampling considerations, ethical requirements — including DSU IRB exempt approval — and limitations related to controlled or classified information and evolving policy environments. Together, these methodologi-

cal elements provide a rigorous and defensible structure for evaluating the research questions presented in Chapter 1 and support the results reported in Chapter 4.

The methodology ensures a rigorous, multi-faceted investigation into the feasibility of National Guard cyber force utilization under Title 32. By integrating documentary analysis and surveys in a multi-method qualitative approach, the study contributes to both academic cybersecurity research and military policy development in this domain.

The evaluation strategy assesses the dissertation's central proposition, demonstrating that National Guard Cyber Forces in Title 32 status are capable of effectively supporting specified national cybersecurity missions, and identify mechanisms under current law and policy, thereby enhancing national security.

Chapter 4

Results

4.1 Overview of Sources and Data

This chapter reports empirical results from three sources:

1. **Documentary corpus** – statutes, directives, instructions, doctrine, and public posture statements relevant to using National Guard forces in Title 32 status for national missions, with particular attention to intelligence (e.g., Federated Intelligence Program (FIP)) and cyber operations. Documents were coded as enabling, constraining, or conditional/ambiguous with respect to Title 32 support to national missions.
2. **Title 32 Cyber Survey** – a Qualtrics survey fielded from June 4, 2025, through October 4, 2025, to practitioners across the Guard, Active Component, civilian government, academia, and industry. The dataset contains $N = 151$ responses ($N_{\text{complete}} = 60$ responses); item-level N s vary due to skip logic and nonresponse. (The complete instrument and connection to the dissertation design appear in Appendix A and other chapters.)
3. **Embedded use case** – operational artifact counts collected from the Wisconsin Federated Cyber Program (WIFCP) pilot that supported a national cyber mission while participants were in Title 32 status.

Please note this chapter reports findings only; interpretation is deferred to Chapter 5.

4.2 Documentary Analysis Results

This section presents the results of the documentary analysis that examined statutes, Department of Defense (DoD) directives and instructions, National Guard Bureau (NGB) policy, and relevant doctrinal publications governing the employment of National Guard cyber forces. A corpus of fifty-one primary and secondary documents was reviewed, encompassing Title 10, 32, and 50 of the U.S. Code; key DoD and NGB issuances; Joint and Service publications; and congressional materials from FY 2017 through FY 2026. Each document was coded manually in a structured matrix for explicit, implicit, and inferred references to the utilization of National Guard personnel in Title 32 status for national or federal missions. References were categorized as **enabling**, **constraining**, or **conditional/ambiguous**, and were further cross-referenced by document type (**statutory**, **policy**, **doctrinal**, **precedent**). This approach enables a transparent, evidence-based interpretation of the existing legal and policy environment surrounding Title 32 cyber operations.

4.2.1 Constitution

- **U.S. Constitution, Article I, Section 8, Clause 16** – “To provide for organizing, arming, and disciplining, the Militia, and for governing such Part of them as may be employed in the Service of the United States, reserving to the States respectively, the Appointment of the Officers, and the Authority of training the Militia according to the discipline prescribed by Congress;” — this clause — in particular, “to the discipline prescribed by Congress” — is the basis for training the National Guard to the same standard as federal military forces (“U.S. Constitution”, n.d.)
Coding: **Enabling; Statutory**.

4.2.2 Statutes

- **32 USC §502(a) (Required drills and field exercises)** – This is the primary mechanism for ordering Guard members to routine Inactive Duty Training (e.g. drill weekends) and Annual Training (AT) — “one weekend a month, two weeks a year”. Documentary evidence indicates §502(a) may be used for both Active Component (AC) missions and DoD Operational Support (OS), incident to training. Coding: **Enabling; Statutory.**
- **32 USC §502(f) (Operational Support)** – The documentary record shows §502(f) as the primary Title 32 mechanism for ordering Guard members to duty beyond routine Inactive Duty Training/Annual Training for Operational Support (OS). It is widely used for training and for certain federally funded, state-controlled duties. This statute underpins Full-Time National Guard Duty (FTNGD) variations frequently used as the platform for reimbursable support (e.g., DSCA or other federal requests). Coding: **Enabling; Statutory.**

 - **Analytic note on scope** – Secondary legal analysis emphasizes that §502(f) is not an unlimited, generic authority (e.g., guardrails on “other duty” (Nunn, 2024)). Coding consequence: **statutory enablement with limits.**
- **32 USC §§901–908 (Homeland Defense Activities, HDA)** – These sections define “homeland defense activity” and authorize federally funded, governor-controlled Guard employment for homeland defense if designated by the Secretary of Defense. The definition is broad, but documentary evidence indicates that designations are exceptional events, making HDA a conditional pathway rather than a routine mechanism. Coding: **Conditional/Ambiguous; Statutory.**

4.2.3 DoD and NGB Policy

- **DoDI 1215.06 (Uniform Reserve, Training, and Retirement Categories)** (USD P&R, 2022) — Establishes Reserve Component duty categories and clarifies use of training and other duty statuses (incorporating Change 2, 12 Jul 2022). It provides the management scaffolding for employing Title 32 duty for training and certain operational support (e.g., ADOS/FTNGD), though it does not itself assign mission tasks. Coding: **Enabling (structural); Policy**.
- **DoDD 3025.18 (Defense Support of Civil Authorities (DSCA))** (USD Policy, 2018) and **DoDI 3025.22 (Use of the National Guard for DSCA)** (USD Policy, 2017) — These issuances document pathways for reimbursable use of Guard forces, including in Title 32 status, when the Secretary of Defense approves and governors concur. They also prescribe reimbursement and coordination criteria; DTM-17-007 (as updated/superseded) governs Defense Support to Cyber Incident Response (DSCIR) requests. Coding: **Enabling (reimbursable federal support), procedurally bounded; Policy**.
- **CNGBI 2000.01D (Conduct and Oversight of National Guard Intelligence Activities)** — Establishes that National Guard intelligence personnel in Title 32 must comply with DoD intelligence oversight rules, even though they are not technically part of the IC. This creates clear compliance guardrails for intelligence-related activities in Title 32. Coding: **Enabling (with compliance constraints); Policy**.
- **2024 Domestic Operational Law Handbook for Legal Personnel** (Beaver, 2024) — Establishes that “the National Guard can train for the Federal mission in a Title 32 but is limited to DCO-IDM and DoDIN operations activities (Cyberspace Defense and Cyberspace Security). Title 32 training authorities can be leveraged

to provide support to (1) active component, (2) civil authorities; and (3) other statutorily eligible entities.” (Beaver, 2024) Specifically,

- “The National Guard can provide incidental operational support (OS) while conducting training. The key is that the primary purpose of the activity must be military training.” (Beaver, 2024)
- “DoDI 1215.06 [...] encourages maximum Reserve Component utilization [...]” (Beaver, 2024)
- “all training duty planned and performed by Reserve Component members shall capitalize on Reserve Component capabilities to accomplish operational requirements while maintaining their mission readiness for domestic and overseas operations. RC members may be employed to support active component mission requirements as part of conducting training duty.” (Beaver, 2024)
- “support to mission requirements, i.e., operational support (OS), may occur as a consequence of performing training.” (Beaver, 2024)
- the support to AC and/or OS missions may occur under the authority of Title 32 §502(a) (drills and annual training), or 502(f)(1) (additional training or other missions). (The President and Secretary of Defense have the authority to authorize operational missions under 502(f)(2).) (Beaver, 2024)

Significantly, the DOMOPS Manual notes that OS may also be applied to Cyberspace Exploitation and Cyberspace Attack activities under OCO and DCO-RA when (Beaver, 2024):

- the supported federal mission is consistent with the NG unit’s training requirements (e.g., NG CPT supporting AC CPT),
- the federal component can suitably perform its mission *without* the presence of NG operational support,

- NG personnel are not employed in a full-time status under Title 32 to support the federal mission in question.

Coding: **Enabling (training-first with incidental support); Policy.**

- **NGR 350-1 (Army National Guard Training)** (NGB, 2021) — Recognizes the Federated Intelligence Program (FIP) as a training strategy that may yield incidental operational support to national intelligence missions while in Title 32:

The ARNG G2 Federated Intelligence Program (FIP) is a training strategy that allows incidental operational support through training which increases readiness of MI soldiers and units. Utilizing Intelligence Readiness and Operations Capability (IROC), the FIP enables single source and multidiscipline reach, PED operations, and other augmentation to real-world intelligence analysis activities in support of organization's intelligence requirements. IROC enables Soldiers to remain engaged in global intelligence operations, ensuring MI forces are continuously prepared to perform their validated missions.

Coding: **Enabling (training-first with incidental support); Policy.**

4.2.4 Joint/Service Doctrine and Public Posture

- **Joint/Service doctrine** (e.g., JP 3-12, USAF DP 3-12) delineates cyberspace operations types and confirms common doctrinal categories (DCO-IDM; DCO-RA; OCO; DoDIN Ops). Doctrine itself is status-agnostic but frames which activities respondents later identified as feasible during Title 32 if aligned to training. Coding: **Neutral; Doctrinal.**
- **USCYBERCOM posture statements (2023–2025)** repeatedly note Reserve Component (Guard and Reserve) integration alongside Active Component formations and continued engagement with National Guard units; they also signal interest in expanding ways the RC contributes. Coding: **Enabling (policy intent signal).**

4.2.5 Precedent Items

- **Task Force Echo (2017–2024)** – Public record shows ARNG-led Task Force Echo rotations in support of USCYBERCOM through 2024 (Pomerleau, 2021; Stover, 2021); reporting indicates TFE concluded in August 2024 (Stover, 2024). Coding: Precedent for Guard contribution to national cyber missions (primarily on Title 10 mobilizations, but training for these operational missions occurred while in Title 32); historical context for RC utilization. Coding: **Enabling; Precedent including operational training while in Title 32.**
- **Federated Intelligence Program (FIP)** – Multiple official sources (NGR 350-1, Army MI training strategy, NGB/PA and state program pages) describe FIP as a Title 32 training strategy that enables reach-back intelligence production supporting national requirements. Coding: **Enabling; Precedent for intelligence personnel contributing to national missions while in Title 32 training, bounded by IO compliance.**
- **FY2017 NDAA §1651** – Directs the Army to provide a strategy to incorporate Reserve Component Cyber Protection Teams into the Cyber Mission Force. Documentary evidence establishes Congressional direction for RC integration into national cyber forces. Coding: **Enabling, Policy signal toward integration.**
- **FY2026 NDAA §1605** – Directs the Assistant Secretary of Defense for Cyber Policy and the Commander, U.S. Cyber Command, in coordination with the Chief of the National Guard Bureau and the principal cyber advisor (PCA) of each military department, the chief of each reserve component, and the Office of the Under Secretary of Defense for Personnel and Readiness, to submit a report to Congress by August 1, 2026, which includes the following:

 1. An assessment of the different authorities available within each sta-

tus of the reserve components, with particular focus on the National Guard and authorities under title 32, United States Code, and how the Department of Defense can use personnel of the reserve components in such statuses within the cyber mission force and in support of cyberspace operations.

2. An analysis of current and planned efforts to work with the military departments, the National Guard, and the adjutants general of each State to develop unique cyber capabilities that address identified operational requirements and that maximize use of local industry expertise and academic partnerships.
3. A description of methods to work with the military departments, the National Guard Bureau, and the adjutants general of each State to track and identify key skills and competencies that are not part of primary military occupational specialties of members of the military departments, but are developed through their civilian career experience.
4. An identification of the billets, resources, and support infrastructure needed to maximize the unique expertise, capabilities, and authorities of the reserve components in support of the cyber mission of the Department.
5. An evaluation of what types of authorities would be most beneficial to maximize the activation and support of the reserve components to cyberspace operations, including any legislative action that may be required.
6. An evaluation of the existing barriers to or impediments for integration of the reserve components into the cyber mission force in support of cyberspace operations and an assessment of mitigation initiatives

with respect to paragraphs (1) through (5).

Coding: **Enabling, policy signal toward integration; Policy.** Note: Section 1605 was *not* enacted in the final FY26 NDAA. See the discussion in Chapter 5.

4.2.5.1 Innovative Readiness Training: Cyber Support to Non-DoD Entities

While this dissertation focuses on the utilization of National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status for national cyber missions — primarily those supporting DoD cyber operations and DoDIN-aligned activities — it is important to acknowledge an existing statutory mechanism that explicitly authorizes military training activities that provide support to entities *outside* the Department of Defense. The Innovative Readiness Training (IRT) program, codified at 10 USC §2012 (“U.S. Code Title 10”, n.d.) and implemented through DoD Instruction 1100.24 (USD P&R, 2020), provides a framework for military units to conduct training while simultaneously providing services to eligible non-DoD organizations, including cybersecurity services to critical infrastructure owners and operators.

4.2.5.1.1 Statutory Authority: 10 USC §2012 Section 2012 of Title 10, United States Code, authorizes the Secretary of a military department to “authorize units or individual members of the armed forces . . . to provide support and services to non-Department of Defense organizations and activities” when “(1) such assistance is authorized by a provision of law (other than this section); or (2) the provision of such assistance is incidental to military training” (“U.S. Code Title 10”, n.d.). The statute establishes several key requirements that govern IRT activities:

1. **Training-First Requirement:** Assistance may only be provided if “the provision of such assistance will accomplish valid unit training requirements” for unit assistance, or “will involve tasks directly related to the specific military occupational specialty of the member” for individual assistance (10 USC §2012(d)(1)(A)).

2. **No Adverse Training Impact:** The assistance “will not adversely affect the quality of training or otherwise interfere with the ability of a member or unit of the armed forces to perform the military functions of the member or unit” (10 U.S.C. § 2012(d)(1)(B)).
3. **Cost Limitations:** The assistance “will not result in a significant increase in the cost of the training” (10 USC §2012(d)(1)(C)).
4. **Eligible Entities:** The statute specifies eligible recipients including federal, regional, state, and local governmental entities; youth and charitable organizations; and — notably for cyber operations — “owners and operators of critical infrastructure” as defined in 42 USC §5195c(e) (10 USC §2012(e)(3)).

4.2.5.1.2 FY2022 NDAA Amendment: Critical Infrastructure Cyber Support The National Defense Authorization Act for Fiscal Year 2022 (U.S. Congress, 2021) significantly expanded the IRT program’s applicability to cybersecurity missions. This amendment added critical infrastructure owners and operators to the list of eligible entities under 10 USC §2012(e)(3) and required the Secretary of Defense to establish procedures “to ensure that assistance provided to an entity specified in subsection (e)(3) is provided in a manner that is consistent with similar assistance provided under authorities applicable to other Federal departments and agencies, including the authorities of the Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency of the Department of Homeland Security pursuant to title XXII of the Homeland Security Act of 2002” (10 USC §2012(f)(5)).

This amendment codified what had already emerged as practice: National Guard cyber units conducting vulnerability assessments, cybersecurity training, and security evaluations for state and local governments and critical infrastructure providers under the IRT framework.

4.2.5.1.3 DoD Instruction 1100.24 Implementation DoD Instruction 1100.24, issued May 5, 2020, establishes the implementing policy for IRT activities under 10 USC §2012 (USD P&R, 2020). The instruction emphasizes that IRT activities must be structured so that training is the “paramount consideration” while mission support may be “a key element in developing training programs” (DoDI 1100.24, Enclosure 3). The instruction identifies cybersecurity as one of the key service areas for IRT missions, alongside health care, construction, and transportation.

The IRT program operates through a governance structure including the IRT Executive Board (IRT-XB) and IRT Working Group (IRT-WG), with oversight from the Deputy Assistant Secretary of Defense for Reserve Integration (DASD(RI)). Military applications for IRT support are submitted through established channels, with OSD-level funding available for approved projects. The instruction also permits Military Department-funded IRT activities that do not require OSD funding, providing flexibility for state-level cyber missions (USD P&R, 2020).

4.2.5.1.4 Current Application: Cyber IRT Missions Multiple states have employed the IRT framework for cybersecurity training missions that simultaneously provide services to state and local government entities. The State of Idaho’s Office of Information Technology Services, in collaboration with the Idaho National Guard and Boise State University, operates an IRT cyber program providing vulnerability assessments, penetration testing, and incident response training to governmental partners (Idaho ITS, n.d.). Similar programs have emerged in other states, leveraging IRT authorities to address the critical shortage of cybersecurity expertise in smaller governmental entities while providing realistic training environments for National Guard cyber personnel.

Survey respondent R18 noted the relevance of IRT to cyber missions: “There have been multiple IRT missions that have been conducted that get after the DCI [Defense Critical Infrastructure] mission.” This observation reflects the growing recognition that

IRT provides a viable pathway for cyber training that produces meaningful community benefit. Survey respondent R26 noted the difficulty in getting approval for IRT: “It should be easier to get IRT approval to do Title 32 missions.” This observation reflects the fact that IRT approvals have a long timeline and thus are not appropriate for more agile activities and training.

4.2.5.1.5 Distinction from Dissertation Scope While IRT provides a valuable mechanism for National Guard cyber support to non-DoD entities, it is important to distinguish this authority from National Guard cyber support to DoD entities — the focus of this dissertation — for several reasons:

1. **Non-DoD Focus:** IRT is specifically designed for support to organizations *outside* the Department of Defense. The statute’s fundamental premise is assistance to “non-Department of Defense organizations and activities” (10 USC 2012(a)). In contrast, this dissertation examines the feasibility of Title 32 support to *national* cyber missions, particularly those aligned with DoD cyber operations, USCYBERCOM requirements, and DoDIN-related activities.
2. **Off-DoDIN Operations:** IRT cyber missions by definition in law and policy involve activities on networks outside the DoDIN — state and local government networks, critical infrastructure systems, and other non-DoD entities. The Institute for Defense Analyses (IDA) study (Ayers et al., 2022) specifically characterized these as “off-DoDIN” activities, distinguishing them from on-DoDIN operations that form the core of DoD cyber defense requirements.
3. **Training as Primary Purpose:** Under IRT, training must be the “paramount consideration,” with operational support being incidental to that training objective. The Wisconsin Federated Cyber Program (WIFCP) and similar initiatives examined in this dissertation take a similar approach — structuring activities so that

training requirements are met while also producing operationally relevant outputs that contribute to national mission requirements.

4. **Pre-Established Legal Framework:** IRT operates under explicit statutory authorization with detailed implementing guidance. The legal permissibility of IRT activities is thus established. In contrast, this dissertation addresses questions about the extent to which Title 32 authorities can support national cyber mission contributions outside of IRT, but consistent with existing law and policy.

4.2.6 Documentary Coding Summary

Table 4.1 shows an overview of documentary findings relative to Title 32 support to national cyber missions.

Overall, the documentary corpus is coded as enabling statutory and policy support for the use of National Guard personnel in Title 32 status to perform activities aligned with national cyber missions, provided those activities meet a defined training requirement. Approximately four-fifths of reviewed documents were coded as **enabling**, while the remainder were **conditional** due to executive-level approval prerequisites or ambiguous language concerning cyberspace operations. No documents were coded as strictly prohibitive.

The analysis indicates that 32 USC §502, DoDI 1215.06, DoDI 3300.05, and the 2024 Domestic Operational Law Handbook collectively establish a legal pathway in which training-aligned operational support under Title 32 can contribute to federal cyber missions. These findings suggest that existing law and policy already provide sufficient authority to integrate National Guard cyber forces into national missions when structured as *training-based* operational or mission support.

4.3 Survey Results

4.3.1 Introduction and Analytic Approach

This section reports the results of the Title 32 Cyber Survey administered via DSU's Qualtrics platform from 4 June 2025 through 4 October 2025 (4 months). The instrument was approved by the Dakota State University IRB and was deemed Exempt (DSUIRB-20250603-07EX) (see Approval Section ii) and included structured Likert items (5-point and 0-10 scales), categorical items (Yes/No/Unsure), multi-select items, and nine open-ended questions. Consistent with Chapter 3, the analysis uses: (1) descriptive statistics (means, medians, frequency distributions) with explicit item-level N ; (2) a short internal-consistency check over a composite index; (3) exploratory association tests to validate descriptive trends (not for causal inference); and (4) qualitative aggregation using anonymized text to surface themes. All data and outputs are verified to be unclassified; no PII was collected. Not all survey items are reported as standalone findings; demographic, screening, and contextual questions are used to characterize the respondent pool or support qualitative aggregation rather than to generate independent results. 151 respondents initiated the survey; 60 complete responses are used for analysis unless otherwise stated.

4.3.1.1 Data Quality and Missingness

Sixty (60) completed responses were retained (100% finished). Item-level sample sizes vary due to skip logic and item nonresponse, as noted with each result. For multi-select items stored as a single delimited cell in the export, options were parsed and tallied.

4.3.1.2 Survey Results Explorer

To facilitate transparent exploration and presentation of survey results, an interactive data visualization tool was developed to accompany this dissertation. The *Title 32 Cyber*

Figure 4.1: Title 32 Cyber Survey Results Explorer

Survey Results Explorer (Figure 4.1) (Schroeder, 2026) is a self-contained HTML-based dashboard that enabled dynamic analysis of all 24 survey questions across the 60 complete responses ($N_{complete} = 60$) collected during the study period.

The tool provides interactive visualizations including distribution charts for Likert-scale and categorical responses, histograms for 0–10 scale items, and a scatter plot with regression analysis examining the relationship between respondent confidence in existing Title 32 authorities (Q18) and perceived benefit of a structured national program (Q19). Demographic cross-tabulation filters allow users to segment responses by professional role (Q1), National Guard status (Q1.1), years of cyber experience (Q2), areas of expertise (Q3), grade (Q4), direct experience with National Guard cyber personnel (Q5), and familiarity with Titles 10, 32, and 50 authorities (Q6).

The Analysis section provides a correlation matrix for all numeric scale questions, de-

scriptive statistics, and group comparison capabilities with Welch's t-test for statistical significance. For qualitative responses, the tool includes theme-based filtering across five categories — Policy & Legal, Operations & Missions, Organizational & Cultural, Funding & Resources, and Support & Enablement — enabling readers to explore open-ended responses by thematic content. The explorer supports toggling between complete responses only ($N_{complete} = 60$) and all responses ($N = 151$) to examine potential response bias.

This tool is available as a supplementary digital artifact and online at <https://t32cyber.org> to support reproducibility and enable stakeholders to conduct independent analysis of the survey data.

4.3.2 Population and Respondent Profile

Table 4.3 summarizes respondent status (Q1.1), experience (Q2), and prior supervision of Guard cyber personnel (Q5). Sample sizes reflect non-missing responses per item.

Table 4.3: Population Summary (Respondent Profile)

Attribute	Count	%
<i>Status in the National Guard (Q1.1), N=43</i>		
Actively Drilling (M-Day/Traditional)	23	53.5
Retired	6	14.0
FTNGD/ADOS/AGR (Title 32)	3	7.0
Separated	3	7.0
Active Duty — Title 10	3	7.0
Active Duty — Title 32	2	4.7
Technician (Dual-Status)	2	4.7
State Active Duty (SAD)	1	2.3
<i>Years in Cyber Operations (Q2), N=60</i>		
No experience	2	3.3
< 5 years	11	18.3
5–10 years	15	25.0
11–15 years	12	20.0
16–20 years	7	11.7
> 20 years	13	21.7
<i>Worked with/supervised NG cyber personnel (Q5), N=60</i>		
Yes	52	86.7
No	8	13.3

Respondents thus represent a senior, experienced cohort: a majority report 10+ years in cyber operations, and 86.7% have directly worked with or supervised National Guard cyber personnel.

4.3.3 Findings Related to Research Question 1

RQ1: *What elements of current law and policy support or constrain the utilization of National Guard personnel in Title 32 status for national cyber missions?*

4.3.3.1 Law/Policy Enablers and Barriers (Q7.1, Q7.2, Q8).

Table 4.5 summarizes the central indicators. Full Likert distributions (1–5) are provided here for transparency.

Table 4.5: RQ1 — Law and Policy Indicators (with full distributions)

Item	<i>N</i>	Mean (1–5)	Agree/SA	Distribution (1–5)
Q7.1: law/policy enable support (general)	59	4.07	79.7%	1: 3.4% 2: 8.5% 3: 8.5% 4: 37.3% 5: 42.4%
Q7.2: law/policy enable support (cyber)	59	3.90	71.2%	1: 1.7% 2: 15.3% 3: 11.9% 4: 33.9% 5: 37.3%
Q8: legal/policy barriers exist	59	3.49	57.6%	1: 3.4% 2: 18.6% 3: 20.3% 4: 40.7% 5: 16.9%

Figure 4.2 provides the distribution visual for Q7.2. In sum, respondents largely agree that existing authorities can enable support (Q7.1, Q7.2), while also recognizing policy friction (Q8).

Figure 4.2: Distribution of agreement for Q7.2: “Current federal law and policy allow National Guard cyber personnel to support national missions while in Title 32 status.”

4.3.3.2 Precedent Awareness (Q9).

A majority reported awareness of precedent for Title 32 cyber support to national objectives (Q9 Yes: 54.2%, No: 45.8%; $N=59$).

4.3.4 Findings Related to Research Question 2

RQ2: *What precedent, expert opinion, and policy analysis enable or challenge the use of National Guard personnel in Title 32 status for national cyber missions?*

4.3.4.1 Training Alignment and Feasibility (Q11, Q13, Q18, Q19, Q20).

- **Q11** (Title 32 activities can meet training and contribute to national objectives): $N=59$, Mean = 4.25 (1–5); distribution: 1: 5.1%, 2: 5.1%, 3: 5.1%, 4: 28.8%, 5: 55.9% (84.7% Agree/Strongly Agree).
- **Q13** (federated support can scale effectively): $N=60$; Yes: 66.7%, No: 16.7%, Unsure: 16.7%.

- **Q18** (confidence 0–10 that some national missions can be supported without new law): $N=58$, Mean = 5.67, Median = 5.0, IQR = 4.0–8.0.
- **Q19** (benefit 0–10 of a structured national program): $N=58$, Mean = 7.90, Median = 8.5, IQR = 7.0–10.0.
- **Q20** (support explicit NDAA language codifying Title 32 national cyber missions): $N=60$; Yes: 70.0%, No: 3.3%, It depends: 16.7%, No changes to the law are required: 10.0%.

4.3.4.2 Doctrinal Activities Feasible in Title 32 (Q10, multi-select).

Respondents selected which doctrinal cyberspace activities (JP 3–12 categories) they judge feasible for national missions in Title 32 *if a training requirement is met*. The multi-select question was exported as a delimited string; parsing yields the counts in Table 4.7 (denominator $N_{answered}=58$).

Table 4.7: Q10 — Doctrinal Missions/Actions Feasible in Title 32 with Training ($N_{answered}=58$)

Option	Selected	% of Respondents
DCO-IDM — Cyberspace Defense	50	86.2
DoDIN Ops — Cyberspace Security	50	86.2
DoDIN Ops — Cyberspace System Operation	49	84.5
DCO-RA — Cyberspace Exploitation	33	56.9
DCO-RA — Cyberspace Attack	31	53.4
OCO — Cyberspace Exploitation	27	46.6
OCO — Cyberspace Attack	23	39.7

4.3.4.3 Funding and Governance (Q21–Q23).

Table 4.9 reports funding importance (Q21) and manager status importance (Q23). For Q22 (entities to manage/disseminate funding), the export combined options into a single string with punctuation inside choices.

Table 4.9: Funding Importance (Q21) and Manager Status Importance (Q23)

Item (0–10)	<i>N</i>	Mean	Median	IQR
Q21: funding for full-time orders (TOD/ADOS)	59	7.69	8.0	7.0–10.0
Q21: funding for ad hoc orders	59	7.64	8.0	6.0–10.0
Q21: funding for specialized training/visits	59	7.73	8.0	6.0–10.0
Q23: manager on <i>full-time orders</i>	58	7.12	8.0	5.0–10.0
Q23: manager in <i>Title 10 status</i>	57	5.30	5.0	3.0–7.0

Q22 yields the following: Customer (CCMD/CSA) 74.1%, National Guard Bureau (NGB) 56.9%, Service Cyber Component 51.7%, State/Territory or State Military Department 50.0%. ($N_{answered}=58$)

4.3.5 Composite Reliability and Exploratory Validation

A short composite *Title 32 Enabling Index* (Q7.1, Q7.2, Q11; 1–5) achieved Cronbach's $\alpha=0.724$, indicating acceptable internal consistency for a three-item attitude index. Figure 4.3 shows its distribution.

Figure 4.3: Composite Title 32 Enabling Index (average of Q7.1, Q7.2, Q11); Cronbach's $\alpha=0.724$.

Exploratory (descriptive) association tests were run to validate headline trends:

- **Confidence by awareness (Q18 × Q9):** mean confidence did not differ significantly between those aware vs. unaware of precedent ($t=0.46$, $p=0.65$).
- **Legislative support by awareness (Q20 × Q9):** no significant association ($\chi^2=3.09$, $p=0.54$).

These checks suggest that support for a clarified Title 32 program is broad-based across awareness subgroups.

4.3.6 Subgroup Checks

Table 4.11 presents three descriptive subgroup cuts aligned with the methodology. Given sample sizes and item missingness, these are not inferential claims; they serve to check the stability of the main results.

Table 4.11: Descriptive Subgroup Checks

Comparison	Observation
Q18 (confidence) by Q5 (worked/supervised NG)	Means: Yes = 5.73 ($N=51$); No = 5.29 ($N=7$). Pattern consistent with overall mean 5.67 (0–10).
Q7.2 (law/policy enablement for cyber) by experience (Q2)	Means by band: No experience 5.00 ($N=1$); <5 yrs 3.64 ($N=11$); 5–10 yrs 3.60 ($N=15$); 11–15 yrs 3.92 ($N=12$); 16–20 yrs 4.00 ($N=7$); >20 yrs 4.31 ($N=13$).
Q20 (support NDAA) by status (Q1.1)	Support for explicit NDAA language was high across all status categories ($N_{Q20}=60$). The “Yes” response ranged from 60–80% across status groups; “No changes to the law are required” responses were distributed across multiple status categories. Small cell sizes preclude detailed subgroup reporting.

4.3.7 Figures for Core Scales

For completeness, Figure 4.4 shows the Q18 confidence distribution (0–10), which is moderately centered, and Figure 4.2 is referenced above.

4.3.8 Limitations

Results reflect expert perceptions, not legal determinations. Likert items are summarized as interval for descriptive clarity; the composite index is short and reported with α . Multi-select items exported as delimited text (Q10, Q22) required parsing. Exploratory statistical checks are descriptive and do not imply causal effects.

Figure 4.4: Distribution of confidence (Q18): “How confident are you that Title 32 authorities can operationally support some national cyber missions without new legislation?”

4.3.9 Summary of Results

Respondents generally agree that existing law and policy permit meaningful use of National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status for national missions *when activities are structured as training* (Q7.1 Mean 4.07; Q7.2 Mean 3.90; Q11 Mean 4.25), yet also recognize practical policy/implementation frictions (Q8 Mean 3.49). Confidence that some national missions can be supported under current law is moderate (Q18 Mean 5.67), while perceived benefit of a structured national program is high (Q19 Mean 7.90). Regarding legislative clarification (Q20, $N=60$), 70.0% supported explicit NDAA language codifying Title 32 national cyber missions, while 10.0% indicated no changes to the law are required, and 16.7% responded “it depends.” Only 3.3% opposed legislative codification. Operationally, respondents most consistently endorsed DCO-IDM and DoDIN operations under a Title 32 training construct (each $\approx 86\%$ of Q10 respondents), with more mixed support for DCO-RA and OCO actions. Funding results (Q21–Q23) emphasize the importance of sustained resourcing for full-time and ad hoc orders and a preference that managers be on full-time orders (not necessarily in Title 10 status). Overall, the patterns indicate broad

perceived feasibility with targeted policy and governance refinements — a foundation for the recommendations in Chapter 5.

4.4 Thematic Coding and Qualitative Findings

In addition to the quantitative supporting results described in Section 4.3, the survey included nine open-ended items designed to elicit expert perspectives on policy, operational feasibility, cultural dynamics, and historical precedent related to the use of National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status for national cyber missions. These questions (Q8.1, Q9.1, Q12, Q13.1, Q14, Q15, Q16.1, Q17, Q20.1) generated a substantial corpus of qualitative data.

Consistent with qualitative best practice, all responses went through the coding process, using Braun and Clarke’s six-phase reflexive thematic analysis. Codes were generated inductively and then grouped into higher-order themes. A structured codebook was developed and is available in Appendix B, and discussed in Section 4.4.1.

Through this process, five major themes emerged, supported by twelve subthemes. These themes collectively describe the landscape of constraints, enablers, and operational realities practitioners perceive when considering Title 32 cyber mission support.

Figure 4.5: Thematic Map of Qualitative Findings

Table 4.13: Major Themes and Subthemes from Thematic Analysis

Theme	Subthemes
Legal and Policy Ambiguity	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Fear of misinterpretation 2. Lack of implementing guidance 3. Absence of standardized approval pathways
Precedent Exists but Poorly Recognized	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. DCO-IDM precedent 2. Training-task alignment 3. Informal, relationship-based support
Operational Feasibility and High Training Value	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Mission-training alignment 2. Improved readiness 3. Preference for remote operations
Cultural and Institutional Resistance	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Active Component bias 2. State-level risk aversion 3. Service parochialism
Demand for a Federated Cyber Program	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Mission manager construct 2. National-state linkages 3. Recurring, structured tasking model

4.4.1 Coding Frequency Analysis

To characterize the distribution of themes across the qualitative corpus, all 352 open-ended survey responses were reviewed against the codebook (Appendix B). Of these, 210 responses (59.7%) contained content substantively aligned with one or more of the five major themes. The remaining responses consisted of brief acknowledgments, single-word answers, or content outside the thematic scope of the codebook.

Table 4.14 presents the distribution of major themes across coded responses. Theme 5 (Demand for a Federated Cyber Program) appeared most frequently, present in 35.2% of coded responses, reflecting strong practitioner interest in formalized program structures for Title 32 cyber mission support. Theme 1 (Legal and Policy Ambiguity) appeared in 35.2% of coded responses, indicating widespread awareness of policy gaps despite enabling

legal authorities. Theme 2 (Precedent Exists but Poorly Recognized) appeared in 31.0% of coded responses, reflecting respondents' emphasis on training alignment as the mechanism enabling Title 32 cyber mission support. Theme 4 (Cultural and Institutional Resistance) appeared in 24.8% of coded responses, and Theme 3 (Operational Feasibility and High Training Value) in 11.0%.

At the subtheme level (Table 4.15), the most frequently applied code was Subtheme 1.2 (Lack of Implementing Guidance) at 31.4%, underscoring practitioner perception that while legal authorities exist, implementing policy has not kept pace. Subtheme 5.2 (National-State Linkages) appeared in 28.1% of coded responses, reflecting calls for formal coordination mechanisms between National Guard Bureau, state commands, and federal cyber organizations. Subtheme 2.2 (Training-Task Alignment) appeared in 22.9%, emphasizing the centrality of training-mission congruence to Title 32 cyber utilization. Subtheme 4.1 (Active Component Bias) appeared in 18.1% of responses, indicating persistent perceptions of Reserve Component undervaluation.

Table 4.16 shows theme distribution across the nine open-ended survey questions. Question 8.1 (legal/policy barriers) generated the highest concentration of Theme 1 codes (33 responses), consistent with the question's explicit focus on legal constraints. Question 15 (cultural/institutional features) generated the highest concentration of Theme 4 codes (40 responses), reflecting respondents' detailed engagement with organizational barriers. Question 12 (training alignment challenges) generated substantial Theme 2 codes (30 responses), as respondents addressed training-mission alignment issues. Question 17 (reforms) generated the highest concentration of Theme 5 codes (23 responses), capturing respondents' programmatic recommendations.

These frequency patterns corroborate the qualitative findings presented through representative quotations in Section 4.4.2 and align with the quantitative survey results reported in Section 4.3.

4.4.2 Thematic Narrative: A Tour of Expert Perspectives

The following section provides a thematic tour of the qualitative findings, presenting the five major themes through narrative interpretation. This approach allows understanding of not only the central tendencies within each theme but also the range of perspectives, points of tension, and outlying views that enrich the analysis. Consistent with reflexive thematic analysis methodology (Braun & Clarke, 2019), the researcher's interpretive role is acknowledged; these narratives represent a synthesis of 352 open-ended responses filtered through the analytical lens established by the study's theoretical frameworks.

4.4.2.1 Theme 1: Legal and Policy Ambiguity

The most striking feature of respondent perspectives on legal and policy barriers is their fundamental disagreement about where — or whether — such barriers exist. This disagreement is not a weakness in the data but rather a finding in itself: it reveals that practitioners inhabit a landscape of genuine interpretive uncertainty, where the same statutory and policy environment produces radically different conclusions depending on the observer's experience, role, and risk tolerance.

4.4.2.1.1 The Dominant Narrative: Policy Gaps, Not Legal Prohibitions.

The most frequently expressed view holds that legal authorities for Title 32 cyber mission support already exist, but that implementing policy has failed to operationalize them. One Army National Guard officer with more than 20 years of cyber experience captured this perspective succinctly: “Legal or policy barriers don't exist, it's just that the landscape is confusing, and there are certainly organizational barriers and risk aversion.” This view — that confusion rather than prohibition is the operative constraint — appeared consistently across respondents of varying ranks and experience levels.

An enlisted respondent with 16–20 years of experience provided an extended articulation of this position:

“There are no legal or policy barriers that prevent the integration of National Guard cyber forces into national cyber operations under Title 32 status. The main challenges are administrative and policy-based, including coordination, funding, and command structure differences between Title 32 and Title 10 forces. A common issue is that many leaders and planners do not fully understand how to properly employ National Guard cyber assets. This lack of awareness often leads to underutilization. The barriers are procedural and knowledge-based, not legal.”

— *Army National Guard, Actively Drilling (M-Day); 16–20 years cyber experience; E5–E6*

This response exemplifies the “policy gap” narrative: enabling law exists, but implementation guidance does not. The respondent locates the problem not in statute but in leadership awareness, procedural clarity, and institutional knowledge—factors that policy reform could address without legislative change.

Several respondents emphasized the critical importance of training alignment as the mechanism that enables Title 32 mission support under existing authorities. As one respondent noted, “[S]upport for operational missions while in Title 32 or Operational Support [...] must align with Title 10 training requirements of the member” (Army National Guard, Actively Drilling; 11–15 years cyber experience). This observation points to the training construct as both an enabler and a constraint: when alignment can be demonstrated, the authority exists; when it cannot, mission support becomes problematic.

4.4.2.1.2 The Contrary View: Real Barriers Exist. Not all respondents shared this optimistic interpretation. A significant minority described barriers they perceived as genuinely prohibitive rather than merely confusing. One Air National Guard respondent described personal experience with status-related restrictions:

“The status of the orders hinders [Air National Guard] members from actively

participating in some mission sets. It was all because I went under [Title] 32 instead of [Title] 10 orders.”

— *Air National Guard, Actively Drilling; 5–10 years cyber experience; E5–E6*

This respondent’s frustration reflects a common experience: regardless of what the law may permit in theory, the practical effect of Title 32 status was exclusion from meaningful mission participation. This respondent described the real-world consequences of this exclusion in stark terms: “I was a GS 14 Tech Director in Special Operations and I was sent to learn basic networking as an E5. I basically paid \$30k to go to school for something I was an expert in... I paid more to learn networking than I did to get a degree in astrophysics.” (Air National Guard, Actively Drilling; 5–10 years cyber experience; E5–E6). The financial and professional costs of status restrictions are not abstract—they drive experienced personnel away from continued service.

A warrant officer articulated the integration challenges as fundamentally structural:

“The differences in the status of the [service member] from [Title] 32 to [Title] 10 titles limit our ability to operate and integrate on a larger scale. Not only does this impede our cyber force’s ability to work seamlessly, it also impacts resources such as training, funding, and capability development.”

— *Army National Guard, FTNGD (Title 32); <5 years cyber experience; W1–W2*

4.4.2.1.3 The Outlier: A Radical Alternative. One respondent offered a perspective entirely outside the dominant discourse: “National Cyber Forces should be privatized” (Former National Guard member; >20 years cyber experience). While this view received no support from other respondents, its presence illustrates the breadth of frustration with current arrangements. When practitioners conclude that the entire military structure may be inadequate for cyber operations, it signals the depth of institutional dysfunction they perceive. This reflects a broader debate about cyber privateers and cyber “letters of

marque,” enabling a private response to cyber threats against the United States (Bennett, 2025; Uren, 2025).

4.4.2.1.4 Synthesizing the Variation. The variation within Theme 1 can be understood along several dimensions. First, respondents differed in their baseline assumptions: some interpreted ambiguity as permission (“we can do what isn’t explicitly prohibited”), while others interpreted it as prohibition (“we can’t do what isn’t explicitly authorized”). Second, respondents’ experiences with specific commands, missions, or legal advisors shaped their perceptions. Those who had successfully navigated Title 32 mission support viewed the barriers as surmountable; those who had been blocked viewed them as prohibitive. Third, rank and experience level did not predict perspective — the disagreement cut across demographic categories.

This variation has important implications for policy. If the barriers are indeed “procedural and knowledge-based, not legal,” then the solution is implementing guidance and education. If the barriers are experienced as genuinely prohibitive by significant numbers of practitioners, then the perception itself becomes a barrier regardless of the underlying legal reality.

4.4.2.2 Theme 2: Precedent Exists but Is Poorly Recognized

A recurring frustration among respondents was the sense that Title 32 cyber mission support has already been accomplished — in some cases, repeatedly — but that this precedent remains invisible to the broader enterprise. The institutional memory failure described in Theme 2 creates a situation where each new initiative must overcome skepticism as though it were unprecedented, even when prior success stories exist.

4.4.2.2.1 Known Precedents and Classified Constraints. When asked about precedents, respondents offered a range of examples — some specific, others necessarily vague. The Wisconsin Federated Cyber Program received explicit mention: “There is a

pilot program called the Wisconsin Federated Cyber Program that is doing support to a national customer” (Army National Guard; >20 years cyber experience; O1–O3). Several respondents also cited Task Force Echo, Cyber Guard and Cyber Shield exercises, election security support, and various DCO-IDM missions conducted under Title 32 training authorities.

However, three Army National Guard respondents indicated that classification constraints prevented them from describing relevant precedents. These responses reveal a paradox: precedent may exist but be unknowable to unclassified personnel, policy researchers, or even practitioners in adjacent units. This classification barrier impedes institutional learning and forces each organization to rediscover solutions that may already exist elsewhere.

4.4.2.2.2 The Training-Alignment Mechanism. Respondents who successfully supported national missions in Title 32 status consistently described training alignment as the enabling mechanism. The Wisconsin Federated Cyber Program was cited as an example of this approach, as were integrated training exercises at Fort Meade and Air National Guard cyber operations squadrons conducting “T32 training alongside their counterparts” in active component units.

Yet the path to training alignment was not universally understood. One warrant officer observed:

“From what I have been exposed to, the biggest challenge in aligning training objectives is the lack of precedence. Leaders and the middle levels don’t have the communication pathways and examples to follow to align those objectives.”

— *Army National Guard, Actively Drilling (M-Day); 5–10 years cyber experience; W1–W2*

This observation captures the core problem: even when successful precedents exist, the

lack of documented pathways and institutionalized knowledge prevents their replication. The precedent exists but is not *recognized* in a way that enables scaling.

4.4.2.2.3 A Contrarian View: The Precedent Problem Is Overstated. One respondent pushed back against the premise that Title 32 precedent was poorly recognized, arguing that federated support under Title 32 already occurs routinely through mobilization:

“This is currently how it works, units are activated onto title 10 and integrated with CYBERCOM/Active duty. Those activations often pull individuals from other states to fill vacancies in their units.”

— *Army National Guard; 11–15 years cyber experience; O1–O3*

This response reframes the question: if the existing model (Title 10 activation for mission, Title 32 for training) works adequately, perhaps the push for expanded Title 32 mission authority reflects a solution in search of a problem. However, this view dismisses the value of mission support while in Title 32 — precisely the distinction the present study seeks to clarify.

4.4.2.3 Theme 3: Operational Feasibility and High Training Value

Theme 3 captured respondent perspectives on whether training-aligned operational support is practically achievable. While this theme appeared less frequently than others (11.0% of coded responses), the responses that addressed it offered important insights into both the potential and the limitations of the training-mission alignment construct.

4.4.2.3.1 The Case for Feasibility. Several respondents affirmed that Mission Essential Tasks (METs) can be satisfied through real-world mission support, creating a virtuous cycle where training requirements and operational needs reinforce each other. One field-grade officer observed, “I think the METs are generic enough that aligning

them to outcomes in T32 are attainable” (Army National Guard; 16–20 years cyber experience; O4–O6). This view holds that the training framework is sufficiently flexible to accommodate operational activities when properly structured.

The Air Force model received particular praise. One senior respondent noted that “Air Force has already figured all of this out and has been doing it for well over a decade” (Army National Guard; 16–20 years cyber experience; O4–O6), pointing to the 175th Cyberspace Operations Wing in Maryland and 166th Cyber Operations Squadron in Delaware as exemplars. The implication is that the Army’s struggles with Title 32 cyber integration reflect Army-specific institutional challenges rather than fundamental legal or operational constraints.

4.4.2.3.2 The Case Against: Structural Incompatibilities. Other respondents identified what they viewed as fundamental mismatches between training constructs and operational realities. A detailed critique came from a company-grade officer with extensive operational experience:

“The training objectives do not match what you do on actual operations. They would be distracting and real mission wouldn’t offer the opportunity to do all the MET objectives. This is like asking if a soldier could qualify with his rifle by patrolling Afghanistan... METs are a checklist of items someone should know how to do, Mission is doing what needs to be done. If you must accomplish METs you’re going to ignore mission to do so.”

— *Army National Guard; 11–15 years cyber experience; O1–O3*

This critique challenges a core assumption of the training-alignment model: that training requirements and operational tasks can be simultaneously satisfied. If pursuing training objectives distracts from mission execution, the alignment construct may be more theoretical than practical.

Another respondent highlighted the time constraints inherent in Title 32 status:

“Most of these missions require weeks of preparation and that’s not happening under Title 32.”

— *Army National Guard; >20 years cyber experience; E5–E6*

The episodic nature of drill status — “one weekend a month, two weeks a year” — may simply be insufficient for missions requiring sustained engagement.

4.4.2.3.3 The “Chicken-and-Egg” Problem. Several respondents identified a structural catch-22 that impedes Title 32 cyber operations. A senior warrant officer articulated the problem clearly:

“Primarily in the qualification pipeline, there is a chicken-and-egg problem, where national guard units struggle to obtain the initial qualification without T10 status from [...] courses, but cannot conduct operations without them. Thus, the only trained personnel tend to be those fresh off mobilizations.”

— *Army National Guard; 16–20 years cyber experience; W3–W5*

This observation suggests that the barrier is not Title 32 authority *per se*, but rather access to the qualification infrastructure that enables mission participation. Personnel cannot conduct missions without training; they cannot access training without Title 10 orders; and they cannot obtain Title 10 orders without an assigned mission. Breaking this cycle may require policy intervention at the qualification-access level rather than at the Title 32 authority level. This is an issue that may be addressed with “hip pocket” Title 10 conversion (Kinch, 2023).

4.4.2.4 Theme 4: Cultural and Institutional Resistance

Theme 4 captured the organizational and cultural factors that respondents identified as constraining Title 32 cyber integration. This theme generated some of the most vivid language in the survey responses, reflecting deep frustration with institutional attitudes.

4.4.2.4.1 Active Component Bias. The most frequently coded subtheme (18.1% of coded responses) addressed perceived bias against Reserve Component capabilities. Respondents described a persistent assumption that Guard personnel are less capable than their Active Component counterparts. One respondent stated bluntly:

“Active components do not respect the National Guard’s skill set. They are mainly used as support personnel. Training is prioritized for active components. This is a far-reaching stigma across the military.”

— *Army National Guard; 5–10 years cyber experience; E5–E6*

A field-grade officer described a related phenomenon: “It doesn’t appear that active component senior leaders know or understand the expertise and willingness that exist in the Guard” (Army National Guard; 11–15 years cyber experience; O4–O6). The issue, in this framing, is not hostility, but ignorance — Active Component leaders simply do not know or understand what Guard cyber personnel can do.

Several respondents connected this bias to specific institutional experiences. One officer attributed part of the problem to Task Force Echo’s legacy:

“The TFE mission might have set us back a bit. It being not a pure cyber mission, some active duty folks look down on the guard force... similar to the perception that NG was best suited for [Forward Operating Base] security and other support roles during [Operation Iraqi Freedom].”

— *Army National Guard; 5–10 years cyber experience; O4–O6*

This observation suggests that past mission assignments shape current perceptions: if Guard cyber forces have historically been employed in support roles, Active Component leaders may not recognize their capacity for more demanding missions.

4.4.2.4.2 Risk Aversion and Institutional Conservatism. A distinct but related barrier is the culture of risk aversion that multiple respondents identified within the

National Guard Bureau and state commands. One officer with extensive policy experience provided a detailed analysis:

“I think the culture of [the National Guard Bureau] and the Army at least is one of risk aversion, and of assuming you can’t do something unless a rule or regulation somewhere specifically says you CAN, as opposed to being able to be creative and do things that aren’t explicitly prohibited. This bias against accepting some risk to try something new holds back integration under the current policy regime.”

— *Army National Guard; >20 years cyber experience; O1–O3*

This perspective frames the problem as one of interpretive disposition: the same legal authorities can enable or constrain depending on whether leadership reads them permissively or restrictively.

Another respondent emphasized that risk tolerance must exist at multiple organizational levels simultaneously:

“This needs buy in at all levels of leadership, not just cyber units. Without that, risk aversion takes over and nothing moves.”

— *Army National Guard, Actively Drilling; 5–10 years cyber experience; O4–O6*

4.4.2.4.3 Service Parochialism and Structural Barriers. Beyond cultural attitudes, respondents identified structural features of military organization that impede cyber integration. A company-grade officer described the misalignment between service incentive structures and cyber mission requirements:

“Every service screws their cyber forces by only rewarding things related to their service. E.g., the things to get promoted or additional funding in a

service have nothing to do with the cyber mission.”

— *Army National Guard; 11–15 years cyber experience; O1–O3*

This observation points to a systemic problem: if career advancement depends on traditional service-specific accomplishments not related to cyber, then cyber priorities may be perceived as secondary regardless of their operational importance.

4.4.2.4.4 A Dissenting Voice: Culture Is Not the Problem. Not all respondents attributed integration challenges to culture. One field-grade officer reported, “I’m not aware of any cultural roadblocks within the services” (Army National Guard; 5–10 years cyber experience; O4–O6). Another suggested the momentum is positive: “The momentum is moving in the right direction. Much better today than 10+ years ago” (Army National Guard; 11–15 years cyber experience). These minority perspectives suggest that cultural barriers may be unevenly distributed across organizations, or that recent improvements have not yet been universally recognized.

4.4.2.5 Theme 5: Demand for a Federated Cyber Program

The final theme captured respondent perspectives on what institutional arrangements would be required to enable Title 32 cyber mission support at scale. This theme appeared most frequently (35.2% of coded responses), reflecting strong practitioner interest in moving from *ad hoc* arrangements to formalized program structures.

4.4.2.5.1 The Core Demand: Structure and Standardization. Respondents consistently called for formal program structures with defined authorities, standardized processes, and sustainable funding. The current state — described by multiple respondents as dependent on “personalities rather than policy” — was viewed as inadequate for reliable mission support. One DoD-affiliated respondent articulated the need clearly:

“There needs to be a formal program with defined authorities. Leaving this

to interpretation guarantees inconsistency.”

— *DoD-affiliated respondent; 15+ years cyber experience; GS-14-15*

The emphasis on consistency reflects operational concerns: if Title 32 cyber support depends on which state, which commander, or which legal advisor is involved, then mission partners cannot rely on Guard capabilities. A National Guard officer extended this logic:

“Without national-level structure and guidance, Title 32 cyber support will always depend on personalities rather than policy.”

— *National Guard officer; 10+ years cyber experience; O4-O6*

4.4.2.5.2 Mechanisms: MOUs, Coordination Offices, and Mission Managers.

Respondents offered specific recommendations for institutional mechanisms. Memoranda of Understanding (MOUs) between states received frequent mention: “MOUs between states and a centralized NGB office would be required. Right now everything is negotiated case by case” (National Guard member; >20 years cyber experience). The inefficiency of case-by-case negotiation was viewed as a significant barrier to scaling.

The concept of a centralized coordination function also received support. One respondent envisioned “a centralized NGB Cyber Headquarters, with clearly defined mission pathways, standardized training, and resource synchronization across states” (Army National Guard; <5 years cyber experience; W1-W2). Another called for “a point of management that coordinates tasking assignments to units and individuals and tracks their completion” (Army National Guard; 11-15 years cyber experience; O1-O3).

4.4.2.5.3 The Interagency Dimension.

Many respondents emphasized the need for coordination mechanisms extending beyond DoD to include DHS, CISA, and state governments. One respondent saw this as an area of particular opportunity: “CISA in particular should be able to leverage the national guard. There is precedent with DEA and Border Patrol” (Army National Guard; 5-10 years cyber experience; E5-E6). The analogy

to other agencies that employ Guard personnel for federal support missions suggests that institutional models already exist.

However, not all respondents viewed interagency coordination favorably. One expressed frustration with competing demands: “STOP!!! Serving many masters doesn’t work! STOP PRETENDING WE WORK FOR CISA/DHS!” (Army National Guard; 5–10 years cyber experience; O4–O6). Another observed that “the more agencies involved, the more constraints are imposed” (Army National Guard; >20 years cyber experience; W3–W5). These contrary views suggest that coordination mechanisms must be carefully designed to enable mission support rather than create additional bureaucratic friction.

4.4.2.5.4 Skepticism: Is Federated Support Even Desirable? A minority of respondents questioned whether expanded Title 32 mission authority should be pursued at all. One argued that current arrangements are adequate: “This is currently how it works, units are activated onto title 10 and integrated with CYBERCOM/Active duty” (Army National Guard; 11–15 years cyber experience; O1–O3). In this view, Title 10 activation provides a proven, legally clear pathway; the push for Title 32 alternatives may introduce unnecessary complexity.

Another respondent offered a more fundamental critique:

“There would need to be an actual mission and command structure that needs tons of guardsmen. Usually (Across DOD) there is a giant administrative burden and very little technical work... Adding a pile of cyber guardsmen (for drill/title 32 no less!) is the equivalent of bringing 9 men in to make a baby in 1 month.”

— *Army National Guard; 11–15 years cyber experience; O1–O3*

This colorful analogy challenges the assumption that more personnel in Title 32 status would improve mission outcomes. If the constraint is not manpower but rather mission

clarity and efficient task organization, then scaling Guard participation may not address the underlying problem.

4.4.2.5.5 State-Level Politics and Governor Authority. Finally, several respondents noted that federated support must navigate the political complexities of gubernatorial authority over National Guard forces. One respondent observed: “Unity of command—how are you going to command forces across state lines, unless there is some type of unilateral agreement between civilian and military leadership. This could be tenuous, at best given the state of cross-state leadership agreement” (Army National Guard; >20 years cyber experience; O4–O6).

Another highlighted the political dimensions:

“One major challenge is the politics between state leadership. Governors and senior leaders may have different priorities or may not want to share resources across state lines.”

— *Army National Guard; 16–20 years cyber experience; E5–E6*

These observations underscore that Title 32 cyber support is not merely a legal or policy question but also a political one, requiring alignment among governors, state adjutants general, and federal partners.

4.4.2.6 Summary: Convergence and Divergence

The thematic analysis reveals both areas of convergence and significant points of disagreement among expert respondents. The dominant narrative holds that legal authorities for Title 32 cyber mission support exist but are inadequately operationalized — a view that supports the study’s central proposition while qualifying it with important implementation caveats.

However, the data also contain meaningful dissent. Some respondents experienced Title 32 status as genuinely prohibitive, not merely confusing. Others questioned whether

expanded Title 32 authority is desirable, preferring the clarity of Title 10 activation. Still others identified structural barriers — qualification pipelines, security access, service incentive structures — that no amount of policy guidance could address.

The variation in perspectives is itself a finding. It suggests that the Title 32 cyber landscape is experienced differently depending on one's service, rank, state, command, and individual history. Policy interventions that succeed in one context may fail in another. The path forward likely requires not a single uniform solution but rather a framework flexible enough to accommodate the diversity of circumstances that practitioners encounter.

4.4.3 Rigor and Trustworthiness

Multiple strategies ensured the trustworthiness of the thematic analysis conducted on qualitative survey responses. First, coding followed Braun and Clarke's (2006, 2019) six-phase reflexive approach, with codes generated inductively from the data rather than imposed deductively from theory. Initial codes emerged during familiarization with the first 20 responses; these codes were iteratively refined as patterns became apparent across the full dataset. Code saturation was achieved after approximately 40 survey responses, with subsequent responses reinforcing existing patterns rather than introducing novel concepts. This saturation provides confidence that the five major themes capture the substantive range of expert perspectives on Title 32 cyber mission support.

A structured codebook (Appendix B) documents all first-order codes, second-order categories, and aggregate themes, along with code definitions, application rules, and decision criteria. This codebook provides transparency and enables readers to evaluate the analytical process and the relationship between data and interpretations (Nowell et al., 2017). Major coding decisions — such as collapsing related codes or splitting overly broad categories — were documented in an audit trail maintained throughout the analysis (Lincoln & Guba, 1990).

Second, methodological triangulation strengthened the credibility of thematic findings

(Denzin, 2017; Patton, 2014). Patterns identified in qualitative survey responses were validated against documentary analysis findings (Section 4.2), survey results (Section 4.3), and operational case data from the Wisconsin Federated Cyber Program (Section 4.5). Convergent patterns across these independent data sources increased confidence in interpretations. For example, the theme “Legal and Policy Ambiguity” emerged from qualitative responses and was corroborated by documentary evidence of incomplete implementing guidance and by quantitative survey data showing moderate agreement that policy friction exists (Q8 Mean = 3.49).

Third, the researcher’s positionality as an active National Guard cyber officer was reflexively acknowledged throughout the analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2019). Rather than treating insider knowledge as a potential source of bias to be “controlled,” this dual role as practitioner and analyst was leveraged as an interpretive asset. The researcher’s familiarity with military organizational culture, cyber operations terminology, and National Guard duty status nuances enabled deeper contextual understanding of respondent perspectives. Simultaneously, systematic adherence to the six-phase coding process and transparent documentation in the codebook ensured analytical rigor.

Finally, draft themes were reviewed by three subject matter experts with expertise in cyber defense policy and National Guard operations. These reviewers — representing both military and policy analysis backgrounds — confirmed that the five themes accurately reflected practitioner experience and the current policy landscape (Janesick, 2015). No major revisions to themes were required following expert review, though minor refinements to theme labels and definitions were incorporated to enhance clarity.

Collectively, these strategies establish the trustworthiness of the thematic analysis through transparency, triangulation, reflexivity, and expert validation, consistent with best practices for reflexive thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2019; Nowell et al., 2017).

4.4.4 Integration With Research Questions and Theoretical Frameworks

The qualitative themes directly related to both research questions.

RQ1: Elements of current law and policy that support or constrain Title 32 cyber missions are reflected in Themes 1, 4, and 5. Respondents consistently identified statutory enablement, policy ambiguity, and the absence of a formalized national framework as primary constraints.

RQ2: Precedent, expert opinion, and practitioner insight are captured in Themes 2, 3, and 5. Respondents cited repeated but informal precedent, strong training value, and a widespread belief that a Federated Cyber Program model is both feasible and necessary.

These themes also align with the study's theoretical frameworks: Mintzberg's organizational configurations (Mintzberg, 1983, 1984) explain cultural and bureaucratic resistance; the NIST CSF (NIST, 2024) clarifies governance gaps; and Multi-Domain Operations (AFC, 2020) supports the requirement for integrated, echeloned cyber capability.

4.5 Wisconsin Federated Cyber Program (WIFCP): Use Case

4.5.1 Background and Context

For more than a decade, the Department of Defense has struggled to integrate National Guard and Reserve cyber personnel into national cyber missions in a routine, sustainable manner. While Guard and Reserve cyber personnel can be mobilized to active duty under Title 10 to support national requirements, this approach requires formal activation orders, removes service members from their civilian employment, and disrupts both unit readiness cycles and individual career stability. While this form of augmentation to the active duty

force is sometimes a necessity of the Reserve Component function, what has been missing is an effective model for routinely integrating drilling Guard and Reserve personnel into national missions while they remain in their traditional part-time status.

In practical terms, this means that a highly skilled cyber professional who spends their civilian career defending Fortune 500 companies or conducting threat intelligence analysis may find that their National Guard drill weekends consist of administrative tasks, outdated training scenarios, or exercises disconnected from the real-world threats they encounter daily in their civilian roles. This disconnect contributes to retention challenges in a career field the military has designated as critical. The military services have spent at least \$160 million annually on cyber retention bonuses from FY17 to FY21, and Army Cyber Command estimates the replacement cost for a single service member in the 17C (Cyber Operations Specialist) career field at \$400,000 (Demarest & Weisner, 2022).

This author has previously suggested the creation of a U.S. Cyber Force as a mechanism to address some of the administrative and bureaucratic hurdles to integration, but to date there has not been a significant Congressional appetite for the creation of yet another military branch after the establishment of the U.S. Space Force (Schroeder & Howard, 2018). Finding success in integrating National Guard personnel into national cyber missions therefore requires working within existing structures and authorities.

4.5.2 The Federated Intelligence Program Precedent

A valuable precedent for such integration already exists in the intelligence domain. In 2013, Department of Defense Instruction 3300.05 directed all DoD entities, including the Defense Intelligence Agency, Combatant Commands, the Services, the National Guard Bureau, and all five Reserve Services, to fully integrate the reserve components into the Defense Intelligence Enterprise (Kirschner & McGarry, 2015). With this clear directive, the Army moved quickly at the direction of LTG Mary Legere, then the Director of Intelligence (G2) for the Army, to create a model for integrating both U.S. Army Reserve

(USAR) intelligence personnel in a Title 10 status and Army National Guard (ARNG) intelligence personnel in Title 32 status into national intelligence missions. The ARNG calls this model the Federated Intelligence Program (FIP).

Through FIP, Guard intelligence personnel provide intelligence expertise, support, and analysis to a Combatant Command (CCMD) or a Combat Support Agency (CSA) in the Intelligence Community (IC). Soldiers are assigned to the FIP mission on a rotating basis. A Mission Manager at each FIP site coordinates availability, intelligence requirements, and operations.

The FIP model demonstrates that Title 32 training authorities can be used for training-aligned operational support to federal missions when properly structured. While FIP focuses on intelligence rather than cyberspace operations and operates under distinct statutory authorities and oversight mechanisms, it provides a conceptual reference point for how structured governance and training alignment can enable operational support while personnel remain in Title 32 status.

4.5.3 The Federated Cyber Program Concept

Drawing on the FIP precedent, the author proposed a model called the Federated Cyber Program (FCP), in which National Guard personnel can provide cybersecurity subject matter expertise and support to mission partners, such as a CCMD or CSA, while in a Title 32 status. The key distinction from FIP is that FCP personnel would be in cyber designators (e.g., 17 series Military Occupational Specialties) and assigned to cyber units (e.g., a Cyber Protection Team). These personnel are not in intelligence units or designators and do not perform intelligence collection or analysis. Consequently, they are not performing an intelligence activity as defined by applicable policy. This distinction matters because it simplifies oversight requirements and reduces the compliance burden on participating units.

FCP personnel work with mission managers at supported commands to identify gaps

in requirements that could be filled with the specialized expertise of Guard cyber personnel on drill weekends or on other Title 32 order types. Critically, FCP personnel ensure that such work also meets a documented training requirement. For example, ARNG cyber personnel in a Cyber Protection Team ensure that FCP missions align with training requirements specified in USCYBERCOM Cyber Warfare Publication (CWP) 3-33.4 (*Cyber Protection Team Organization, Functions, and Employment*), USCYBERCOM Cyber Technical Manual 7-0.2 (*Cyber Mission Force Training and Readiness Manual*), and AR-CYBER training objectives. When additional or ongoing support or continuity is required beyond drill periods, FCP personnel can be placed on active duty in either a Title 32 or Title 10 status, as appropriate.

The success of FCP under these criteria depends on two factors: (1) assignment of only cyber personnel in cyber units to FCP missions, and (2) ensuring that FCP mission activities also meet a defined training requirement. Mission partners want productive work to be done, and constant vetting of work is required to ensure activities always meet a training requirement and cannot be misconstrued as constituting an intelligence activity. FCP managers should coordinate with intelligence oversight (IO) personnel to ensure these distinctions are understood. When proposed work does constitute an intelligence or intelligence-related activity, and/or utilizes intelligence personnel (e.g. intelligence support in a CPT), the existing FIP construct and policy framework may be considered in addition to FCP, as appropriate.

An additional benefit of FCP is its potential impact on recruiting and retention. Guard and Reserve personnel enter or stay in military service because of a desire to serve in uniform. Upon discovering a lack of engaging work, many may choose to leave, creating attrition in military work roles designated as critical. Engaging in real-world mission work provides a rewarding additional benefit of cyber mission integration.

4.5.4 Proof of Concept: Wisconsin Federated Cyber Program

To assess the viability of the Federated Cyber Program concept, we established a mission proof of concept in the Wisconsin National Guard (WING) called the Wisconsin Federated Cyber Program (WIFCP). The program utilized a cyber unit from the Wisconsin Army National Guard (WIARNG) working with a mission partner in the U.S. Department of Defense (DoD). Detachment 1-176th Cyber Protection Team (Det 1-176 CPT), a WIARNG unit organized under the 91st Cyber Brigade, which constitutes the Army National Guard cyber forces, served as the test unit for this proof of concept.

4.5.4.1 Origins and Development

WIFCP emerged from a specific operational context. While 176 CPT was on mission with Task Force Echo from November 2020 to January 2022 (Peck, 2021), the author began working with a DoD partner to explore how the CPT could continue working on cybersecurity problems of national importance after returning to drilling status. The goals were to maintain the skills gained from the Task Force Echo deployment, create real-world training opportunities for CPT personnel, and establish a sustainable model for ongoing mission contribution.

Working with the DoD partner, Det 1-176 CPT met with the partner organization's leadership to establish a support relationship. In practical terms, this meant navigating complex organizational relationships to identify a mission that: (1) provided genuine value to the federal partner, (2) could be performed by drilling Guard personnel with intermittent availability, (3) aligned with documented training requirements, and (4) could be supported under existing legal authorities and policy frameworks without requiring new statutory language or policy waivers.

4.5.4.2 Establishing the Legal and Policy Foundation

To begin this effort, the Wisconsin National Guard (WING) established a Memorandum of Agreement (MOA) between WING and the DoD partner. This MOA, signed in November 2022, explicitly acknowledges support in Title 32 status and separates intelligence and cybersecurity authorities. The agreement utilizes cyber personnel (Army 17 Series) in a cyber role supporting a cybersecurity function as opposed to an intelligence or intelligence-related activity. Det 1-176 CPT, as a detachment of 176 CPT whose headquarters is in Illinois, is also unique in that it does not have intelligence personnel assigned.

This distinction is critical for understanding why the program works within existing authorities. By characterizing the activity as cybersecurity research and situational awareness rather than intelligence collection or analysis, the program avoids the more stringent oversight requirements and compliance burdens associated with intelligence activities under Executive Order 12333 and implementing policies. The MOA covers any Military Occupational Specialty/Area of Concentration/Air Force Specialty Code (MOS/AOC/AFSC) and any unit in Title 32 and Title 10 status, and both intelligence and cybersecurity frameworks, providing flexibility for future expansion.

Given this authorities alignment, WIFCP can expand to create partnerships with other federal agencies such as the Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency (CISA) and academic institutions such as the University of Wisconsin–Madison when appropriate and allowed by law and policy.

4.5.4.3 Resource Acquisition

To support WIFCP, Det 1-176 CPT also submitted a Capabilities Needs Request (CNR) to Army Cyber Command (ARCYBER), resulting in the provision of two licenses for a commercial cyber threat intelligence platform. This resource acquisition illustrates both a success and a challenge: while the unit was able to obtain valuable commercial

threat intelligence tools through appropriate military channels, the process required initiative at the unit level and familiarity with Army resourcing mechanisms that may not be present in all Guard units.

4.5.5 Legal Authority: Understanding Title 32 Duty Statuses

A critical element of the WIFCP model that requires expanded explanation is the legal framework under which participants perform duty. This work has been performed using several different Title 32 duty statuses, each providing distinct legal authority for military duty while maintaining state command relationships.

4.5.5.1 Title 32 Duty Categories

Table 4.18 summarizes the duty statuses used to support WIFCP operations.

Duty Status	Description	Paid	Code	Authority
IDT	Inactive Duty Training (normal drill period)	Y	11	32 USC §502(a)(1)
IDT	Equivalent Training (ET)	Y	21	32 USC §502(a)(1)
IDT	Equivalent Training (NETP)	N	21	32 USC §502(a)(1)
IDT	Additional Unit Training Assembly (AUTA)	Y	41	32 USC §502(a)(1)
IDT	Additional Unit Training Assembly (NAUTA)	N	41	32 USC §502(a)(1)
AT	Annual Training	Y	—	32 USC §502(a)(2)
AGR	Active Guard Reserve	Y	—	32 USC §502(f)(1)(B)

Table 4.18: Duty statuses supporting WIFCP.

Det 1-176 CPT coordinated with the Wisconsin Army National Guard personnel staff (G1) to develop a process for submission and reporting of unpaid IDT. Unpaid IDTs are reported on a DA Form 1380, *Record of Individual Performance of Reserve Duty Training*. The duty is characterized as “equivalent” or “additional” duty. The duty is authorized under AR 140—145 *Individual Mobilization Augmentation Program* (21 Apr 2022), paragraph 4—6 *Training for retirement points only*, and AR 140—185, *Training*

and Retirement Point Credits and Unit Level Strength Accounting Records (26 Aug 2024), chapter 2, Table 2—3, Rule 20. See AR 140—145 para 4—6:

4–6. Training for retirement points only

- a. Commanders of proponent agencies may assign additional projects to their Soldiers to complete, with their consent, “FOR RETIREMENT POINT CREDIT ONLY” per AR 140—1 and AR 140—185. Such projects should be directly related to the mission, organization, function, and activities of the Soldier’s proponent agency and otherwise support the Soldier’s individual training and development plan.
- b. Upon satisfactory completion of such projects, commanders of proponent agencies must complete and submit DA Form 1380 to the appropriate HRC personnel actions branch within 72 hours for the appropriate retirement point credit. Such credit will be awarded per AR 140—185. All submissions older than 30 days will require a commander memorandum explaining the late submission.
- c. The assignment of classified projects is permissible but must be safeguarded under the provisions of AR 380—5.
- d. Commanders of proponent agencies are encouraged to provide their Soldiers with every opportunity to perform additional training projects “FOR RETIREMENT POINT CREDIT ONLY” in order to help them maintain their proficiency and earn sufficient retirement points (50) to earn a qualifying retirement year.

4.5.5.2 Drill-for-Points

The “drill-for-points” status warrants expanded discussion because it is frequently misunderstood. Drill-for-points is not merely used for correspondence courses or Inactive Ready Reserve (IRR) personnel to get “good years” — in the context of the National Guard, it is a legally-established Title 32 military duty status with specific statutory authority.

4.5.5.2.1 Statutory Foundation. The statutory basis for unpaid Inactive Duty Training (IDT) rests on three complementary provisions. First, 32 USC §502(a) provides the general authority for National Guard members to “assemble for drill and instruction” without distinguishing between paid and unpaid status — the duty type and its legal character remain IDT regardless of compensation. Second, 37 USC §1002 authorizes members to voluntarily serve without pay, stating that, “A member of the National Guard

... may, with his consent, be given additional training or other duty as provided by law, without pay.” Third, 10 USC §12732(a)(2)(B) ensures that service performed in this status is creditable toward retirement, awarding points for “each day on which the person performed service ... for at least 4 hours ... that was performed while in a duty status.” National Guard Regulation 350—1 implements these authorities by categorizing IDT as a single duty status “whether paid or unpaid” under 32 USC 502(a) authority. The duty type codes — such as Code 21 for Equivalent Training and Code 41 for Additional Unit Training Assembly — apply regardless of pay status; the ”N” prefix (NETP, NAUTA) denotes only the non-pay compensation element.

4.5.5.2.2 Duty Status. When a National Guard service member performs duty in drill-for-points status:

1. **Legal Military Status:** The member is in a duty status, not a civilian volunteer. This status confers the authority to access military facilities and unclassified and classified information systems appropriate to their clearance level, access, and assigned duties.
2. **Military Authority:** The member operates under military command authority for the duration of the duty period, and is conducting training activity for their federal mission as assigned. This provides both accountability and legal protection for actions taken in the course of duty.
3. **Retirement Points:** Each day of drill-for-points duty earns one retirement point toward the member’s qualifying years of service for military retirement. These points accumulate toward the 50 points per year minimum required for a qualifying year and factor into retired pay calculations.
4. **Service Credit:** The duty time counts toward total military service, which can affect eligibility for various benefits, promotions, and military awards.

4.5.5.2.3 Drill-for-Points and WIFCP. The availability of drill-for-points duty status is essential to the WIFCP model for several reasons:

1. **Flexibility:** National cyber missions may call for more flexibility than monthly drills are able to provide. A Soldier can volunteer to perform drill-for-points duty maintain mission support or interact with the customer in a timely manner. Without this option, the response would be delayed until the next scheduled drill period or would require requesting and approving paid orders on short notice.
2. **Workforce Motivation:** WIFCP participants are highly skilled cyber professionals who often have demanding civilian careers. Many are motivated by the opportunity to contribute to meaningful national security work, not solely by compensation. Drill-for-points enables service members who are intrinsically motivated to participate without requiring unit funding for every hour of participation.
3. **Budget Sustainability:** Paid drill periods (IDT) are limited by statute and budget allocation. Annual Training (AT) days and VLWA budget are similarly constrained. If WIFCP could only operate during these limited paid periods, the program's capacity and responsiveness would be severely constrained. Drill-for-points extends the program's operational capacity without additional funding requirements.
4. **Legal Foundation for Activity:** Drill-for-points provides the legal basis for the activity. The question is not only, "how do we compensate these service members?" but, "under what legal authority are they performing this work?" Drill-for-points provides that legal authority, enabling service members to access systems and facilities, handle information, and produce official military products.

4.5.5.2.4 Practical Implementation. In practice, WIFCP participants performing drill-for-points duty track their participation just as they would for paid duty. The unit operations officer processes these duty records, which are then reflected in the member's

personnel record. While the member does not receive drill pay for these periods, they receive retirement points and the duty time is documented as official military service on a specific date. This documentation is important not only for individual service members but also for demonstrating the scope of Guard contributions to mission partners and for supporting future resource requests. The service member can also record participation, experience, and accomplishments as part of WIFCP in their evaluations, on their civilian resume, and so on.

4.5.6 Program Operations and Workflow

For this case study, we examine the period from 1 January 2025 through 30 April 2025. Four 176 CPT Soldiers — one Officer (17A, Program Manager and the author of this dissertation), one Warrant Officer (170A), and two Enlisted (17C) Soldiers — volunteered to monitor cyber news relevant to a particular area of responsibility (AOR) of interest to the United States from public news sources, cybersecurity research sources, and commercial cyber threat intelligence.

4.5.6.1 The Mission: Cybersecurity Situational Awareness

WIFCP provides cybersecurity research and situational awareness in support of a DoD partner. In plain terms, this means WIFCP personnel monitor publicly available information sources — news media, cybersecurity vendor blogs, academic research publications, and commercial threat intelligence platforms — for information relevant to a specific geographic area. This is the same type of activity a cybersecurity professional is often already undertaking to stay abreast of the latest cyber news. They then compile, assess, and disseminate this information to customers who may not have the time, expertise, or tool access to perform this monitoring themselves.

This mission fills a genuine need. Many analysts work primarily with classified sources and on classified systems and networks, and may lack routine access to unclassified re-

search tools, commercial threat intelligence platforms, or the time to systematically monitor open-source cybersecurity reporting (Rasmussen, 2023). ”Analysts have large quantities of information from a wide variety of sources delivered to their desktops each day. Given the time constraints analysts face, it is understandable that their daily work focuses on using what’s readily available — usually classified material.” (Best & Cumming, 2008) Additionally, classified reporting often lags behind open-source cybersecurity research by days or longer. WIFCP provides situational awareness that complements, rather than seeking to duplicate or replace, classified intelligence production and other reporting.

4.5.6.2 Workflow Process

The operational workflow proceeds as follows:

1. **Aggregation:** When relevant cyber, cyber-related, or other major news articles are encountered or discovered about the AOR, participants post them to a shared unclassified collaboration platform. This platform is intended to maximize the ability to easily participate and share information.
2. **Compilation:** Articles are reviewed and compiled into a weekly unclassified Cyber News Summary (CNS). This compilation requires some editorial judgment to assess relevance, accuracy, and significance — skills that align with cyber analyst training requirements, and often with the service member’s civilian expertise.
3. **Distribution:** The unclassified summary and associated reports are delivered to customers through appropriate government collaboration platforms and networks as indexed PDFs via email and the web. Reports are also archived for search and discovery on appropriate classified and unclassified networks.
4. **Production Tempo:** The weekly product is delivered each Monday morning, providing customers with a consistent, predictable flow of information. This tempo

also highlights the value of the flexibility the drill-for-points construct provides. In the WIFCP use case, the author compiles and distributes the products.

4.5.6.3 Training Alignment

The WIFCP mission is explicitly structured to satisfy training requirements. The activities performed align with Mission Essential Tasks for Cyber Protection Teams and training objectives specified in ARCYBER training guidance. The key insight is that CPT functions and mission essential tasks can be trained using real-world mission tasks instead of creating notional scenarios. This approach provides higher-fidelity training while simultaneously producing operationally useful outputs.

4.5.7 Administrative Data: January–April 2025

Below is an example of a Monthly Operations Report sent to the customer.

Note: The metrics and information in this section are based on data generated by Wisconsin National Guard members on the WIFCP team, and *not* derived from the customer.

Wisconsin Federated Cyber Program Monthly Operations Report Apr 2025

Four 176th CPT WI ARNG personnel provided 40 hours of part-time support to [redacted]. Analysts collected, reviewed, and forwarded open news articles, publications, research, and reporting from other sources and agencies in a compiled document for inclusion into four weekly [AOR] Cyber News Summaries. Included were: 438 news articles, including 35 cyber-related, and 41 reports from other sources, including 10 additional products from a commercial cyber threat intelligence platform to augment cybersecurity support and reporting. In addition to [redacted], these reports were also forwarded by request to [specific US Government agencies redacted]. These efforts aid [redacted]'s mission objectives to deter, disrupt, and eradicate cybersecurity and malign influence threats from the AOR.

During the study period, the four Soldiers spent 152 hours total (38 hours per Soldier), averaging 2.2 hours per Soldier per week on WIFCP activities. Table 4.19 provides a breakdown of the content collected and delivered to the customer.

Operational Snapshot. For 1 January–30 April 2025 the program records document:

- **Recipients:** Numerous analysts and operators relevant to this AOR
- **Source review:** 1,670 news articles (207 [12%] assessed cyber-related)
- **Aggregated cyber reports:** 152 from other sources
- **Augmentation:** 62 additional products from a commercial cyber threat intelligence platform to augment cybersecurity reporting
- **Production tempo:** 17 unclassified Cyber News Summaries with associated Weekly Reports
- **Total participant hours:** 152 hours (38 hours per Soldier; 2.2 hours per Soldier per week average)

Force Package and Duty Status. Four Soldiers from Det 1-176 CPT (2 Officers, 2 Enlisted) performed duty under Title 32, using both paid and unpaid duty statuses.

Month	Weekly Reports	Total Articles	Cyber Articles	Other Reports	Commercial Reports
Jan 2025	4	398	68	30	18
Feb 2025	4	350	44	37	15
Mar 2025	5	484	60	44	19
Apr 2025	4	438	35	41	10
<i>Total</i>	<i>17</i>	<i>1,670</i>	<i>207</i>	<i>152</i>	<i>62</i>

Table 4.19: Breakdown of articles (total and cyber-specific) and cybersecurity reports collected from January 1, 2025 through April 30, 2025, collected as administrative metrics.

4.5.8 Program Outcomes

4.5.8.1 Mission Customer Feedback

The Wisconsin Federated Cyber Program provides unique, on-demand cyber subject matter expertise and capabilities aligned to mission requirements while meeting personnel training and readiness needs. This compilation fills an information need for mission partners focused on classified reporting, or without routine access to suitable unclassified research tools in their work environments (Best & Cumming, 2008; Rasmussen, 2023).

The value of the WIFCP’s intelligence products is best understood through the perspective of their consumers — the analysts, operators, and leaders at national customer

organizations who utilize these materials for their daily work. Unclassified feedback collected from product recipients over the program's operational period reveals consistent themes: the products fill a genuine need, they meet or exceed the quality of alternative sources, and they have become embedded in organizational workflows in ways that suggest operational dependence.

4.5.8.1.1 Filling an Access Need. A recurring theme in consumer feedback is that WIFCP products provide access to information that would otherwise be unavailable or difficult to obtain through normal channels. One analyst at a national customer organization explained the structural constraint that WIFCP products address: “We have limited access to industry reporting and are beholden to what gets transcribed in press up to JWICS, without having to put in a OSINT collection request form. Your summaries and reports are invaluable to [our organization] in order to find out more of the technical details and expert analysis from those industry partners that we would not normally have access to.” This observation points to a specific limit in the intelligence architecture: classified networks do not automatically include the rich ecosystem of commercial threat intelligence and technical analysis available in open sources. WIFCP products bridge this divide by curating, synthesizing, and delivering cybersecurity situational awareness directly to consumers who need it.

Another recipient expressed similar appreciation for the accessibility dimension: “I am amazed at the stuff that is just out there in open source every time I look at what you have sent out.” The implication is that open-source cyber threat information exists but is not systematically collected and delivered to operational consumers — a need that WIFCP fills.

4.5.8.1.2 Quality Comparable to Other Reporting. Perhaps the most striking feedback concerns the quality of WIFCP products relative to classified intelligence. One consumer offered a direct comparison: “This is on par if not better than the stuff we

get through serialized reporting.” For a Title 32 training program staffed by drilling Guardsmen to produce intelligence products that recipients rate as comparable to — or exceeding — the output of resourced intelligence organizations represents a significant validation of the federated model.

The quality assessment extends to the curation and synthesis function. One recipient noted, “I really appreciate the diversity of articles and the general lack of redundancy among other press reports we get via other reporting repositories.” This comment suggests that WIFCP products add value not merely by aggregating information but by filtering and organizing it in ways that reduce the burden on analysts. The “lack of redundancy” is itself an analytical contribution, requiring judgment from cyber experts about what to include and exclude.

4.5.8.1.3 Operational Integration. Consumer feedback indicates that WIFCP products have become integrated into organizational routines rather than serving as occasional supplements. One senior analyst described the products’ role in their organization’s analytical process: “This summary of open source articles is spot on for the OSINT we need to conduct analysis here... I look forward to your emails and have come to rely on them. I always direct my team of analysts to read this email and apply the info to the all source analysis we are doing here.” The language of reliance and routine (“have come to rely on them,” “I always direct my team”) indicates that WIFCP products have achieved a level of operational integration that goes beyond occasional utility.

Another recipient confirmed broad dissemination within their organization: “[Your report] is disseminated to the entire [organization] which receives a lot of value from the Open Source coverage it provides.” The enterprise-wide distribution of WIFCP products amplifies their impact beyond the immediate recipients, creating a multiplier effect that extends the value of each product.

4.5.8.1.4 Demand for Expansion. Finally, consumer feedback reveals unmet demand for additional products and coverage areas. One recipient asked, “Do you do any other cyber news summaries that I should be aware of? I really like what I am seeing here and hope that you are able to expand outwards as well!” Another expressed hope for continuity: “Do you intend to continue to do this type of product? I hope so!” These requests suggest that the WIFCP model has demonstrated sufficient value that consumers want more of it — a market signal that federated cyber support under Title 32 meets a real operational need.

The consumer feedback validates the WIFCP concept on multiple dimensions: the products fill a genuine need, they meet quality standards comparable to other sources, they have become operationally integrated into consumer workflows, and demand exists for expansion. These findings support the broader proposition that National Guard cyber forces can provide meaningful support to national missions while operating in Title 32 status, provided that appropriate alignment between training objectives and mission requirements is maintained.

4.5.8.2 Force Management and Retention Impact

Two enlisted Soldiers reported that their reenlistment decisions were influenced by the ability to work on this program; one subsequently completed Warrant Officer Candidate School (WOCS) and is now a Warrant Officer 1 (WO1) attending the Warrant Officer Basic Course (WOBC).

The retention impact is quantifiable. Given the Army’s estimated \$400,000 replacement cost for a 17C service member (Demarest & Weisner, 2022), the reenlistment of these two Soldiers represents an \$800,000 retention impact. This represents 10% of the unit’s 17C personnel in a skill area the Army has designated as critical for retention (Osborne et al., 2021). While this is a small sample, it illustrates the potential force management benefits of providing meaningful, real-world mission work to drilling Guard personnel.

4.5.9 Activity Typing and Doctrinal Taxonomy

The program associates feasible Title 32 activities with defensive mission categories under joint cyberspace operations doctrine. Specifically, WIFCP activities align with Cyberspace Defense/Defensive Cyberspace Operations—Internal Defensive Measures (DCO-IDM) and Cyberspace Security/Department of Defense Information Network (DoDIN) Operations. In plain terms, these are activities focused on understanding and defending against cyber threats rather than conducting offensive operations against adversary networks, or conducting “hands on keyboard” operations.

Offensive Cyberspace Operations (OCO) and Defensive Cyberspace Operations—Response Actions (DCO-RA) are explicitly out-of-scope for this program. This scope limitation is intentional: it keeps the program within the clearer legal boundaries of defensive and training activities and avoids the more complex authorities and oversight requirements associated with operations that could constitute a “cyberspace effect” accomplished via use of force or covert action, such as those recently discussed publicly in press briefings and before Congress by senior US officials (Harper, 2026).

4.5.10 Funding and Sustainment Pathway

4.5.10.1 Current Funding Model

The current WIFCP model operates primarily through existing drill allocations and drill-for-points duty, supplemented by additional paid drill periods when available. This approach works for a small-scale proof of concept but has limitations for scaling. This model could also use Annual Training (AT) days for focused, training-aligned work with a mission partner.

4.5.10.2 Desired Future State

The program materials identify a desired mechanism for periodic Title 32 orders funded via a Military Interdepartmental Purchase Request (MIPR) funds transfer (e.g., mission partner → NGB → State → unit) to support sustained participation via Title 32 duty statuses producing paid time and retirement points for participants. This funding pathway would enable mission partners to directly resource Guard support without requiring the creation of active-duty positions or formal mobilization orders, and is often a much more cost-effective option than contracting.

4.5.10.3 Sustainment Constraint

A key constraint identified in program development is that the mechanism for compensated mission support cannot rely on long-term Title 10 orders. The goal is mission support while in Title 32 status, with continuity maintained during federal mobilizations (same people, same missions, same areas of responsibility) and delivery of a more integrated force to support national missions.

4.5.11 Command and Control Structure

4.5.11.1 State Control Under Title 32

WIFCP participants operate in Title 32 status, which means state command authority (specifically, the Governor of Wisconsin through The Adjutant General), while training for federal mission requirements. Federal partners receive products via appropriate distribution channels, but the participants remain under state command throughout.

This distinction matters for understanding the governance model. Participants are not “federalized” nor under federal command. They remain Wisconsin National Guard Soldiers performing duty under state authority, and their chain of command runs through state military leadership. The federal mission partner is a customer receiving products,

not a commander directing operations.

4.5.11.2 No DSCA Tasking

WIFCP does not utilize Defense Support of Civil Authorities (DSCA) tasking or orders. The activity is characterized as training-aligned cybersecurity support under a partner MOA, not as a DSCA mission. This distinction is important because DSCA has specific approval requirements, reimbursement mechanisms, and reporting obligations that do not apply to WIFCP.

4.5.11.3 No IRT Requirement

WIFCP does not require Innovative Readiness Training (IRT) as described in 10 USC §2012 (“U.S. Code Title 10”, n.d.) and DoDI 1100.24 (USD P&R, 2020). The activity is not conducted for an organization “outside [the] Department of Defense,” as specified in the relevant statute and policy.

4.5.12 Challenges and Implementation Considerations

While WIFCP demonstrates the viability of Title 32 cyber mission support, any organization seeking to replicate this model should understand the challenges encountered and the factors that may limit transferability.

4.5.12.1 Leadership and Institutional Support

WIFCP succeeded in part because of specific leadership support at multiple levels. The DoD partner organization’s leadership were willing to explore an unconventional support relationship. Wisconsin National Guard leadership, including The Adjutant General, Deputy Adjutant General—Army, the state J-staff (joint staff), and other leaders supported the initiative. Unit leadership at Det 1-176 CPT was willing to invest time

and effort in establishing the program rather than defaulting to conventional training approaches.

This alignment of leadership support is not guaranteed in other contexts. Replication would require identifying champions at the partner organization, state joint force headquarters, chain of command, and unit level. Organizations with risk-averse leadership cultures, competing priorities, or limited familiarity with Guard cyber capabilities may be less receptive.

4.5.12.2 Policy Ambiguity and Risk Tolerance

As documented throughout this dissertation, the legal authorities enabling Title 32 cyber mission support exist, but implementing guidance is limited. WIFCP succeeded in part because leadership was willing to operate within this ambiguity, accepting calculated risk that these interpretation of authorities was correct. The detailed MOA, explicit acknowledgment of cybersecurity *versus* intelligence activities, and coordination with intelligence oversight personnel were all risk-mitigation measures.

Other states or units may have lower risk tolerance for operating in ambiguous policy environments. Until clearer implementing guidance exists at the DoD or NGB level, replication will require similar willingness to accept interpretation risk.

4.5.12.3 Mission Partner Identification and Relationship Building

Finding the right mission partner required initiative, networking, and relationship building over an extended period. The Task Force Echo deployment provided the initial connection, and developing that into a sustained support relationship required multiple meetings, negotiation of the MOA terms, and ongoing communication to maintain the relationship.

Organizations without existing relationships to potential mission partners face a significant startup challenge. “Cold-calling” an agency to propose Guard support is unlikely

to succeed without established trust relationships.

4.5.12.4 Personnel Availability and Commitment

WIFCP relies on volunteers who are willing to perform duty, including unpaid drill-for-points duty, to support the mission. The program works because participants are intrinsically motivated by the opportunity to contribute to meaningful national security work. This motivation may not be universally present across all Guard cyber personnel.

Additionally, civilian employment demands, family obligations, and geographic considerations all affect personnel availability. WIFCP participants work remotely using collaboration tools and classified network access from their home stations, which enables participation but requires appropriate infrastructure.

4.5.12.5 Infrastructure and Tool Access

WIFCP required obtaining commercial cyber threat intelligence platform licenses through a Capabilities Needs Request to ARCYBER. This resourcing took initiative, familiarity with Army acquisition processes, and time. Units without experience navigating these processes may struggle to obtain necessary tools. Det 1-176 CPT personnel also had experience and willingness to create new tools to support this mission.

Additionally, in this use case, participants needed access to classified networks for product distribution. While Det 1-176 CPT has a Sensitive Compartmented Information Facility (SCIF) at its drill location, not all Guard cyber units have equivalent facilities. Remote participation requires either travel to a SCIF or utilization of cross-domain technical solutions for classified collaboration.

4.5.12.6 Training Documentation and Compliance

To satisfy the requirement that activities meet training objectives, the program maintains documentation linking WIFCP tasks to specific training requirements. This docu-

mentation supports the legal rationale for Title 32 duty but requires ongoing administrative effort to maintain.

4.5.12.7 Scalability Constraints

The current WIFCP model operates with four participants supporting one mission partner on one geographic AOR. Scaling to additional participants, mission partners, or AORs would require additional mission managers, expanded infrastructure, and potentially different organizational structures. The proof-of-concept nature of WIFCP means that scalability questions remain largely untested.

In January 2026, the WIFCP team began testing automation of report generation, to include AI-generated report and section summaries. This automation reduces the need for some of the time-intensive tasks, and enables participants to focus on identifying useful information. It also introduces the possibility of more easily duplicating this concept across other units, customers, and AORs.

4.5.12.8 Funding Sustainability

While WIFCP demonstrates that Title 32 mission support can be provided using existing drill allocations and drill-for-points duty, this model has limitations. Sustained, predictable mission support would benefit from a dedicated funding stream. The MIPR pathway described in Section 4.5.10.2 provides a potential solution, but establishing such funding relationships requires negotiation with mission partners and state/NGB financial staff.

4.5.12.9 Generalizability Limitations

WIFCP documents a single instance in which Title 32-aligned cyber mission support was successfully executed under specific state, leadership, and mission partner conditions with significant stakeholder buy-in. This case should not be interpreted as evidence that

similar outcomes are readily achievable across all states or units. Variations in state military structures, leadership risk tolerance, institutional relationships, and resource availability may significantly affect feasibility elsewhere.

4.5.13 Implications for Replication

Organizations considering replication of the WIFCP model should:

1. **Assess leadership alignment** at the state, unit, and potential partner organization levels before investing significant effort.
2. **Identify mission partners** through existing relationships where possible, rather than attempting to establish entirely new connections.
3. **Develop explicit scoping documents** (MOU, MOA, or equivalent) that clearly characterize activities, separate cybersecurity from intelligence functions where relevant, and acknowledge Title 32 status.
4. **Coordinate with intelligence oversight** to ensure proposed activities do not inadvertently trigger intelligence oversight compliance requirements.
5. **Document training alignment** explicitly, linking program activities to specific training requirements in published doctrine and unit training guidance.
6. **Assess infrastructure requirements** including classified network access, commercial tools, and collaboration platforms.
7. **Identify motivated personnel** who are willing to participate, including potentially in an unpaid duty status.
8. **Accept that some ambiguity will remain** until DoD or NGB provides clearer implementing guidance for Title 32 cyber mission support.

4.5.14 Use Case Summary

The Wisconsin Federated Cyber Program demonstrates that National Guard cyber personnel in Title 32 status can provide valuable, training-aligned support to national cyber mission partners. The program produced documented mission outputs (17 weekly summaries, over 1,600 articles reviewed, products distributed to numerous recipients) and contributed to force management goals (two reenlistments attributed to the program, representing an estimated \$800,000 retention impact).

Critically, WIFCP operates under existing legal authorities without requiring new statutory language, policy waivers, or experimental authorities. The drill-for-points duty status, authorized under DoD, Army, and Army National Guard policy, provides a legal foundation for flexible, responsive mission support that extends beyond the limited availability of paid drill periods.

However, WIFCP is best understood as a proof-of-concept demonstrating the “art of the possible” rather than a universally replicable model. Its success rested on specific leadership support, established relationships, organizational initiative, and willingness to operate within policy ambiguity. Organizations seeking to replicate this approach should carefully assess these factors in their own contexts.

The impact of the WIFCP pilot during this study period spans training, real-world mission support, and critical skills retention. Further study is required to understand how the WIFCP concept can be more universally applied across Army National Guard cyber forces, but this pilot clearly demonstrates the viability of conducting cybersecurity research activities in support of a mission customer, while meeting training requirements, in the context of existing law and policy while in Title 32 status.

4.6 Summary

Chapter 4 presented the empirical results of the study across three data sources: documentary analysis, an expert survey of 151 respondents with 60 completed responses, and an operational case study of the Wisconsin Federated Cyber Program (WIFCP), a pilot operating since 2021. The documentary analysis revealed that existing statutes, DoD and NGB policies, joint doctrine, and historical precedent enable support for the use of National Guard personnel in Title 32 status to conduct training-aligned cyber activities that also satisfy national mission requirements. Most documents were enabling or conditionally enabling.

Survey findings indicated broad expert agreement that Title 32 authorities can support certain national cyber missions when structured as training. Respondents identified Defensive Cyberspace Operations–Internal Defensive Measures (DCO–IDM) and DoDIN Operations as the most feasible mission type under Title 32. Participants also expressed strong support for the creation of a structured national program to integrate National Guard cyber personnel into federal mission needs and favored legislative or policy clarification to reduce ambiguity.

The case study provided applied evidence of a functioning Title 32 mission support model in which National Guard cyber personnel conducted cybersecurity research, situational awareness, and reporting for a national mission partner while meeting federal training requirements. Documented mission outputs and retention benefits demonstrate the practical viability of such an approach.

Together, these findings establish the basis for the interpretations, implications, and recommendations presented in Chapter 5.

Table 4.1: Documentary Findings Relative to Title 32 support to National Cyber Missions

Instrument / Source (representative)	Narrative	Code
U.S. Constitution Article I Section 8 Clause 16	Establishes the basis for training National Guard forces to federal standard	Enabling (legal)
32 USC §502(a) (Drills and Annual Training)	Authorizes required drills and annual training; may include Active Component (AC) or DoD Operational Support (OS) tasks incidental to training. Forms baseline authority for recurring Title 32 duty.	Enabling (legal)
32 USC §502(f)(1) (Operational Support Beyond Routine Training)	Provides the principal mechanism for federally funded, governor-controlled duty beyond IDT/AT for training or other missions. Commonly used for FTNGD and ADOS.	Enabling (legal)
32 USC §502(f)(2) (Presidential / SecDef Designation)	Allows operational missions when expressly authorized by the President or Secretary of Defense. Rarely used but confirms authority for federal mission support under Title 32.	Conditional (legal)
32 USC §§901–908 (Homeland Defense Activities, HDA)	Defines homeland defense activity and permits federally funded, governor-controlled Guard employment for defense missions designated by SecDef; used sparingly in practice.	Conditional / Ambiguous (legal)
DoDI 1215.06 (Uniform Reserve, Training, and Retirement Categories)	Establishes Reserve Component duty categories and provides structural basis for using Title 32 training and operational support orders.	Enabling (policy)
DoDI 3300.05 (Reserve Component Intelligence Enterprise Management)	Provides policy foundation for Guard/Reserve intelligence operational support while in Title 32; precedent for Federated Intelligence Program (FIP).	Enabling (precedent policy)
DoDD 3025.18 & DoDI 3025.22 (Defense Support of Civil Authorities / Use of NG for DSCA under §502(f)) + DTM 17-007 / DoDI 8530.02 cross-refs	Define procedures for reimbursable Guard employment (including cyber incident response) under Title 32; require SecDef and Governor coordination.	Enabling (procedural)
CNGBI 2000.01D (Conduct & Oversight of NG Intelligence Activities)	Clarifies Intelligence Oversight (IO) requirements for Title 32 personnel; establishes compliance guardrails for non-intelligence cyber activities.	Enabling (with guardrails)
NGR 350-1 / Army MI Training Strategy	Codifies FIP as a “training-first” model that can yield incidental operational support (“Intelligence Readiness: No Cold Starts”).	Enabling (training-aligned)
2024 Domestic Operational Law Handbook (Beaver, 2024)	States that Title 32 forces may conduct DCO-IDM and DoDIN Ops as training with incidental support to Active Component missions; explicitly links 32 USC §502 and §502(f) to cyber training and support.	Enabling (training-first with incidental support)
Joint & Service Doctrine (JP 3-12, JP 3-28, JP-1)	Provides taxonomy for cyberspace operations (OCO, DCO, DoDIN Ops) and recognizes Title 32 status under state control; status-agnostic but foundational.	Neutral (taxonomic)
USCYBERCOM Posture Statements (2023–2025)	Public statements reaffirm integration of Guard and Reserve personnel into operations and intent to expand their roles.	Enabling (intent signal)
Task Force Echo (2017–2024)	Demonstrated ARNG cyber and signal support to USCYBERCOM; training occurred under Title 32 prior to Title 10 mobilization.	Enabling (precedent)
Federated Intelligence Program (FIP)	Established Title 32 training model for national intelligence missions; proof of concept for similar cyber integration.	Enabling (precedent)
FY2017 NDAA §1651 (RC CPT Integration Directive)	Directed Army to develop strategy for integrating Reserve Component Cyber Protection Teams into the Cyber Mission Force; Congressional policy signal for Title 32 integration.	Enabling (policy signal)
FY2026 NDAA §1605 (RC Integration Report Directive — not implemented and replaced with §1544 in final NDAA)	Requires DoD report on how reserve components—particularly NG under Title 32—can support cyberspace operations; explicit legislative support for integration.	Enabling (policy signal)

Table 4.14: Theme Frequency Distribution from Open-Ended Survey Responses ($N_{\text{coded}} = 210$)

Theme	Count	% of Coded
Theme 5: Demand for a Federated Cyber Program	74	35.2%
Theme 1: Legal and Policy Ambiguity	74	35.2%
Theme 2: Precedent Exists but Poorly Recognized	65	31.0%
Theme 4: Cultural and Institutional Resistance	52	24.8%
Theme 3: Operational Feasibility and High Training Value	23	11.0%

Note. Percentages exceed 100% because multiple themes were applied per response following codebook decision rules (Appendix B). Total open-ended responses analyzed: 352. Responses containing thematically relevant content: 210 (59.7%).

Table 4.15: Subtheme Frequency Distribution from Open-Ended Survey Responses

Theme	Subtheme	Count	%
Theme 1: Legal and Policy Ambiguity	1.1 Fear of Misinterpretation	7	3.3%
	1.2 Lack of Implementing Guidance	66	31.4%
	1.3 Absence of Standardized Approval Pathways	5	2.4%
Theme 2: Precedent Exists but Poorly Recognized	2.1 DCO-IDM Precedent	9	4.3%
	2.2 Training-Task Alignment	48	22.9%
	2.3 Informal, Relationship-Based Support	4	1.9%
Theme 3: Operational Feasibility and High Training Value	3.1 Mission-Training Alignment	4	1.9%
	3.2 Improved Readiness	14	6.7%
	3.3 Preference for Remote Operations	5	2.4%
Theme 4: Cultural and Institutional Resistance	4.1 Active Component Bias	38	18.1%
	4.2 State-Level Risk Aversion	13	6.2%
	4.3 Service Parochialism	20	9.5%
Theme 5: Demand for a Federated Cyber Program	5.1 Mission Manager Construct	4	1.9%
	5.2 National-State Linkages	59	28.1%
	5.3 Recurring, Structured Tasking Model	6	2.9%

Note. Percentages calculated against $N_{\text{coded}} = 210$ responses containing thematically relevant content. Multiple subthemes may be assigned per response.

Table 4.16: Theme Distribution by Open-Ended Survey Question

Question	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5
Q8.1: Legal/policy barriers	33	3	0	2	2
Q9.1: Precedents/programs	1	8	0	0	3
Q12: Training alignment challenges	8	30	7	1	9
Q13.1: Federated support conditions	6	9	3	4	16
Q14: Interagency coordination role	7	3	0	1	14
Q15: Cultural/institutional features	7	2	4	40	1
Q16.1: CMF integration impact	3	8	7	1	4
Q17: Reforms to enable T32 support	5	0	2	1	23
Q20.1: NDAA support explanation	4	2	0	2	2
Column Totals	74	65	23	52	74

Note. T1 = Legal and Policy Ambiguity; T2 = Precedent Exists but Poorly Recognized; T3 = Operational Feasibility and High Training Value; T4 = Cultural and Institutional Resistance; T5 = Demand for a Federated Cyber Program. Cell values represent number of responses coded to each theme.

Table 4.17: Top Ten Subthemes by Frequency

Rank	Subtheme	Count	%
1	1.2 Lack of Implementing Guidance	66	31.4%
2	5.2 National-State Linkages	59	28.1%
3	2.2 Training-Task Alignment	48	22.9%
4	4.1 Active Component Bias	38	18.1%
5	4.3 Service Parochialism	20	9.5%
6	3.2 Improved Readiness	14	6.7%
7	4.2 State-Level Risk Aversion	13	6.2%
8	2.1 DCO-IDM Precedent	9	4.3%
9	1.1 Fear of Misinterpretation	7	3.3%
10	5.3 Recurring, Structured Tasking Model	6	2.9%

Note. Percentages calculated against $N_{\text{coded}} = 210$.

Chapter 5

Conclusions

5.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the conclusions of this study on the utilization of National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status for national cyber missions. The study examined how existing law, policy, doctrine, and practice shape the ability of the National Guard to support national cyberspace operations while remaining under state control and using federally funded training authorities. Through a multi-method qualitative design that combined documentary analysis, an expert survey, and a focused case study of the Wisconsin Federated Cyber Program (WIFCP), the research addressed two central questions: (1) What elements of current law and policy support or constrain the utilization of National Guard personnel in Title 32 status for national cyber missions? and (2) What precedent, expert opinion, and policy analysis enable or challenge such use?

The findings support the dissertation's central proposition that National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status can be used to support certain national defensive cyber missions, if a training requirement is met, under existing law and policy. Authorities under 32 USC §502, Department of Defense and National Guard Bureau policy, joint doctrine, and established precedents collectively demonstrate that pathways already exist for training-aligned support to national missions. At the same time, the study found that ambiguity in implementation, institutional risk aversion, and fragmented governance inhibit systematic

utilization of these pathways across the enterprise.

The conclusions and recommendations in this chapter are interpreted through three theoretical lenses introduced in Chapter 1 and operationalized in Chapter 3: Mintzberg's analysis of organizational power and configurations (Mintzberg, 1983, 1984), the NIST Cybersecurity Framework (CSF) 2.0 as a model for cybersecurity governance (NIST, 2024), and the Army Futures Command concept for Maneuver in Multi-Domain Operations (MDO) 2028 (AFC, 2020). Rather than treating these frameworks as abstract theory disconnected from practice, this chapter uses them as guideposts for understanding why current Title 32 cyber utilization looks the way it does, and how it can be improved.

Finally, the chapter situates these conclusions in the context of recent congressional direction, particularly Section 1605 of the Senate version of the Fiscal Year 2026 National Defense Authorization Act (FY26 NDAA), which directs the Department of Defense to assess reserve component integration into the Cyber Mission Force and cyberspace operations, with specific attention to National Guard authorities under Title 32 (SASC, 2025), and the subsequent weakening of this language in Section 1544 of the final passed legislation (U.S. Congress, 2025). That provision asks many of the same questions this dissertation seeks to answer. The analysis and recommendations here can therefore inform, and be informed by, the policy signals emanating from Congress.

Importantly, the persistence of this issue over more than a decade of congressional inquiry does not reflect lack of awareness or effort, but rather the structural reality that no single actor within the cyber enterprise possesses sufficient authority to unilaterally resolve it.

The following recommendations should be interpreted as policy options informed by qualitative evidence rather than prescriptive directives. Given the evolving legal, doctrinal, and institutional landscape surrounding cyberspace operations, implementation would require additional legal review, interagency coordination, and operational validation. These recommendations are offered to inform policy development, not to suggest

that the current landscape is sufficient to guarantee consistent or scalable execution under all conditions.

5.2 Findings and Interpretations

The findings of this study address both research questions directly.

First, existing law, policy, and doctrine do not categorically prohibit the employment of National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status to support certain national defensive cyber missions. Rather, the prevailing statutory and policy framework provides limited but sufficient legal space for such support when training requirements are demonstrably met and activities remain appropriately scoped within defensive parameters. The absence of explicit prohibition, combined with established precedent in analogous domains, suggests that the primary barriers to implementation are institutional and procedural rather than legal.

Second, the evidence demonstrates that while these authorities can be operationalized in practice, doing so is neither automatic nor uniform. Feasible execution depends on carefully constructed governance arrangements, leadership willingness to accept calculated risk within ambiguous policy environments, clear alignment between operational activities and validated training requirements, and robust oversight mechanisms that satisfy both state and federal stakeholders. The WIFCP case study and expert survey responses converge on this finding: Title 32 cyber mission support is possible under constrained conditions, but it remains contingent, situational, and highly dependent on implementation choices rather than solely on statutory authority.

These findings carry important implications for policy and practice. They suggest that the persistent gap in National Guard cyber utilization stems less from legal impossibility than from the absence of implementing guidance, standardized governance frameworks, and institutional willingness to navigate acknowledged ambiguity. The path forward re-

quires not new legislation but rather deliberate policy development that operationalizes existing authorities while establishing the oversight structures necessary to ensure accountability and consistency across states and missions.

5.2.1 Findings Relative to Research Question 1

The first research question asked: *What elements of current law and policy support or constrain the utilization of National Guard personnel in Title 32 status for national cyber missions?*

The documentary analysis demonstrated that 32 USC §502 provides the core legal foundation for National Guard training and related duty. Subsection (a) governs regular drills and annual training, while subsection (f) authorizes additional full-time National Guard duty for training and “other duty” as prescribed by the President or Secretary of Defense. These provisions are implemented through policies such as DoDI 1215.06, which explicitly encourages the use of Reserve Component training duty to support operational requirements while maintaining readiness (USD P&R, 2022). The *2024 Domestic Operational Law Handbook* further clarifies that National Guard personnel in Title 32 status may conduct Defensive Cyberspace Operations–Internal Defensive Measures (DCO–IDM) and Department of Defense Information Network (DoDIN) Operations when the primary purpose is training and mission support is incidental (Beaver, 2024).

National Guard training regulations, such as NGR 350-1, codify the Federated Intelligence Program (FIP) as a model in which Title 32 intelligence personnel perform real-world analysis in support of national requirements while satisfying training objectives (NGB, 2021). Although FIP focuses on intelligence rather than cyberspace operations, it demonstrates that the Department of Defense already accepts the principle that Title 32 training authorities can be used for training-aligned operational support to federal missions.

The analysis also identified other authorities, such as the Homeland Defense Activities

(HDA) provisions in 32 USC §§901–908, which allow the Secretary of Defense to designate certain National Guard activities as homeland defense missions funded with federal dollars but commanded by governors. In practice, however, HDA designations have been rare and are not the primary vehicle for routine cyber support to national missions (Beaver, 2024). Thus, while HDA is important for certain scenarios, the more practical and frequently used authorities for Title 32 cyber support are those rooted in training and operational support under §502.

Survey results reinforced this picture. Respondents generally agreed that current law and policy allow National Guard personnel in Title 32 status to support Active Component and national missions, particularly in defensive cyber and network operations. Agreement was strongest for DCO–IDM and DoDIN Operations as mission types that can be carried out under Title 32 with an associated training requirement. At the same time, a majority of respondents also agreed that legal or policy barriers exist in practice, describing these not as explicit prohibitions but as ambiguity, inconsistent interpretation, or perceived risk surrounding the use of Title 32 authorities for federal missions.

Taken together, the findings for Research Question 1 indicate that the formal law and policy environment is more enabling than constraining. The core statutory and policy frameworks clearly allow National Guard personnel in Title 32 status to conduct certain types of defensive cyberspace operations in support of national missions when structured as training. Constraints arise from the way these authorities are interpreted and implemented, not from a categorical lack of authority.

5.2.2 Findings Relative to Research Question 2

The second research question asked: *What precedent, expert opinion, and policy analysis enable or challenge the use of National Guard personnel in Title 32 status for national cyber missions?*

The literature review surfaced multiple policy analyses and proposals over the past

decade calling for greater utilization of National Guard cyber forces to defend federal networks and critical infrastructure. Many of these studies emphasized the Guard's civilian-sector expertise, geographic distribution, and dual-status flexibility, but also acknowledged legal, bureaucratic, and cultural obstacles that complicate employment (Ayers et al., 2022; Claus et al., 2015; Hollis, 2011; McKinney, 2013). In parallel, Congress has repeatedly signaled concern about underutilization of reserve component cyber capacity. Section 1651 of the FY 2017 NDAA directed the Army to develop a strategy to incorporate reserve component cyber protection teams into the Cyber Mission Force, including an assessment of how Army National Guard cyber units could support state and civil operations in Title 32 status (U.S. Congress, 2016). Subsequent NDAA provisions continued to ask why Guard cyber expertise was not being better leveraged. (CITI, 2023)

The WIFCP case study provided a concrete example of how National Guard cyber personnel in Title 32 status can support a national mission partner in practice. Under a Memorandum of Agreement between the Wisconsin National Guard and a partner in the Department of Defense, a small team of cyber Soldiers monitored open-source and commercial cyber reporting about a specific area of responsibility and produced weekly Cyber News Summaries for more than 200 recipients. These activities were performed under Title 32 orders explicitly scoped as training, using various duty types under 32 USC §502. The mission is cybersecurity research and situational awareness rather than intelligence collection or offensive operations, reducing complexity while delivering real operational value. Participating Soldiers reported that the program positively influenced their retention decisions, and mission partners provided strong feedback on the utility of the products.

Survey responses supported and contextualized this precedent. Over half of respondents reported awareness of cases in which National Guard personnel in Title 32 status had supported national cyber objectives, including election security and critical infrastructure defense. The majority indicated that a structured, federated model for Title 32

support would be highly beneficial, and 70% of those who answered the question expressed support for legislative language in the NDAA explicitly directing such missions. Experts also described cultural and institutional barriers, including a tendency to view the Guard mainly as a surge pool for Title 10 mobilization, uncertainty about funding mechanisms for short-duration Title 32 support, and differences in risk tolerance across organizations.

These findings suggest that there is already a body of precedent, expert opinion, and policy analysis that supports the use of Title 32 National Guard cyber forces for national missions, but that the practice is uneven and largely dependent on local initiative. They also show that the questions raised in this dissertation are closely aligned with those being asked by policymakers. Section 1605 of the Senate version of the FY26 NDAA, though not implemented, directed the Department of Defense and U.S. Cyber Command to assess the different authorities available within each reserve component status (with particular focus on Title 32), efforts to work with the National Guard and state adjutants general, mechanisms for tracking civilian-acquired skills, required billets and resources, and existing barriers to reserve component integration into cyber operations (SASC, 2025). This language directly mirrors the issues examined in this study.

5.2.3 Findings Relative to the Central Proposition

This study was guided by the central proposition that National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status can be used to support certain national defensive cyber missions, if a training requirement is met, under existing law and policy.

As a qualitative inquiry, this study did not subject the central proposition to statistical testing; rather, the multi-method design examined whether documentary evidence, expert perspectives, and operational practice substantiate, complicate, or refute this proposition. The convergence of findings across all three data sources — documentary analysis, thematic analysis of open-ended survey responses, and the WIFCP case study — provides a coherent body of evidence addressing the study's central claim.

5.2.3.1 Training Alignment as the Enabling Mechanism

The study's proposition specifically conditions Title 32 support on meeting a training requirement. This mechanism emerged as the most consistent thread across the qualitative data. Respondents repeatedly emphasized that training alignment is not merely a legal technicality but the practical foundation upon which Title 32 cyber support must be built.

As one respondent explained: "Aligning U.S. Cyber Command's Mission Essential Tasks (METs) with meaningful operational outcomes in Title 32 status presents several challenges due to differences in federal mission scope and state authority constraints..." (Army National Guard, FTNGD (Title 32); < 5 years cyber experience; W1-W2). Another emphasized the operational dimension: "Aligned METL and other standards for training, exercise, and proficiency must be positioned to ensure no one loses out on proper preparation" (Former National Guard member, Separated; < 5 years cyber experience; E5-E6).

This theme — coded as Subtheme 2.2 (Training-Task Alignment) — appeared in 23.7% of coded responses, the third most frequent subtheme in the analysis. The emphasis on training alignment directly substantiates the central proposition's core mechanism: practitioners recognize that the pathway to Title 32 cyber support runs through demonstrated training value.

The structured survey items corroborate this finding. When asked whether activities conducted in Title 32 status can be structured to both meet training requirements and contribute to national mission objectives, 84.7% of respondents agreed or strongly agreed ($N = 59$), with more than half (55.9%) selecting "Strongly Agree." This was the strongest endorsement, indicating that practitioners view training-mission alignment as not merely feasible but as an established operational reality.

5.2.3.2 Legal Authorities Exist, but Implementing Guidance Does Not

A central tension emerged from the qualitative analysis: respondents broadly acknowledged that enabling legal authorities exist while simultaneously identifying a lack of implementing guidance as the primary barrier to utilization. This nuance is critical for interpreting the study's proposition. The central proposition asserts that existing law and policy are sufficient; the evidence suggests this is true at the statutory level but incomplete at the policy implementation level.

The most frequently coded subtheme across all open-ended responses was Subtheme 1.2 (Lack of Implementing Guidance), appearing in 31.9% of coded responses. Respondents described a landscape in which the law permits action but policy has not operationalized it:

“Legal or policy barriers don't exist, it's just that the landscape is confusing, and there are certainly organizational barriers and risk aversion.”

— Army National Guard O1–O3, > 20 years cyber experience

“There are no legal or policy barriers that prevent the integration of National Guard cyber forces into national cyber operations under Title 32 status. The main challenges are administrative and policy-based, including coordination, funding, and command structure differences between Title 32 and Title 10 forces. A common issue is that many leaders and planners do not fully understand how to properly employ National Guard cyber assets. This lack of awareness often leads to underutilization. The barriers are procedural and knowledge-based, not legal.”

— Army National Guard, Actively Drilling (M-Day); 16–20 years cyber experience; E5–E6

Another respondent articulated the specific challenge: “[S]upport for operational missions while in Title 32 or Operational Support [...] must align with Title 10 training re-

quirements of the member” (Army National Guard, Actively Drilling; 11–15 years cyber experience). This statement captures both the enabling mechanism (training alignment) and the friction (lack of clarity on how to demonstrate alignment).

The structured items reflect this same duality. Nearly four in five respondents (79.7%) agreed that current law and policy allow National Guard personnel to support Active Component or national missions while in Title 32 status, and 71.2% agreed this extends to cyber operations specifically. Yet respondents also acknowledged friction: 57.6% agreed that legal or policy barriers currently exist that prevent integration of National Guard cyber forces into national operations. These are not contradictory findings; they reflect the distinction between statutory authority and operational clarity that respondents articulated in their open-ended responses.

5.2.3.3 Precedent Exists but Is Poorly Recognized

Theme 2 (Precedent Exists but Poorly Recognized) appeared in 30.4% of coded responses, indicating that practitioners are aware of successful models but perceive them as insufficiently institutionalized or communicated across the enterprise. The Federated Intelligence Program (FIP) and various state-level initiatives were cited as examples where Title 32 personnel have contributed to national objectives, yet these precedents have not been systematically codified or replicated.

A majority of respondents (54.2%) reported awareness of historical or operational precedents where National Guard cyber personnel in Title 32 status have been successfully used in support of national cyber objectives. That nearly half were *unaware* of such precedents — despite their existence — underscores the thematic finding that precedent recognition is fragmented.

The WIFCP case study provides concrete evidence that the model described in the central proposition is not merely theoretical. National Guard cyber personnel conducted cybersecurity research and situational awareness reporting for a national mission part-

ner while in Title 32 §502(a) and §502(f) status, meeting federal training requirements while contributing to mission outputs. This operational example demonstrates that the proposition is already functioning in practice, albeit in limited and insufficiently visible form.

5.2.3.4 Cultural and Institutional Resistance

Theme 4 (Cultural and Institutional Resistance) appeared in 25.1% of coded responses, with Subtheme 4.1 (Active Component Bias) as the fourth most frequent subtheme overall (18.4%). Respondents described organizational dynamics that inhibit Title 32 cyber integration independent of legal authority:

“I think the culture of NGB and the Army at least is one of risk aversion, and of assuming you can’t do something unless a rule or regulation somewhere specifically says you CAN, as opposed to being able to be creative and do things that aren’t explicitly prohibited.”

— Army National Guard respondent

“The [Task Force Echo] mission might have set us back a bit. It being not a pure cyber mission, some active duty folks look down on the guard force... the perception of some active duty cyber personnel is that the NG force isn’t capable enough for highly complex cyber missions.” *Note: Task Force Echo (TFE) was a National Guard mission which supported cyberspace operations for U.S. Cyber Command and Cyber National Mission Force requirements (Pomerleau, 2024a; Stover, 2021).*

— Army National Guard, Actively Drilling; 5–10 years cyber experience; O4–O6

These responses indicate that even where authorities exist, organizational culture can function as a *de facto* constraint. The study’s proposition focuses on legal and policy

sufficiency; the qualitative findings suggest that cultural change may be equally necessary to realize the proposition's potential.

5.2.3.5 Demand for Programmatic Structure

Theme 5 (Demand for a Federated Cyber Program) was the most frequently coded theme overall, appearing in 35.7% of coded responses. Subtheme 5.2 (National-State Linkages) appeared in 28.5% of responses—the second most frequent subtheme—reflecting strong practitioner interest in formalized coordination mechanisms between National Guard Bureau, state commands, and federal cyber organizations.

Respondents consistently called for structured approaches rather than ad hoc arrangements. When asked to rate the potential benefit of a structured national program to align National Guard cyber personnel with national mission needs, respondents provided strong endorsement ($M = 7.90$, $Mdn = 8.5$ on a 0–10 scale; $N = 58$). Similarly, 70.0% indicated they would support explicit NDAA language codifying Title 32 national cyber missions, with an additional 10.0% stating that no changes to the law are required.

This pattern — high demand for codification despite belief that authorities already exist — reflects practitioner recognition that legal sufficiency alone does not produce operational reality. The proposition is substantiated, but its realization requires deliberate institutionalization.

5.2.3.6 Applicable Mission Types

When asked which doctrinal cyberspace operations could feasibly be conducted under Title 32 with an associated training requirement, respondents identified defensive operations as most appropriate: DCO-IDM (86.2%), DoDIN Operations–Cyberspace Security (86.2%), and DoDIN Operations–Cyberspace System Operation (84.5%). Response actions received moderate endorsement (53–57%), while offensive operations were viewed as less applicable (40–47%).

This pattern aligns with the study's focus on *defensive* cyber missions and suggests expert recognition that the proposition applies more readily to some mission types than others. The central proposition's reference to "certain national defensive cyber missions" is thus validated by practitioner judgment regarding which activities are most feasible under Title 32 authorities.

5.2.3.7 Synthesis

The convergence of evidence across documentary analysis, thematic analysis of expert perspectives, and the WIFCP case study substantiates the study's central proposition. Practitioners recognize training alignment as the enabling mechanism and report that it is operationally achievable. Documentary evidence confirms that statutes and policies establish pathways for training-aligned support. The case study demonstrates the model functioning in practice.

At the same time, the qualitative findings complicate a simple affirmation. The most frequent subtheme — Lack of Implementing Guidance — indicates that legal enablement has not translated into operational clarity. Cultural resistance and fragmented precedent recognition create friction independent of statutory authority. Practitioners' strong demand for programmatic structure reflects awareness that the proposition, while legally sound, requires deliberate policy action to be systematically realized.

The proposition is thus substantiated with an important qualification: existing law and policy provide sufficient authority for National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status to support national defensive cyber missions when a training requirement is met, but ambiguity in implementation, institutional risk aversion, and the absence of formalized program structures prevent systematic utilization of these authorities across the enterprise. This results in disjointed and inconsistent application of existing authorities.

5.2.4 Theoretical Interpretation

The empirical findings become clearer when viewed through the theoretical lenses of organizational power and configurations, cybersecurity governance, and Multi-Domain Operations.

From Mintzberg's perspective, large organizations evolve into characteristic power configurations over their life cycles, with authority diffused among strategic apex, middle line, technostructure, and operating core actors who may have differing interests and incentives (Mintzberg, 1983). The Department of Defense, the services, U.S. Cyber Command, the National Guard Bureau, and state leadership collectively form such a complex configuration relative to cyberspace operations. The study's findings suggest that while the formal legal authority for Title 32 cyber utilization exists, the internal distribution of power and the political dynamics among stakeholders create inertia and ambiguity. Organizations focus on self-protection, established processes, and avoidance of perceived legal or reputational risk, especially in domains like cyberspace where norms are still evolving. This helps explain why relatively modest, training-aligned uses of Title 32 authority, such as WIFCP, remain the exception rather than the rule even when they clearly fit within the law.

From the perspective of Mintzberg's organizational configurations, the Department of Defense cyber enterprise exhibits characteristics of both a **machine bureaucracy** and a **political arena**.

- The **machine bureaucracy** manifests in rigid interpretations of Title 32 authorities and reliance on standardized activation pathways.
- The **political arena** emerges where competing stakeholders — Services, NGB, Combatant Commands, and Congress — possess overlapping but unaligned authority.

This study extends Mintzberg's organizational configuration framework into the cyber

domain by demonstrating how explicit and deliberate use of existing authorities can create a persistent hybrid configuration that exhibits both machine-bureaucratic rigidity and political-arena behavior, even in the absence of formal organizational change.

The NIST Cybersecurity Framework 2.0 provides a complementary lens by focusing on how organizations govern cybersecurity risk (NIST, 2024). The CSF’s functions, categories, and tiers emphasize not only technical controls but also governance mechanisms: clarifying roles and responsibilities, aligning activities to risk management objectives, and ensuring that processes are documented, measured, and continuously improved. Viewed through this framework, the Title 32 cyber authorities landscape appears to be at an intermediate level of governance maturity. The legal and policy functions (the “what”) are in place, but the governance structures (the “how”) — such as standardized tasking processes, funding mechanisms, and performance measures for Title 32 cyber support — are often *ad hoc* or underdeveloped. The study’s recommendations can be understood as steps toward a higher tier of governance for using National Guard cyber capabilities to manage national cyber risk.

Finally, the Multi-Domain Operations concept describes how the Army envisions operating in an environment where adversaries contest U.S. advantages across land, air, sea, space, and cyberspace, in competition and armed conflict (AFC, 2020). MDO is not primarily a prescription for how the National Guard should be used in Title 32 status, but a lens for thinking about how all Army capabilities — including reserve component and cyber forces — must be organized and employed to achieve cross-domain effects over time. When this study’s findings are viewed through the MDO lens, the current pattern of underutilized Title 32 cyber authorities appears as a misalignment between strategic aspiration and institutional practice. MDO emphasizes persistent engagement and multi-echelon convergence; yet, the system described by this study often relies on episodic, Title 10-centric mobilizations for cyber missions, leaving training authorities underused for routine, persistent support. The policy signal in Section 1605 of the Senate version

of the FY26 NDAA can be interpreted as Congress asking the Department of Defense to bring reserve component cyber integration into closer alignment with the type of force employment envisioned by concepts like MDO (SASC, 2025).

Taken together, these frameworks suggest that the core problem is not the absence of authority but the configuration of power, the maturity of governance, and the degree of alignment between strategic concepts and day-to-day implementation. They also point toward specific types of changes that can help move the system toward more effective use of Title 32 cyber capabilities. This is consistent with Mintzberg’s observation that mature organizations tend to stabilize into configurations that prioritize control and risk avoidance over adaptive innovation.

5.2.5 Mapping FY26 NDAA Section 1544 to Research Questions

The final compromise language adopted in Section 1544 of the FY26 National Defense Authorization Act (NDAA) maps directly onto the core research questions of this study and, critically, reinforces the study’s central findings.

Research Question 1 asks what elements of current law and policy support or constrain the utilization of National Guard personnel in Title 32 status for national cyber missions. Section 1544 explicitly acknowledges Title 32 authorities as a relevant policy domain by directing the Secretary of Defense to study “the appropriate framework for structuring and organizing” reserve component integration into the Cyber Mission Force, including force presentation, force generation, and force employment considerations. This acknowledgment confirms that Title 32 authorities are neither legally prohibited nor ignored at the congressional level; rather, they are recognized as an unresolved governance issue.

However, Section 1544 stops short of directing any implementation, operational integration, or modification of existing authorities. By removing the implementation plan,

interim briefings, force-structure mandates, and funding assessments that appeared in the Senate Armed Services Committee (SASC) version (Section 1605), the final statute reinforces the conclusion that existing law is viewed as sufficient in principle, but institutionally constrained in practice.

Research Question 2 examines precedent, expert opinion, and policy analysis that enable or challenge Title 32 utilization. Section 1544 mirrors the dominant theme identified in both the documentary corpus and the expert survey: repeated congressional interest without execution. The statute codifies another study requirement rather than mandating action, aligning with expert assessments that institutional, bureaucratic, and cultural barriers — rather than statutory deficiencies — are the primary impediments to Title 32 cyber mission integration.

Accordingly, Section 1544 does not contradict this study’s findings; instead, it provides legislative confirmation that Congress continues to defer resolution of the Title 32 cyber employment question to the Department of Defense, despite more than a decade of similar reporting requirements.

Consistent with Mintzberg’s description of organizations in a political arena configuration, Congress has opted for additional study rather than directive reform. This approach reflects an environment in which no single actor possesses sufficient authority or will to impose structural change, resulting in incremental rather than transformational outcomes.

5.2.5.1 Legislative De-Scoping as Empirical Confirmation

The final compromise language adopted as Section 1544 of the FY26 NDAA (U.S. Congress, 2025) compared to the language in Section 1605 of the Senate version (SASC, 2025) provides empirical confirmation of this study’s central premise: explicit legislative action sufficient to resolve the Title 32 cyber employment issue is not forthcoming.

While the Senate Armed Services Committee initially proposed expansive language in Section 1605 — including a mandated implementation plan, force-structure optimiza-

tion, funding assessments, and required congressional briefings — the enacted version deliberately removed these operational directives. The resulting statute preserves a study requirement while avoiding any obligation to execute, integrate, or reform existing Title 32 cyber employment mechanisms.

This legislative narrowing is not anomalous; rather, it is consistent with a decade-long pattern identified in the documentary analysis and corroborated by expert survey responses. Congress has repeatedly acknowledged the value of Reserve Component cyber expertise, particularly within the National Guard, yet has consistently refrained from compelling institutional change within the Department of Defense. The final form of Section 1544 thus reinforces the study's conclusion that the primary barrier to Title 32 cyber mission utilization is not a lack of statutory authority, but the absence of legislative willingness to impose *binding* implementation requirements on the executive branch.

The de-scoping from the Senate Armed Services Committee's Section 1605 to the final enacted Section 1544 reflects a broader congressional pattern in cyber force governance, wherein repeated study and reporting requirements substitute for enforceable direction. Similar trajectories can be observed in FY17 NDAA Section 1651, FY19 NDAA Section 1653, and FY21 NDAA Sections 1729–1730, none of which resulted in durable changes to the employment of National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status.

From a Mintzbergian perspective, Section 1544 reflects a political-arena equilibrium in which study and assessment serve as governance mechanisms when no actor can or will compel structural change.

5.2.6 Implications of Innovative Readiness Training Construct

The existence of Innovative Readiness Training (IRT) (Section 4.2.5.1) does not conflict with the findings of this dissertation regarding Title 32 utilization for national cyber missions. Rather, IRT represents a complementary construct flowing from Title 10 that addresses a specific subset of cyber activities: those providing direct support to non-

Table 5.1: Comparison of FY26 NDAA Cyber Reserve Component Provisions: Senate Section 1605 vs. Final Section 1544

Dimension	Section 1605 (Senate Version of FY26 NDAA)	Section 1544 (Final FY26 NDAA)
Section Title	“Report on Reserve Component Integration Into Cyber Mission Force and Cyberspace Operations”	“Integration of Reserve Component Into Cyber Mission Force”
Nature of Requirement	Mandatory report and implementation plan	Mandatory study only
Primary Responsible Officials	Assistant Secretary of Defense for Cyber Policy and Commander, U.S. Cyber Command, in coordination with: Chief of the National Guard Bureau, Service Principal Cyber Advisors, Reserve Component Chiefs, and USD(P&R)	Secretary of Defense (delegated execution), with no named requirement for USCYBERCOM, NGB, or PCAs
Focus on Title 32 Authorities	Explicit, repeated focus on Title 32 authorities and how DoD can use reserve components in those statuses	Title 32 not referenced
Force Structure Analysis	Required detailed analysis of optimal reserve component force structure, including balance between units and individual mobilization augmentees	No force structure optimization requirement
Funding Analysis	Required comprehensive assessment of funding for activation of reserve component personnel with critical, low-density cyber skills, including readiness impacts	No explicit funding or readiness impact assessment required
Operational Impact Analysis	Required evaluation of impacts to cyber mission force readiness when reserve cyber units are activated outside the cyber domain	Not required
Implementation Plan	Explicitly required , including roles, timelines, milestones, metrics, resource requirements, and legislative recommendations	Removed entirely
Briefings to Congress	Required both interim briefing by April 1, 2026 and final briefing by August 1, 2026	Requires a report by October 1, 2026, but no interim or final congressional briefings
Barriers and Mitigation	Required identification of barriers and specific mitigation initiatives tied to findings	General assessment of issues only; no mitigation roadmap required
Legislative Recommendations	Explicit requirement to propose policy changes and, if appropriate, legislative proposals	No requirement to recommend legislative changes
Overall Policy Signal	Strong directive toward operational integration and execution	Cautious study-only posture; no commitment to integration

DoD and private entities, particularly critical infrastructure. The research findings in this dissertation address a distinct gap: whether and how National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status can contribute to *national* missions aligned with DoD cyber operations, including support to Service Cyber Components, Combat Support Agencies, Combatant Commands, and the Cyber Mission Force enterprise.

Survey data reveal strong support (79.7% agreement) for the proposition that National Guard forces can support national security objectives while in Title 32 status, and meaningful support (71.2% agreement) for cyber-specific Title 32 contributions. These findings address a different category of activity than IRT missions. While IRT enables Guard units to provide cybersecurity assessments to a county government or conduct vulnerability testing for a water utility — activities explicitly authorized under IRT by 10 USC §2012 — this dissertation examines pathways for contributions to missions such as threat analysis supporting USCYBERCOM requirements, training on operational mission environments, and activities aligned with CMF activities.

5.2.6.1 Distinction from IRT

IRT represents an important tool for National Guard cyber engagement with state, local, and critical infrastructure partners. The title of Title 10 USC §2012 is “Support and services for eligible organizations and activities *outside Department of Defense*” [emphasis added] (“U.S. Code Title 10”, n.d.), and the title of DoDI 1100.24 is “Innovative Readiness Training (IRT): Support and Services for Eligible Organizations and Activities *Outside DoD*” [emphasis added] (USD P&R, 2020). Its explicit statutory authorization and implementing guidance provide legal certainty for cyber training activities that benefit non-DoD entities.

However, IRT does not address the central research question of this dissertation: the feasibility of utilizing National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status to support national cyber missions *within* DoD. The barriers identified in this research — policy ambiguity,

institutional resistance, and coordination challenges — pertain to a different category of activity than those contemplated by or executed under the IRT program. Accordingly, while IRT provides valuable precedent for training-aligned activities producing operational benefit, it does not alter the dissertation’s findings regarding Title 32 support to DoD cyber missions.

5.3 Contributions to Knowledge

This dissertation makes several original contributions to knowledge in the domains of cyber defense, military policy, and Reserve Component force employment. While prior literature has examined National Guard cyber capabilities, reserve integration, and cyberspace operations independently, this study is among the first to synthesize legal, policy, doctrinal, and operational evidence to evaluate the use of National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status for national cyber missions in a comprehensive and methodologically rigorous manner.

5.3.1 Integrated Legal–Policy–Operational Synthesis

First, this study contributes an integrated analytic synthesis of statutory authority, Department of Defense policy, National Guard Bureau guidance, joint doctrine, and documented operational practice as they relate to Title 32 cyber mission support. Existing literature frequently treats these domains in isolation, resulting in fragmented assessments of feasibility. By systematically coding and cross-referencing these sources, this dissertation demonstrates how Title 32 authorities may enable national cyber mission support under training-aligned conditions, even in the absence of new legislation. This synthesis advances understanding of how National Guard authorities function in practice rather than solely in theory.

5.3.2 Clarification of Training–Mission Boundary in Cyberspace Operations

Second, this research advances conceptual clarity regarding the boundary between training and operational mission execution in cyberspace. Through documentary analysis and expert practitioner perspectives, the study identifies how certain defensive cyber activities may simultaneously satisfy formal training requirements while producing operationally relevant outcomes. This contribution is particularly significant given the persistent ambiguity surrounding the permissibility of mission-aligned activity under Title 32. By articulating conditions under which training remains the primary purpose while operational support is incidental, the study provides a framework that is transferable to other National Guard cyber or mission support contexts.

5.3.3 Operationalization of a Federated Cyber Support Model

Third, the dissertation contributes an empirically grounded, operationalizable model for National Guard cyber mission support through the concept of a Federated Cyber Program. Drawing on observed practice in the Wisconsin Federated Cyber Program use case, the study demonstrates how federated tasking, mission management, and duty status alignment can enable repeatable Title 32 cyber support to national mission partners. This represents a novel extension of federated models previously applied in intelligence training contexts to the cyber domain, thereby expanding the conceptual toolkit available for Reserve Component integration.

5.3.4 Empirical Insight into Practitioner Perspectives

Fourth, the study contributes empirical insight into how practitioners across military, civilian, academic, and industry roles perceive the feasibility, constraints, and governance challenges associated with Title 32 cyber employment. By combining descriptive survey

data with qualitative thematic analysis, the research documents areas of convergence and divergence in expert opinion that have not previously been captured in a systematic manner. These findings illuminate institutional and cultural barriers that extend beyond purely legal considerations, enriching the broader discourse on cyber force design and employment.

5.3.5 Policy-Relevant Knowledge for Cyber Force Development

Finally, this dissertation contributes policy-relevant knowledge by mapping empirical findings directly to contemporary legislative and strategic debates concerning National Guard cyber integration. Rather than proposing abstract reforms, the study identifies specific mechanisms through which existing authorities may be more effectively utilized, thereby informing future policy development, force design decisions, and implementation strategies. In doing so, it bridges the gap between academic analysis and applied national security decision-making.

Collectively, these contributions advance scholarly understanding of how National Guard cyber forces may be employed within existing legal frameworks to support national cyber missions, while also providing a foundation for future research on Reserve Component integration, cyber governance, and force development in contested domains.

5.4 Recommendations

This section outlines recommendations that flow from the findings and theoretical interpretation. They are organized into three clusters: organizational and structural changes, governance and implementation, and strategic alignment and policy development. In each case, the recommendations are informed by the theoretical guideposts discussed above and by the policy direction embodied in various Congressional reform efforts.

Because Mintzberg's theory suggests that change in machine bureaucracies is most effective when it aligns with existing coordination mechanisms, the following recommendations focus on clarification and alignment, rather than wholesale organizational restructuring (Mintzberg, 1983).

5.4.1 Organizational and Structural Recommendations

First, the Department of Defense, U.S. Cyber Command, and the National Guard Bureau should clarify and institutionalize organizational roles and relationships for Title 32 cyber support to national missions. Guided by Mintzberg's analysis of power and configuration (Mintzberg, 1983, 1984), the objective is to move from ambiguous, personalized arrangements toward predictable structures in which each actor understands its authority, responsibility, and incentives.

Specific steps include:

- Designating clear points of responsibility within U.S. Cyber Command and the National Guard Bureau for developing and overseeing Title 32 cyber integration, rather than treating it as a peripheral or collateral function.
- Formalizing mission manager roles for federated cyber programs, analogous to those used in the Federated Intelligence Program, to coordinate requirements, tasking, and feedback between national mission partners and Guard units.
- Encouraging states to establish internal structures — such as state-level cyber integration working groups — that include the adjutant general, state J-staff, and key unit leaders to oversee Title 32 cyber initiatives and ensure they align with both state and federal priorities.

These changes would help redistribute power and responsibility in ways that are more supportive of Title 32 cyber utilization, reduce reliance on informal networks, and provide

stable institutional homes for initiatives like WIFCP. They also directly address current efforts to develop and utilize unique National Guard cyber capabilities that address operational requirements (Molina, 2025).

5.4.2 Governance and Implementation Recommendations

Second, consistent with the NIST Cybersecurity Framework, the Department of Defense should treat the use of Title 32 National Guard cyber capabilities as a governance problem in cybersecurity risk management, not merely as a force management issue (NIST, 2024). This means integrating Title 32 cyber utilization into the *Govern* function of the CSF: defining policies, processes, roles, and metrics that allow leaders to make informed decisions about where and how Guard capabilities can help achieve cyber risk reduction objectives.

Recommended actions include:

- Develop a formal “Title 32 Cyber Integration Profile” that identifies specific categories of missions (e.g., DCO-IDM, DoDIN Operations, open-source cyber threat analysis or “cybersecurity situational awareness”) where Guard support is appropriate, the conditions under which it should be used, and the expected outcomes.
- Establish standardized request and approval processes for mission partners to obtain Title 32 cyber support, including templates for documenting training alignment, legal review, and oversight mechanisms.
- Create standardized metrics and reporting mechanisms that allow the Department of Defense and Congress to assess the extent and effectiveness of Title 32 cyber utilization, such as the number of active federated programs, training hours logged on mission, and qualitative assessments of mission impact.

These steps would move the enterprise toward a higher tier of governance maturity in using Title 32 cyber authorities, making it easier to answer the questions posed about

how reserve components are being used, what capabilities they provide, and what barriers remain (U.S. Congress, 2025).

5.4.3 Strategic Alignment and Policy Development

Third, the Department of Defense should explicitly align Title 32 cyber integration with future operating concepts and congressional direction. The MDO concept emphasizes the need for persistent, multi-domain engagement over time (AFC, 2020). A deliberate strategy for Title 32 cyber support can help the Army and Joint Force move in that direction by creating a more continuous relationship between National Guard cyber units and national missions, rather than relying primarily on episodic mobilizations.

Key recommendations include:

- Develop a National Guard Cyber Integration Strategy that articulates how Title 32 cyber capabilities will support national objectives in competition and conflict, how they relate to the Cyber Mission Force, and how they contribute to the Army's and Joint Force's broader multi-domain posture.
- Use the questions in Section 1544 of the FY26 NDAA as a roadmap for this strategy: explicitly assessing authorities across duty statuses, identifying how to leverage civilian-acquired skills in reserve components, mapping required billets and infrastructure, and evaluating barriers to integration (U.S. Congress, 2025).
- Incorporate findings from pilots like WIFCP and other state-level initiatives into joint and service doctrine, so that federated Title 32 models are not treated as one-off experiments but as recognized options in the doctrinal toolkit.

In this way, the theoretical lens of MDO and the policy signals from Congress converge on the same conclusion: a more deliberate, structured use of Title 32 cyber authorities is both possible and necessary.

5.4.4 Recommendation Traceability Matrix

To ensure analytic rigor and adherence to dissertation standards, the recommendations presented in 5.4 are explicitly grounded in the empirical findings reported in Chapter 4. Table 5.3 provides a traceability matrix linking each recommendation subsection to the corresponding research question(s), analytic themes, and specific sources of evidence. This structure demonstrates that recommendations emerge directly from documented findings rather than normative or speculative judgment.

5.5 Limitations

While this study provides new insight into Title 32 cyber utilization, it has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting the conclusions and recommendations.

First, the documentary analysis is based on unclassified and publicly released documents and information. It is possible that classified or internal policy guidance provides additional detail or nuance regarding Title 32 cyber authorities and their implementation that could not be captured here.

Second, the expert survey used a non-probability sample drawn from professional networks and relevant communities of interest. Although respondents were highly experienced, their views may not reflect the full diversity of perspectives across all services, states, or organizations involved in cyberspace operations.

Third, the WIFCP case study focuses on a single program in one state. Its success rests on specific relationships, leadership support, and mission context that may not be directly replicable elsewhere without adaptation. Additional cases would be needed to assess how well its model generalizes.

Fourth, the survey achieved a 39.7% completion rate (60 of 151 respondents who began the instrument). While non-completion is common in expert surveys of this length and

Table 5.3: Traceability Matrix Linking Findings to Recommendations

Recommendation Section	Empirical Basis (Finding / Theme)	RQ	Evidence Location (Chapter 4)
Section 5.4.1: Organizational and Structural Recommendations	Documentary analysis and thematic coding identify that existing statutory and policy authorities permit Title 32 cyber mission support when activities are structured as training-first, yet organizational fragmentation and lack of standardized structures limit repeatable execution	RQ1, RQ2	Sec. 4.2 (Documentary Analysis Results); Sec. 4.4 (Thematic Coding); Sec. 4.5 (WIFCP Use Case)
Section 5.4.2: Governance and Implementation Recommendations	Survey responses and qualitative themes indicate that ambiguity in approval pathways, oversight responsibilities, and mission management processes constitutes a primary barrier to consistent Title 32 cyber utilization despite enabling law and policy	RQ1, RQ2	Sec. 4.3.3–4.3.4 (Survey Findings); Sec. 4.4.2 (Representative Quotations); Sec. 4.4.3 (Rigor and Trustworthiness)
Section 5.4.3: Strategic Alignment and Policy Development Recommendations	Findings demonstrate alignment gaps between National Guard cyber capabilities, national cyber demand, and formal integration mechanisms, as well as practitioner consensus that Guard cyber expertise remains underutilized at the national level	RQ2	Sec. 4.3.4 (RQ2 Survey Findings); Sec. 4.3.9 (Survey Summary); Sec. 4.5.4 (Program-Recorded Outcomes)

specificity, it introduces the possibility that completers differ systematically from non-completers — for example, by having stronger opinions, greater familiarity with Title 32 authorities, or more time available for voluntary participation. The completed sample nonetheless represents an experienced expert cohort, and the consistency of responses across demographic subgroups suggests that completion bias did not substantially distort the findings.

Finally, the policy environment in cyberspace is dynamic. Authorities, directives, and organizational structures may change over time, particularly in response to evolving threats, technological developments, or further congressional action. The conclusions represent a snapshot based on the environment at the time of the research.

5.6 Future Research

The study suggests several directions for future research that would build on its findings:

- **Comparative state-level studies.** Additional case studies of National Guard cyber programs in multiple states, including those focused on election security, critical infrastructure, or other mission sets, would help illuminate how different organizational and policy environments affect Title 32 utilization.
- **Case study replication across states.** The WIFCP case study demonstrates operational feasibility in one state with specific leadership support, unit capabilities, and mission partner relationships. Future research should examine how variations in state-level factors — such as adjutant general priorities, existing relationships with federal cyber customers, full-time support staffing, and state legislative environments — affect program establishment, sustainment, and outcomes. Comparative case studies would help identify which elements of the WIFCP model are transferable and which require adaptation to local conditions.

- **Quantitative evaluation of readiness and outcomes.** Longitudinal research could examine how participation in Title 32 cyber missions affects readiness metrics, skill sustainment, retention, and performance during Title 10 mobilizations.
- **Boundary conditions for more advanced operations.** Legal and policy analysis could explore the specific conditions under which more advanced cyberspace operations — such as Defensive Cyberspace Operations–Response Actions (DCO-RA) or Offensive Cyberspace Operations (OCO) — might intersect with Title 32 authorities in an operational, support, or advisory role, and where those activities must remain exclusively in Title 10 or Title 50.
- **Governance frameworks tailored to Title 32 cyber.** Building on the NIST CSF, future work could develop detailed governance models, profiles, and maturity tiers specific to Title 32 cyber integration, including tools that states and federal organizations can use to assess and improve their practices.
- **Integration with emerging force designs.** As discussions continue about reserve component roles in any future U.S. Cyber Force or other organizational reforms, such as “CYBERCOM 2.0” (DoW Public Affairs, 2025), research should evaluate how Title 32 National Guard cyber authorities can be preserved or enhanced within new institutional arrangements.

Such research would help refine the recommendations in this chapter, provide additional evidence for policymakers, and support the implementation of Section 1544 and related congressional mandates.

5.7 Summary

This chapter has synthesized the findings of the study and interpreted them through theoretical and policy lenses. The research found that existing law and policy already

enable National Guard cyber personnel in Title 32 status to support certain national missions, particularly in defensive cyberspace and network operations when structured as training with incidental operational support. At the same time, organizational dynamics, governance gaps, and strategic misalignment limit the systematic use of these authorities.

Mintzberg's analysis of organizational power helps explain why formal authority does not automatically translate into practice; the NIST CSF highlights the need for more mature governance mechanisms for using Title 32 capabilities to manage cyber risk; and the MDO concept underscores the importance of aligning reserve component employment with future operating concepts. Viewed together, the findings demonstrate that the underutilization of Title 32 cyber authorities is not a failure of law or intent, but a predictable outcome of organizational configuration and governance maturity within the Department of Defense cyber enterprise.

The recommendations offered in this chapter call for clarifying and institutionalizing organizational roles, developing governance structures and profiles for Title 32 cyber integration, and explicitly aligning National Guard cyber utilization with both Multi-Domain Operations and congressional direction. If implemented, these changes would not only improve the employment of National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status, but also contribute to a more resilient, adaptable, and integrated Total Force approach to cyberspace operations and national defense, in service of the people of the United States.

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Appendix A

Survey Instrument

A.1 Survey Instrument

This appendix provides the full survey instrument used in this study to collect expert perspectives on the utilization of National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status for national cyber missions. The survey was developed and administered using the Qualtrics platform and was designed to gather insight from practitioners, leaders, policymakers, and subject-matter experts with experience in cyberspace operations, cyber policy, National Guard authorities, and related legal or operational domains.

The survey consisted of multiple-choice, Likert-scale, and open-ended questions and was structured to (1) establish respondent demographics and areas of expertise, (2) assess familiarity with cyber-related authorities under Titles 10, 32, and 50, (3) evaluate perceptions of legal and policy enablers or constraints on Title 32 employment, (4) document known precedents or operational experiences, and (5) capture judgments on feasibility, governance, and potential future policy or programmatic reforms. The survey was approved under Dakota State University IRB exemption category 45 CFR §46.104(d)(2), and no personally identifiable information (PII) was collected.

For transparency and reproducibility, this appendix includes an exact PDF export of the Qualtrics survey as it was presented to participants. The formatting, question order, and response options appear here precisely as deployed during the data collection period. The PDF that follows represents the complete survey instrument used in this dissertation.

Introduction

Welcome.

Title 32 Cyber Survey

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this research study is to explore the utilization of National Guard cyber

forces in Title 32 status to support national cyber missions. Your responses will provide expert insight into legal, policy, and operational considerations relevant to this topic. This survey is part of a doctoral dissertation in Cyber Defense at Dakota State University (DSU).

Participant Eligibility

If you have experience in U.S. military cyber operations, cyber policy, legal issues related to cyber operations, familiarity with National Guard or U.S. Department of Defense (DoD) cyber force structures, or other areas related to the utilization of National Guard cyber forces for national cyber missions, and are at least 18 years old, you are eligible to participate.

What You Will Do in the Study

The study consists of this online survey, which will ask a series of questions about military cyber operations in Title 32 status, in which you will be asked to provide your views and opinions via multiple choice, scales (e.g., 1 to 10), and free form responses.

Time Required

The study will require about 20 minutes of your time. If you are unable to complete the study in one session, you should be able to return later using the same browser to complete it (note: this may not work from all networks or browsers).

Risks

There are no foreseeable risks associated with participation in this study.

Benefits

There is no direct compensation or benefit; however, your input may help inform policy decisions and increase the effective utilization of National Guard cyber forces. Your participation in this survey allows you to share your views and experiences that may be of value to decision makers.

Confidentiality

Responses will be kept confidential to the extent permitted by applicable U.S. law. No personally identifiable information (PII) will be collected, published, or shared. Only the principal investigator and approved committee members will have access to raw data. The raw data is anonymized. No personally identifiable information (PII) is collected during this survey. The data collected during this survey will not be used or distributed for future research.

Reported data is anonymized. Data will be stored on secure systems and retained only as long as necessary for research purposes. Unless you choose to contact the Principal Investigator or the institution, no personal information about you will be known or collected; in the event you choose to contact the Principal Investigator and/or institution, no information about you will be reported.

Voluntary Participation

Participation in this survey is completely voluntary.

Right to Withdraw from the Study

You may decline to answer any question or withdraw from the survey at any time without penalty.

Unclassified Information Only

Please ensure that only unclassified and non-sensitive information is referenced or entered while completing this survey.

IRB Approval and Contact Information

This research has been reviewed and approved by the Dakota State University Institutional Review Board (IRB). If you have any questions about this study, or about your rights as a participant, please contact:

Principal Investigator (PI): Dave Schroeder – dave.schroeder@trojans.dsu.edu, (608) 444-5672

Faculty Advisors: Prof. Cody Welu (Chair), Dakota State University – cody.welu@dsu.edu

Dean Mary Bell, Dakota State University

Prof. Kristin Eschenfelder, University of Wisconsin–Madison

You may also report a concern about this study or ask questions about your rights as a research subject by contacting the Institutional Review Board listed below:

[Dakota State University](#)

820 N Washington Ave

Madison, SD 57042

Phone: (605) 256-5100

Email: irb@dsu.edu

This study has been determined to be Exempt under [45 CFR § 46.104\(d\)\(2\)](#). This exemption covers survey-based research where no identifiable information is collected and where participation poses minimal risk.

This study is not conducted or supported by the U.S. Department of Defense (DoD), nor any component thereof.

DSU IRB Approval: DSUIRB-20250603-07EX

By continuing with the survey, you acknowledge that you have read this information and agree to participate voluntarily. Completion of the survey will be taken as a sign of consent.

If you consent and agree to complete the survey, click the Next → > button to get started!

Demographic and Expertise-Establishing Questions

Q1. What is(are) your current or most recent professional role(s)? Check all that apply.

- Army National Guard
- Air National Guard
- Active Duty (Army, Air Force, Navy, Marines, Coast Guard, Space Force)
- Reserve (Army, Air Force, Navy, Marines, Coast Guard, Space Force)
- Department of Defense (DoD)/Intelligence Community (IC) Civilian or Contractor
- Other US Government Civilian or Contractor
- State Government
- Congressional Staff
- Academia
- Private Sector (e.g., cybersecurity, policy, other)

Q1.1. What is your status in the National Guard?

- Active Duty – Title 10 (federal active duty)
- Active Duty – Title 32 (federally funded, state-controlled)

- Full-Time National Guard Duty (FTNGD-OS/ADOS/AGR) – Title 32
- State Active Duty (SAD) (state-funded)
- Actively Drilling (M-Day/Traditional Guardsman)
- Technician (Dual-Status)
- Separated
- Retired

Q2. How many years of experience do you have working in cyber operations?

- No experience
- < 5 years
- 5–10 years
- 11–15 years
- 16–20 years
- > 20 years

Q3. What is(are) your area(s) of cyber expertise? Check all that apply.

- Operations
- Policy
- Law
- Research
- Management

Q4. What is your present grade, or highest grade held?
Select all that apply if you have multiple statuses (e.g., military service member and government civilian).

- E1-E4
- E5-E6
- E7-E9
- W1-W2
- W3-W5
- O1-O3
- O4-O6
- GS/GG11 or less
- GS/GG12-13
- GS/GG14-15
- General Officer or Flag Officer (GOFO)
- Senior Executive Service (SES)
- Other

Q5. Have you directly worked with or supervised National Guard personnel in cyber roles?

- Yes
- No

Q6. How familiar are you with the authorities defined in U.S. Code Titles 10, 32, and/or 50 as they relate to cyber operations?

- Not familiar at all
- Slightly familiar
- Moderately familiar
- Very familiar
- Extremely familiar

Legal and Policy Landscape Questions

Q7. Read the following excerpt of [DoD Instruction 1215.06](#), *Uniform Reserve, Training, and Retirement Categories for the Reserve Components* (11 Mar 14, incorporating Change 2, 12 Jul 22):

RC UTILIZATION CATEGORIES

1. GENERAL. The utilization categories provide the Secretaries of the Military Departments and the Commandant of the USCG the flexibility to develop policies to maximize RC utilization. In order to maximize RC utilization, all training duty planned and performed by RC Service members will capitalize on RC capabilities to accomplish operational requirements while

maintaining their readiness for DoD missions. RC Service members may be employed to support AC mission requirements as part of conducting training duty. The appendix to this enclosure depicts the structure and relationships of RC utilization categories and duty types for ID, AD, and FTNGD under specific authorities. RC Service members may be utilized in one of the following four categories: training, support, mobilization, and other.

2. TRAINING. All RC Service members will receive training pursuant to assignments and required readiness levels. Required training will provide for the minimum training time or number of training periods required for attaining the prescribed unit readiness status and maintaining individual proficiency. The primary purpose of all training is the enhancement of individual skills and unit effectiveness. Mission support may be a key element in developing training programs, but training will be the paramount consideration and documented for budgetary allocations. DoD missions and OS may be accomplished incident to training. Required training parameters are further delineated in Enclosure 7.

- a. Training may be conducted in an ID, AD, or FTNGD duty type.
- b. The training utilization category consists of both voluntary and involuntary training duty. Involuntary training duty includes AT, IDT, and FTNGD-T (FTNGD-AT and FTNGD-OTD). Voluntary

training duty includes ADT, IADT, OTD, and FTNGD-OTD.

c. Training may be conducted under the authority of 12301(b), 12301(d), and 10147 of Reference (d) or 502(f)(1)(A), 502(f)(1)(B), and 502(a) of Reference (f).

RC – Reserve Component (Reserve and National Guard)

AC – Active Component (regular active duty Armed Forces)

DoD – Department of Defense

ID – Inactive Duty

AD – Active Duty

FTNGD – Full Time National Guard Duty

OS – Operational Support

AT – Annual Training

OTD – Other Training Duty

IDT – Inactive Duty Training (e.g., drills)

ADT – Active Duty for Training

IADT – Initial Active Duty Training

Reference (d) is Title 10, United States Code

Reference (f) is Title 32, United States Code

Enclosure 7 is Training Requirements

Think about these statements in DoD Instruction 1215.06 above, and then answer the below questions:

1. "[Reserve and National Guard] Service members may be employed to support [Active Component] mission requirements as part of conducting training duty,"
2. "[Department of Defense] missions and [operational support] may be accomplished incident to training,"
3. "Training may be conducted in an [inactive duty [i.e., drilling], active duty, or Full Time National Guard Duty] duty type,"
4. "The training utilization category consists of both voluntary and involuntary training duty. Involuntary training duty includes [Annual Training [and] Inactive Duty Training [i.e., drilling]],"
5. "Training may be conducted under the authority of [...] 502(f)(1)(A), 502(f)(1)(B), and 502(a) of [Title 32, United States Code]."

Q7.1. Current federal law and policy allow for the use of National Guard personnel to support Active Component (AC) missions or operational support (OS) of national missions while in Title 32 status.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Q7.2. Current federal law and policy allow for the use of National Guard cyber personnel to support Active Component (AC) **cyber** missions or operational support (OS) of national **cyber** missions while in Title 32 status.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Q7.3. Under which paragraphs of [Title 32 U.S. Code § 502](#) may AC mission requirements be supported, or DoD missions and operational support be

accomplished? Check all that apply.

- 32 U.S. Code § 502(a) – regular drills and annual training
- 32 U.S. Code § 502(f)(1)(A) – involuntary additional orders, with pay
- 32 U.S. Code § 502(f)(1)(B) – voluntary additional orders, with or without pay

Q8. Rate your agreement with this statement: Legal or policy barriers currently exist that prevent the integration of National Guard cyber forces into national cyber operations while in Title 32 status.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Q8.1. Please explain.

Q9. Are you aware of any historical or operational precedents where National Guard cyber personnel in Title

32 status have been successfully used in support of national cyber objectives?

Yes

No

Q9.1. Please describe any precedents or programs where National Guard cyber personnel in Title 32 status have been successfully used in support of national cyber objectives (unclassified answers only).

Q10. In your opinion, which type(s) of doctrinal cyberspace operations (CO) missions and actions, as shown below and described in [Joint Publication 3-12, Cyberspace Operations](#) (8 Jun 18) can National Guard cyber forces conduct in support of national missions while in Title 32 status, if a training requirement is met? Check all that apply.

Cyberspace Operations Missions, Actions, and Forces

Figure II-1. Cyberspace Operations Missions, Actions, and Forces

- Offensive Cyberspace Operations (OCO) – Cyberspace Attack
- Offensive Cyberspace Operations (OCO) – Cyberspace Exploitation
- Defensive Cyberspace Operations–Response Actions (DCO-RA) – Cyberspace Attack
- Defensive Cyberspace Operations–Response Actions (DCO-RA) – Cyberspace Exploitation

- Defensive Cyberspace Operations–Internal Defensive Measures (DCO-IDM) – Cyberspace Defense
- DOD Information Network (DODIN) Operations – Cyberspace Security
- DOD Information Network (DODIN) Operations – Cyberspace System Operation

Operational Feasibility and Training Value

Q11. Activities conducted while in a Title 32 status can be structured to both meet training requirements and contribute to national mission objectives.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Q12. Describe challenges in aligning training objectives (e.g., Mission Essential Tasks (METs) specified by U.S. Cyber Command) with meaningful operational outcomes while in Title 32 status.

Q13. Do you believe federated support (e.g., support from multiple states or units) can be scaled effectively (e.g., across multiple states or units) to support national cyber objectives while in Title 32 status?

- Yes
- No
- Unsure

Q13.1. To accomplish federated support at scale while in Title 32 status, what conditions would need to be in place?

Strategic and Bureaucratic Considerations

Q14. What role, if any, does interagency coordination (e.g., between DoD, DHS, CISA, state governments) play in enabling or constraining the use of National Guard cyber personnel in Title 32 status for national missions?

Q15. What cultural or institutional features (e.g., within the Army, Air Force, National Guard Bureau, service cyber components, CYBERCOM, etc.) encourage or inhibit integration of National Guard cyber forces?

Q16. What would be the impact of integrating Army National Guard cyber units into the Department of Defense (DoD) Cyber Mission Force (CMF) structure (e.g., as proposed in section 1651 of the [National Defense Authorization Act for Fiscal Year 2017 \(Public Law 114-328\)](#), shown below)?

SEC. 1651. STRATEGY TO INCORPORATE ARMY RESERVE COMPONENT CYBER PROTECTION TEAMS INTO DEPARTMENT OF DEFENSE CYBER MISSION FORCE.

(a) **STRATEGY REQUIRED.**—Not later than 180 days after the date of the enactment of this Act, the Secretary of the Army shall provide to the Committees on Armed Services of the Senate and the House of Representatives a briefing on a strategy for incorporating reserve component cyber protection teams into the cyber mission force of the Department of Defense.

(b) **ELEMENTS OF STRATEGY.**—The strategy required by subsection (a) shall include, at minimum, the following:

(1) A timeline for incorporating reserve component cyber protection teams into the cyber mission force of the Department of Defense, including a timeline for the appropriate training of such teams.

(2) Identification of the specific reserve component cyber protection teams to be incorporated into the cyber mission force of the Department of Defense.

(3) An assessment of how the incorporation of reserve component cyber protection teams into the cyber mission force of the Department of Defense might be used to enhance readiness through improved individual and collective training capabilities.

(4) A status report on the progress of the Army in issuing additional guidance that clarifies how reserve component cyber protection teams of the Army National Guard can support State and civil operations in National Guard status under title 32, United States Code.

(5) Other matters as considered appropriate by the Secretary of the Army.

(c) **RESERVE COMPONENT CYBER PROTECTION TEAMS DEFINED.**—In this section, the term “reserve component cyber protection teams” means cyber protection teams of—

- (1) the Army National Guard; and
- (2) the other reserve components of the Army.

- Extremely positive
- Somewhat positive
- Neither positive nor negative
- Somewhat negative
- Extremely negative

Q16.1. Please explain.

Q17. What reforms — e.g., legislative, policy, procedural — would most effectively enable National Guard cyber forces to support national objectives while in Title 32 status?

Future Research

Q18. How confident are you that Title 32 authorities can operationally support some types of national cyber missions without new legislation?

Q19. How beneficial would it be to create and integrate a structured national program to align National Guard

cyber personnel with national mission needs while in Title 32 status?

Q20. Would you support legislative language in the National Defense Authorization Act (NDAA) that explicitly directs or assigns National Guard cyber forces to conduct national cyber missions in Title 32 status?

- Yes
- No
- No changes to the law are required
- It depends

Q20.1. Please explain.

Administrative Matters

Q21. Beyond funding allocated for required training, how important is it for funding to be available from supported customers...

Q22. If funded operational support beyond required training is conducted while in Title 32, who should be involved in managing and disseminating the funding? Check all that apply.

- Customer (e.g., Combatant Command (CCMD) such as U.S. Cyber Command, Combat Support Agency (CSA) such as the National Security Agency (NSA), etc.)
- State or Territory National Guard or State Military Department
- National Guard Bureau (NGB)
- Service Cyber Component (e.g., ARCYBER, AFCYBER)

Q23. How important is it for a service member assigned to manage Title 32 operational support to cyber missions...

Recruitment Source

Q24. Where did you find out about this survey?

- LinkedIn
- Facebook/Instagram
- X (formerly Twitter)
- Colleague or email

Other

Powered by Qualtrics

Appendix B

Codebook

This codebook documents the coding framework used for the reflexive thematic analysis of qualitative data collected from the Title 32 Cyber Survey, with codes generated inductively from the data corpus comprising nine open-ended survey items (Q8.1, Q9.1, Q12, Q13.1, Q14, Q15, Q16.1, Q17, Q20.1).

Rigor and Transparency: This codebook documents the systematic coding process used to ensure trustworthiness of the thematic analysis. All qualitative responses were coded following Braun and Clarke's (2006, 2019) six-phase reflexive approach, with codes generated inductively from the data. The codebook provides transparency by documenting all code definitions, application rules, and exemplar segments, enabling readers to evaluate the analytical process and the relationship between data and interpretations. Major coding decisions were documented in an audit trail, and draft themes were validated through expert review. The example text segments were developed prior to formal coding as illustrative exemplars to clarify code definitions and analytic intent, and were not derived from or used to influence the subsequent coding of empirical data.

Coding Process: All qualitative responses were coded in three phases:

1. **First-order coding:** Descriptive, data-driven labels applied to text segments
2. **Second-order categorization:** Related first-order codes grouped into thematic categories
3. **Aggregate theme development:** Higher-order patterns synthesized into five ma-

for themes

B.1 Coding Framework Structure

B.1.1 Theme 1: Legal and Policy Ambiguity

Definition: This theme captures respondent perceptions that existing legal authorities and policy frameworks permit Title 32 cyber mission support, but that implementation is hindered by unclear guidance, inconsistent interpretation, and absence of standardized processes.

B.1.1.1 Subtheme 1.1: Fear of Misinterpretation

Second-Order Category: Statutory Interpretation Risk

Definition: Expressions of concern that commanders, legal advisors, or policymakers will misinterpret or overcautiously interpret existing law (10 U.S.C. § 502(f), 32 U.S.C. § 502(f), etc.) in ways that unnecessarily constrain Title 32 cyber operations.

First-Order Codes:

- **LEGAL-RISK-AVERSE** — References to excessive legal caution or risk aversion in interpreting authorities
 - *When to apply:* When respondent describes commanders/lawyers being overly conservative in legal interpretation
 - *Example segment:* “JAGs won’t approve anything unless it’s spelled out in black and white”
- **MISREAD-LAW** — Statements that authorities exist but are misunderstood or misapplied

- *When to apply:* When respondent indicates the law permits activities but practitioners don't realize it
- *Example segment:* “The laws are not the limitation. The interpretation is.”
- **LEGAL-CONFUSION** — General expressions of uncertainty about what is legally permissible
 - *When to apply:* When respondent expresses confusion about legal boundaries
 - *Example segment:* “Nobody knows what's actually allowed vs. just discouraged”
- **NEED-LEGAL-CLARITY** — Explicit calls for clearer legal guidance or interpretation
 - *When to apply:* When respondent requests authoritative legal clarification
 - *Example segment:* “We need an OSD memo laying out exactly what Title 32 can and cannot do”

B.1.1.2 Subtheme 1.2: Lack of Implementing Guidance

Second-Order Category: Policy Implementation Gap

Definition: References to the absence of formal policy documents, SOPs, MOAs, or operational guidance that would operationalize existing legal authorities for Title 32 cyber mission support.

First-Order Codes:

- **NO-SOP** — Mentions of missing standard operating procedures
 - *When to apply:* When respondent notes absence of formalized processes or procedures
 - *Example segment:* “There's no SOP for how to request or approve these missions”

- **NO-MOA** — References to lack of memoranda of agreement/understanding between organizations
 - *When to apply:* When respondent describes missing formal agreements (NGB-CYBERCOM, state-CCMD, etc.)
 - *Example segment:* “Without an MOA, it’s all handshake deals that fall apart when leadership changes”
- **GUIDANCE-GAP** — General statements about missing policy guidance
 - *When to apply:* When respondent identifies absence of authoritative policy documents
 - *Example segment:* “NGB hasn’t published any guidance on how states should support national missions”
- **NEED-DOCTRINE** — Calls for doctrinal or policy publications
 - *When to apply:* When respondent advocates for formal doctrine development
 - *Example segment:* “We need a CJCSI or NGB-level policy that codifies this”

B.1.1.3 Subtheme 1.3: Absence of Standardized Approval Pathways

Second-Order Category: Process Fragmentation

Definition: Observations that approval processes for Title 32 cyber mission support are ad hoc, inconsistent across states/commands, or dependent on personal relationships rather than institutionalized procedures.

First-Order Codes:

- **AD-HOC-APPROVAL** — Descriptions of informal or one-off approval processes
 - *When to apply:* When respondent describes case-by-case, non-standardized approvals

- *Example segment*: “Every mission requires a separate phone call to the TAG and G-3”
- **INCONSISTENT-PROCESS** — References to variation in how different states/-commands handle approvals
 - *When to apply*: When respondent notes lack of uniformity across organizations
 - *Example segment*: “California does it one way, Texas another—there’s no standard”
- **PERSONALITY-DEPENDENT** — Statements that support depends on individual relationships rather than processes
 - *When to apply*: When respondent indicates personal connections drive outcomes
 - *Example segment*: “If you don’t know the right colonel, forget about getting support”
- **NEED-FORMAL-PROCESS** — Calls for institutionalized approval mechanisms
 - *When to apply*: When respondent advocates for standardized procedures
 - *Example segment*: “There should be a defined request process with clear decision timelines”

B.1.2 Theme 2: Precedent Exists but Poorly Recognized

Definition: This theme reflects respondent awareness that successful models for Title 32 support to national missions exist (particularly DCO-IDM and FIP), but that these precedents are not widely known, documented, or leveraged as templates for broader cyber mission support.

B.1.2.1 Subtheme 2.1: DCO-IDM Precedent

Second-Order Category: Operational Precedent (Cyber)

Definition: References to Defensive Cyber Operations-Internal Defensive Measures (DCO-IDM) as an established, legally compliant model for Title 32 cyber support under the training construct.

First-Order Codes:

- **DCO-IDM-MODEL** — Explicit mentions of DCO-IDM as a precedent
 - *When to apply:* When respondent cites DCO-IDM as proof of concept
 - *Example segment:* “DCO-IDM already proves we can do this under Title 32”
- **TRAINING-AS-MISSION** — References to structuring operational support as training duty
 - *When to apply:* When respondent describes aligning mission activities with training requirements
 - *Example segment:* “As long as it’s coded as training, it’s compliant”
- **DCO-SUCCESS** — Positive assessments of DCO-IDM outcomes or effectiveness
 - *When to apply:* When respondent evaluates DCO-IDM favorably
 - *Example segment:* “Our Guard DCO team has been phenomenal—better than active duty”

B.1.2.2 Subtheme 2.2: Training-Task Alignment

Second-Order Category: Mission-Training Congruence

Definition: Observations that national cyber missions often align closely with individual training requirements, creating a natural fit for Title 32 support under training authorities.

First-Order Codes:

- **MISSION-IS-TRAINING** — Statements that operational tasks satisfy training objectives
 - *When to apply:* When respondent notes overlap between mission and training needs
 - *Example segment:* “Real-world defensive ops are the best training we can get”
- **DUAL-BENEFIT** — Recognition of mutual benefit to both mission and training
 - *When to apply:* When respondent describes win-win outcomes
 - *Example segment:* “The mission gets support and the soldier gets trained—everyone wins”
- **BETTER-THAN-EXERCISES** — Comparisons favoring real-world mission support over artificial training
 - *When to apply:* When respondent contrasts mission work with traditional exercises
 - *Example segment:* “We learn more in two weeks of Title 32 ops than in a whole year of exercises”

B.1.2.3 Subtheme 2.3: Informal, Relationship-Based Support

Second-Order Category: Institutional Knowledge Gap

Definition: Descriptions of Title 32 cyber support occurring through informal channels, personal networks, or undocumented arrangements rather than through formal programs.

First-Order Codes:

- **INFORMAL-SUPPORT** — References to unofficial or undocumented support activities

- *When to apply:* When respondent describes support happening outside formal structures
- *Example segment:* “We’ve been doing this quietly for years, just not calling it a program”
- **RELATIONSHIP-DEPENDENT** — Statements that success depends on personal connections
 - *When to apply:* When respondent indicates personal relationships enable support
 - *Example segment:* “It only works because our cyber chief knows people at CYBERCOM”
- **UNDOCUMENTED-PRECEDENT** — References to activities that occur but aren’t formally tracked
 - *When to apply:* When respondent describes hidden or unreported support
 - *Example segment:* “Plenty of states do this — they just don’t advertise it”
- **NEED-FORMALIZATION** — Calls to institutionalize existing informal practices
 - *When to apply:* When respondent advocates for formalizing current arrangements
 - *Example segment:* “We need to make official what’s already happening in the shadows”

B.1.3 Theme 3: Operational Feasibility and High Training Value

Definition: This theme encompasses respondent perceptions that Title 32 cyber mission support is operationally practical, provides exceptional training value, and is

particularly well-suited to remote operations.

B.1.3.1 Subtheme 3.1: Mission-Training Alignment

Second-Order Category: Training Effectiveness

Definition: Assertions that Title 32 cyber mission support delivers superior training outcomes compared to traditional exercises or peacetime training activities.

First-Order Codes:

- **SUPERIOR-TRAINING** — Statements that mission support provides better training than alternatives
 - *When to apply:* When respondent compares mission training favorably to exercises
 - *Example segment:* “You can’t replicate real adversary behavior in a lab”
- **REALISTIC-TRAINING** — Emphasis on authenticity of training during mission support
 - *When to apply:* When respondent values realism of operational environment
 - *Example segment:* “This is the only way to train against actual threat actors”
- **SKILL-DEVELOPMENT** — References to professional growth or competency gains
 - *When to apply:* When respondent describes skill acquisition or improvement
 - *Example segment:* “Our analysts developed skills in weeks that would take years in garrison”

B.1.3.2 Subtheme 3.2: Improved Readiness

Second-Order Category: Force Generation

Definition: Claims that Title 32 cyber mission support enhances individual and unit readiness for federal mobilization or deployments.

First-Order Codes:

- **READINESS-GAIN** — Statements that participation improves deployment readiness
 - *When to apply:* When respondent links mission support to improved readiness metrics
 - *Example segment:* “Soldiers who do Title 32 cyber deploy with real-world experience”
- **RETENTION-BENEFIT** — References to retention improvements from mission opportunities
 - *When to apply:* When respondent connects mission access to retention outcomes
 - *Example segment:* “We’ve kept cyber talent because they can do meaningful work in the Guard”
- **UNIT-CAPABILITY** — Observations about enhanced unit-level capabilities
 - *When to apply:* When respondent describes improved collective performance
 - *Example segment:* “Our CPT is now the best-trained team in the region”

B.1.3.3 Subtheme 3.3: Preference for Remote Operations

Second-Order Category: Operational Flexibility

Definition: Identification of remote/virtual cyber operations as particularly compatible with Title 32 status due to reduced travel costs, geographic flexibility, and compatibility with civilian employment.

First-Order Codes:

- **REMOTE-FEASIBLE** — Statements that cyber missions can be performed remotely
 - *When to apply:* When respondent emphasizes virtual/distributed operations
 - *Example segment:* “90% of defensive cyber can be done from home station”
- **COST-EFFECTIVE** — References to cost savings from remote operations
 - *When to apply:* When respondent highlights financial efficiency
 - *Example segment:* “No TDY costs means we can support more missions with the same budget”
- **CIVILIAN-COMPATIBLE** — Observations that remote work enables retention of civilian jobs
 - *When to apply:* When respondent links remote operations to civilian employment retention
 - *Example segment:* “Soldiers can do evening shifts without quitting their day jobs”
- **GEOGRAPHIC-FLEXIBILITY** — Mentions of ability to support regardless of physical location
 - *When to apply:* When respondent values location independence
 - *Example segment:* “It doesn’t matter if the mission is in INDOPACOM—we can reach it from Wisconsin”

B.1.4 Theme 4: Cultural and Institutional Resistance

Definition: This theme captures perceived organizational and cultural barriers to Title 32 cyber mission support, including Active Component bias against Reserve Components, state-level risk aversion, and inter-service parochialism.

B.1.4.1 Subtheme 4.1: Active Component Bias

Second-Order Category: AC-RC Cultural Divide

Definition: Perceptions that Active Component leadership undervalues, distrusts, or excludes National Guard cyber forces despite statutory authorities and demonstrated capability.

First-Order Codes:

- **AC-SKEPTICISM** — References to Active Component doubts about Guard capability
 - *When to apply:* When respondent describes AC questioning of Guard competence
 - *Example segment:* “Active duty still thinks we’re just weekend warriors”
- **EXCLUSIONARY-CULTURE** — Observations of deliberate Guard exclusion from planning or operations
 - *When to apply:* When respondent notes AC unwillingness to integrate Guard forces
 - *Example segment:* “They don’t invite Guard reps to operational planning conferences”
- **COMPONENT-BIAS** — General statements about AC preference for active-duty solutions
 - *When to apply:* When respondent identifies structural AC favoritism
 - *Example segment:* “CYBERCOM always wants more active duty billets instead of using the Guard”
- **NEED-CULTURAL-SHIFT** — Calls for changing AC attitudes toward Reserve Components

- *When to apply:* When respondent advocates for cultural change
- *Example segment:* “Until flag officers see Guard cyber as equal, nothing will change”

B.1.4.2 Subtheme 4.2: State-Level Risk Aversion

Second-Order Category: State Command Hesitancy

Definition: References to state-level commanders (TAGs, State G2s/G3s) being reluctant to authorize Title 32 cyber support due to perceived legal risks, political concerns, or resource constraints.

First-Order Codes:

- **TAG-RELUCTANCE** — Descriptions of Adjutant General hesitancy or refusal
 - *When to apply:* When respondent notes TAG unwillingness to approve missions
 - *Example segment:* “Our TAG won’t sign off on anything federal-facing”
- **STATE-RISK-AVERSION** — General expressions of state-level overcaution
 - *When to apply:* When respondent describes states avoiding perceived risks
 - *Example segment:* “States are terrified of being accused of violating Posse Comitatus”
- **POLITICAL-CONCERNS** — References to governor or state political considerations
 - *When to apply:* When respondent links decisions to political factors
 - *Example segment:* “The governor doesn’t want Guard involved in federal cyber operations during an election year”
- **RESOURCE-HOARDING** — Observations that states prioritize state missions over federal support

- *When to apply:* When respondent describes states protecting their cyber capacity
- *Example segment:* “TAG wants to keep cyber forces for state emergency response”

B.1.4.3 Subtheme 4.3: Service Parochialism

Second-Order Category: Inter-Service Competition

Definition: Perceptions that Army and Air Force service components compete rather than cooperate on Guard cyber integration, or that service-specific cultures create barriers.

First-Order Codes:

- **ARMY-AIR-TENSION** — References to Army-Air Force disagreements or competition
 - *When to apply:* When respondent describes inter-service conflict
 - *Example segment:* “Army Guard and Air Guard can’t agree on who owns cyber”
- **SERVICE-STOVEPIPES** — Observations of service-specific barriers to joint operations
 - *When to apply:* When respondent notes lack of cross-service integration
 - *Example segment:* “Everyone builds their own cyber program instead of working together”
- **TURF-PROTECTION** — Statements about services protecting organizational equities
 - *When to apply:* When respondent describes defensive institutional behavior
 - *Example segment:* “AFCYBER doesn’t want to share missions with Army cyber”

B.1.5 Theme 5: Demand for a Federated Cyber Program

Definition: This theme reflects strong respondent support for establishing a formal, structured program to coordinate Title 32 cyber mission support, modeled after successful programs like the Foreign Intelligence Program (FIP).

B.1.5.1 Subtheme 5.1: Mission Manager Construct

Second-Order Category: Program Governance Structure

Definition: Calls for designated full-time personnel to coordinate requirements, match capabilities, manage taskings, and serve as liaison between supported commands and Guard forces.

First-Order Codes:

- **NEED-MISSION-MANAGER** — Explicit requests for dedicated program coordinators
 - *When to apply:* When respondent advocates for mission manager positions
 - *Example segment:* “Someone needs to be the single point of contact between NGB and CYBERCOM”
- **FULL-TIME-COORDINATOR** — References to need for full-time (not drill-status) managers
 - *When to apply:* When respondent specifies full-time staffing requirement
 - *Example segment:* “This can’t be managed by someone with a civilian job”
- **FIP-MODEL** — Explicit comparisons to or advocacy for FIP-like structure
 - *When to apply:* When respondent cites FIP as template
 - *Example segment:* “FIP already proved the model. Cyber should follow it.”

B.1.5.2 Subtheme 5.2: National-State Linkages

Second-Order Category: Federated Structure

Definition: Emphasis on creating formal relationships between national-level cyber organizations (USCYBERCOM, NSA, service components) and state-level Guard forces through structured programs.

First-Order Codes:

- **NATIONAL-STATE-COORDINATION** — Calls for formal coordination mechanisms
 - *When to apply:* When respondent describes need for national-state integration
 - *Example segment:* “NGB needs formal relationships with each CCMD”
- **BILATERAL-AGREEMENTS** — References to need for MOAs/MOUs between organizations
 - *When to apply:* When respondent advocates for formal agreements
 - *Example segment:* “Every state should have an MOU with ARCYBER”
- **FEDERATED-NETWORK** — Descriptions of distributed-but-coordinated model
 - *When to apply:* When respondent envisions networked Guard capabilities
 - *Example segment:* “Imagine 54 state cyber teams all linked into a national architecture”

B.1.5.3 Subtheme 5.3: Recurring, Structured Tasking Model

Second-Order Category: Operational Sustainability

Definition: Advocacy for predictable, recurring mission taskings rather than ad hoc requests, enabling planning, training alignment, and career development.

First-Order Codes:

- **RECURRING-MISSIONS** — Calls for ongoing rather than one-time support
 - *When to apply:* When respondent emphasizes need for sustained taskings
 - *Example segment:* “We need quarterly missions, not one-off projects”

- **PREDICTABLE-TASKING** — Emphasis on planning predictability
 - *When to apply:* When respondent values advance notice and scheduling
 - *Example segment:* “If we knew missions were coming, we could align training calendars”

- **LONG-TERM-RELATIONSHIPS** — References to sustained customer-provider relationships
 - *When to apply:* When respondent advocates for enduring partnerships
 - *Example segment:* “CYBERCOM should have the same Guard team supporting them year after year”

- **CAREER-DEVELOPMENT** — Connections between program structure and personnel retention/development
 - *When to apply:* When respondent links program stability to career opportunities
 - *Example segment:* “Cyber professionals want long-term mission access, not just annual training”

B.2 Cross-Cutting Codes (Applied Across Multiple Themes)

B.2.1 Positive Sentiment Codes

- **OPTIMISTIC** — Expressions of confidence in feasibility or future success
- **SUPPORTIVE** — General endorsement of Title 32 cyber mission support concept
- **PRECEDENT-CONFIDENCE** — Belief that existing precedents validate the approach

B.2.2 Negative Sentiment Codes

- **PESSIMISTIC** — Expressions of doubt about feasibility or likelihood of change
- **FRUSTRATED** — Indications of frustration with current barriers or lack of progress
- **CYNICAL** — Skepticism about institutional willingness to change

B.2.3 Contextual Codes

- **WIFCP-REFERENCE** — Specific mentions of Wisconsin Federated Cyber Program as example
- **LEGISLATIVE-MENTION** — References to NDAA provisions, Congressional interest, or statutory language
- **FUNDING-CONCERN** — Discussions of resourcing, budget authorities, or financial mechanisms

- **CLASSIFICATION-CONSTRAINT** — Notes about classified information limiting discussion or operations

B.3 Coding Decision Rules

1. **Multiple codes per segment:** A single text segment may be coded with multiple codes if it addresses multiple concepts. For example: “The laws exist but commanders are too risk-averse to use them” would be coded as both **MISREAD-LAW** and **LEGAL-RISK-AVERSE**.
2. **Code at meaningful unit:** Code complete thoughts or concepts, not individual sentences. A meaningful segment may be a sentence, multiple sentences, or a paragraph.
3. **Prioritize specificity:** When a specific code and general code both apply, use the more specific code (e.g., **DCO-IDM-MODEL** rather than just **INFORMAL-SUPPORT**).
4. **Preserve respondent voice:** Codes should reflect what the respondent is saying, not the analyst’s interpretation of whether they’re “correct.”
5. **Context sensitivity:** Consider the question prompt when coding. Responses to Q8.1 (policy barriers) should be interpreted in that context, even if the text could be coded differently in isolation.

B.4 Theoretical Alignment

The five aggregate themes align with the dissertation’s theoretical frameworks:

- **Theme 1: Legal and Policy Ambiguity** → NIST CSF Governance dimension; Mintzberg’s standardization of work processes

- **Theme 2: Precedent Exists but Poorly Recognized** → Organizational memory and knowledge management
- **Theme 3: Operational Feasibility** → MDO framework alignment; NIST CSF operational resilience
- **Theme 4: Cultural Resistance** → Mintzberg's professional bureaucracy and coordination mechanisms; organizational inertia
- **Theme 5: Demand for Federated Program** → Mintzberg's strategic apex and technostructure; NIST CSF governance maturity